
HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

COMPILED STUDY MATERIAL FOR MBA

JUNE 1, 2022

II SEMESTER

HUMAN RESOURCES MANAGEMENT

OBJECTIVES / LEARNING OUTCOMES:

- Effectively manage and plan key human resource functions within organizations
- Examine current issues, trends, practices, and processes in HRM
- Contribute to employee performance management and organizational effectiveness
- Problem-solve human resource challenges

Unit 1: Human resources management at work
Definition various definitions, Evolution, Nature of Human factor, HR Model, HRM as a profession The Human Resource Manager, Functions of HRM, Significance of HRM Personnel / HRM as a profession. Organizational Structure; Position and status of HR Manager, Line Authority staff authority The Environment Of Human Resource Management, The Internal Environment, Employer, Challenges Facing HRM, Strategic HRM, Current Issues and Trends in HR
Unit 2 : HR Functions
Job Analysis: A Basic Human Resource Tool, Human Resource Planning.. Human Resource Planning Process Recruitment, Methods of recruitment, Selection, Selection process, Orientation, Socialization Determinants Of Individual Financial Compensation, Compensation Plans & Business Strategy Basic determinants of compensation - Building employer's commitment - Pricing Managerial and Professional jobs - current issues in compensation. Incentive Compensation /Variable Pay various employee benefits and service
Unit 3 : Human resource Development & Training
Purposes of Training, need and rationale.- Role of Training - Training process Purposes of Performance Evaluation. Methods of Performance Appraisal Common Appraisal Problems Career Planning, career stages,. Factors Affecting Career Planning Essentials of success in career planning
Unit 4 : Employee safety and Health
The Nature And Role Of Safety And Health , Developing Safety Programs workplace Violence, Types of Working Environment, Safety Education Occupational Safety - causes of accidents and its prevention - supervisor's role in safety - an overview Labor welfare activities. Sources of Stress, Methods of Stress relievers, Role of HR Managing Stress
Unit 5 : Employee participation and relation
Participation and motivation - types and degree of participation - structure and functions of participation in management Benefits of participation; Managing grievances and Discipline Grievance Procedure – collective Bargaining - Settlement of Disputes, Industrial Relations Defined. Case study managing attrition at Microsoft.
Unit 6 : Future Challenges of HR
Unit 6: Managing Human Resources in future - Gen Y; Managing Human Resources in

International Business.Eight Keys to Global Human Resource Management of Expatriates.
Human Resource

Reference:

1. Nick Wilton-An Introduction to Human Resource management-Sage.
2. MonappaArun&SaiyadainMirza- Personnel Management - Tata McGraw Hill.
3. Tyson Shaun &York Alfred-Essentials of HRM-Butterworth Heinemann
4. Fisher Cynthia D, Schsenfeldt Lyle F, Shaw James B- Human Resources management- All India Publishers and Distributors.
5. Dressler Gary - Human Resource Management- Prentice Hall of India.
6. DeCenzo David A and Robbins Stephen P- Personnel/Human Resources management-Prentice Hall of India.
7. Ivancevich John M- Human Resources Management- Irwin McGraw Hill
8. Kossek Ellen Ernst &Block Richard N-Human Resources Management in the 21st Century- South Westem College Publishing.
9. Ashwathappa- Human Resource Management-McGraw Hill.
10. Dwivedi RS - A Text book of Human Resource Management -Vikas Publishing House, New Delhi.
11. Aquinas PG - Human Resource Management -Principles and Practice -Vikas Publishing House, New Delhi.

19MBA 25: HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT AND AUDIT

Workload : 4 hours per week - Total credits: 4
Examination : 2 hours 50 marks

Objective: A modest attempt to present a comprehensive treatment to concepts, principles, functions and techniques of human resource management in the context of various environmental factors in a modern organization.

Pedagogy: Lectures, assignments, practical exercises, discussions, seminars

Human resources management at work

Session 1 - Introduction to the concept of HRM

Session 2 - Human capital as a source of competitive advantage

Session 3 - Evolution of HRM as a field of study

Session 4 - Personnel Administration to Strategic HRM

Session 5 - Strategic Value of HRM for Employees and the Organization

Session 6 - HRM's contribution to profitability, efficiency, and effectiveness

Session 7 - Functions of HRM

Session 8 - Responsibilities of the HR Department

Session 9 - The HRM Process - Opportunities, Challenges, and Recent Trends in HRM

Session 10 - HR Model - HRM as a profession -The Human Resource Manager

Session 11- Organizational Structure - Position and status of HR Function - Line Authority staff authority - The Environment Of Human Resource Management - Challenges Facing HRM - Strategic HRM

Case Study - Employee Recognition Vs. Employee Equality

HR Functions

Session 12 - Work Design and Planning – Job Analysis - Types of Job Analysis

Session 13 - Job Design - Linking Job Analysis and Job Design to the HRM Process - Opportunities, Challenges Recent Developments in Job Analysis and Job Design

Session 14 - Implications of Demographics, Diversity, and Globalization for Job Design

- Session 15- Recruitment: Attracting the Right Talent - Methods of recruitment - Finding Talent in the External Labor Market - Finding Talent Internally
- Session 16 - Designing an HR Talent Inventory - Linking Recruitment to the HRM Process - Opportunities, Challenges, and Recent Developments in Recruiting Talent
- Session17 - Legal Dimensions of Recruitment: Equal Employment Opportunity and Discrimination
- Session 18 - Selection and Job Fit
- Session 19 - Interviews - Foundational Concepts in Designing and Evaluating Selection Methods - Increasing the Validity and Reliability of the Selection Process -Legal Issues in Selection - Opportunities, Challenges, and Recent Developments in Employee Selection and Job Fit
- Session 20 - Compensation and Incentives - Pay Structures - Types of Pay - Linking Compensation to the HRM Process
- Assignment 1 - Draw up a job analysis of a job role assigned*

Human resource Development

- Session 21 - Purposes of Training - The Training Process: An Overview
- Session 22- Training Needs Assessment - Forms - Linking Training and Development to the HRM Process - Opportunities, Challenges, and Recent Trends in Training and Development
- Session 23 - Managing Employee Competency - Employee Attitudes - Performance Appraisal and Importance
- Session 24 - Performance Measurement - Linking Performance Appraisal to the HRM Process - Opportunities, Challenges, and Recent Developments in Performance Management Performance Evaluation - Methods of Performance Appraisal
- Session 25 - Career Planning
- Case Study : “Employees’ as a source of competitive advantage”*
- Assignment 2*

Employee safety and Health

- Session 26 - Nature And Role Of Safety And Health
- Session 27 - Safety Programs
- Session 28 - Working Environment, Accidents and Prevention - supervisor's role
- Session 29 - Labor welfare activities
- Session 30 - Sources of Stress - Methods of Stress relievers - Role of HR in Managing Stress

Employee participation and relation

- Session 31 - Managing Employee Attitudes - Participation and motivation
- Session 32 - Types and degree of participation - Benefits of participation

Session 33- Managing grievances and Discipline

Session 34 - Grievance Procedure – collective Bargaining - Settlement of Disputes, Industrial Relations

Assignment 3 - Methods of improving employee competency - An Evaluation of three companies

Future Challenges of HR

Session 35 - Managing Human Resources in future - Gen Y

Session 36- Managing Human Resources in International Business

Session 37 - Human Resource Accounting and Audit

Session 38- Globalization and HRM - International Assignments and Political Instability

Session 39- Technology and HRM

Session 40 -HR Legislation and the Future of HRM - Generational Differences - Future Trends in Human Capital and Talent Management

Value Added Unit

Global HRM and the use of computer and the internet (HRIS)

References

1. Nick Wilton-An Introduction to Human Resource management-Sage.
2. Monappa Arun & Saiyadain Mirza- Personnel Management - Tata McGraw Hill.
3. Tyson Shaun & York Alfred-Essentials of HRM-Butterworth Heinemann
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10. Dwivedi RS - A Text book of Human Resource Management -Vikas Publishing House, New Delhi.
11. Aquinas PG - Human Resource Management -Principles and Practice -Vikas Publishing House, New Delhi.
12. Human Resource Management - John S. Bernardien, Manav Books, Indian Edition

Unit 1 Human resources management at work

Definition various definitions, Evolution, Nature of Human factor, HR Model, HRM as a profession The Human Resource Manager, Functions of HRM, Significance of HRM Personnel / HRM as a profession. Organizational Structure; Position and status of HR Manager, Line Authority staff authority The Environment Of Human Resource Management, The Internal Environment, Employer, Challenges Facing HRM, Strategic HRM, Current Issues and Trends in HR

UNIT 1 - HUMAN RESOURE MANAGEMENT AT WORK

INTRODUCTION

Human Resource management is the most happening function as of now. This is so because people offer competitive advantage to a firm and managing people is the domain of HRM. An organization enjoys competitive advantage when it is the only one which can offer a product at a price and at quality while its competitors cannot do so. Fast changes are taking place in the business environment. An organization must have the ability to absorb these changes at a fast rate than in the past, not simply to prove its competency alone but to justify its existence in the dynamic business world as well. All organizations, whether large or small must ensure themselves that they have the competent people capable of accepting this challenge.

Human resource management is a relatively modern concept, which involves arrange of ideas and practices in managing people. Human resource is the most valuable resource in any organization because it can function only through people.

Human Resource Management has come to be recognized as an inherent part of management, which is concerned with the human resources of an organization. Its objective is the maintenance of better human relations in the organization by the development, application and evaluation of policies, procedures and programs relating to human resources to optimize their contribution towards the realization of organizational objectives.

In other words, HRM is concerned with getting better results with the collaboration of people. It is an integral but distinctive part of management, concerned with people at work and their relationships within the enterprise. HRM helps in attaining maximum individual development, desirable working relationship between employees and employers, employees and employees, and effective modeling of human resources as contrasted with physical resources. It is the recruitment, selection, development, utilization, compensation and motivation of human resources by the organization.

CONCEPT OF HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

What exactly is human resource management? Many people find HRM to be an unclear and strange concept. 'This is not simply because of having variety of meanings to this term. This confusion is mainly due to the different interpretations found in articles and books about human resource management.

HRM is the philosophy of people management based on the belief that human resources are extremely important for sustained business success. An organization acquires competitive advantage by using its people effectively and utilizing their expertise to meet clearly defined objectives. HRM is aimed at recruiting capable, flexible and committed people. Managing and rewarding their performance and developing key competencies.

MEANING AND DEFINITION

Human Resource Management is the process of recruitment, selection of employee, providing proper orientation and induction, providing proper training and the developing skills, assessment of employee (performance of appraisal), providing proper compensation and benefits, motivating, maintaining proper relations with labor and with trade unions, maintaining employee's safety, welfare and health by complying with labor laws of concern state or country.

Many great scholars had defined human resource management in different ways and with different words, but the core meaning of the human resource management deals with how to manage people or employees in the organization.

Edwin Flippo defines- HRM as “planning, organizing, directing, controlling of procurement, development, compensation, integration, maintenance and separation of human resources to the end that individual, organizational and social objectives are achieved.”

The National Institute of Personal Management (NIPM) of India has defined human resources personal management as “that part of management which is concerned with people at work and with their relationship within an enterprise. Its aim is to bring together and develop into an effective organization of the men and women who make up enterprise and having regard for the well – being of the individuals and of working groups, to enable them to make their best contribution to its success”.

Scope of HRM

The scope of HRM is indeed vast. All major activities in the working life of a worker – from the time of his or her entry into an organization until he or she leaves the organizations comes under the purview of HRM. The major HRM activities include HR planning, job analysis, job design, employee hiring, employee and executive remuneration, employee motivation, employee maintenance, industrial relations and prospects of HRM.

The scope of Human Resources Management extends to:

- All the decisions, strategies, factors, principles, operations, practices, functions, activities and methods related to the management of people as employees in any type of organization.
- All the dimensions related to people in their employment relationships, and all the dynamics that flow from it.

Figure 1.1: Scope of HRM

The scope of HRM is really vast. All major activities in the working life of a worker – from the time of his or her entry into an organization until he or she leaves it comes under the purview of HRM. American Society for Training and Development (ASTD) conducted fairly an exhaustive study in this field and identified nine broad areas of activities of HRM.

These are given below:

- Human Resource Planning
- Design of the Organization and Job
- Selection and Staffing
- Training and Development
- Organizational Development
- Compensation and Benefits
- Employee Assistance
- Union/Labour Relations
- Personnel Research and Information System

a) **Human Resource Planning:** The objective of HR Planning is to ensure that the organization has the right types of persons at the right time at the right place. It prepares human resources inventory with a view to assess present and future needs, availability and possible shortages in human resource. Thereupon, HR Planning forecast demand and supplies and identify sources of selection. HR Planning

develops strategies both long-term and short-term, to meet the manpower requirement.

- b) **Design of Organization and Job:** This is the task of laying down organization structure, authority, relationship and responsibilities. This will also mean definition of work contents for each position in the organization. This is done by “job description”. Another important step is “Job specification”. Job specification identifies the attributes of persons who will be most suitable for each job which is defined by job description.
- c) **Selection and Staffing:** This is the process of recruitment and selection of staff. This involves matching people and their expectations with which the job specifications and career path available within the organization.
- d) **Training and Development:** This involves an organized attempt to find out training needs of the individuals to meet the knowledge and skill which is needed not only to perform current job but also to fulfil the future needs of the organization.
- e) **Organizational Development:** This is an important aspect whereby “Synergetic effect” is generated in an organization i.e. healthy interpersonal and inter-group relationship within the organization.
- f) **Compensation and Benefits:** This is the area of wages and salaries administration where wages and compensations are fixed scientifically to meet fairness and equity criteria. In addition labour welfare measures are involved which include benefits and services.
- g) **Employee Assistance:** Each employee is unique in character, personality, expectation and temperament. By and large each one of them faces problems everyday. Some are personal some are official. In their case he or she remains worried. Such worries must be removed to make him or her more productive and happy.
- h) **Union-Labour Relations:** Healthy Industrial and Labour relations are very important for enhancing peace and productivity in an organization. This is one of the areas of HRM.
- i) **Personnel Research and Information System:** Knowledge on behavioral science and industrial psychology throws better insight into the workers expectations, aspirations and behaviour. Advancement of technology of product and production methods have created working environment which are much different from the past. Globalization of

economy has increased competition many fold. Science of ergonomics gives better ideas of doing a work more conveniently by an employee. Thus, continuous research in HR areas is an unavoidable requirement. It must also take special care for improving exchange of information through effective communication systems on a continuous basis especially on moral and motivation.

HRM is a broad concept; personnel management (PM) and Human resource development (HRD) are a part of HRM.

Objectives of HRM

The primary objective of HRM is to ensure the availability of competent and willing workforce to an organization. The specific objectives include the following:

- 1) Human capital : assisting the organization in obtaining the right number and types of employees to fulfill its strategic and operational goals
- 2) Developing organizational climate: helping to create a climate in which employees are encouraged to develop and utilize their skills to the fullest and to employ the skills and abilities of the workforce efficiently
- 3) Helping to maintain performance standards and increase productivity through effective job design; providing adequate orientation, training and development; providing performance-related feedback; and ensuring effective two-way communication.
- 4) Helping to establish and maintain a harmonious employer/employee relationship
- 5) Helping to create and maintain a safe and healthy work environment

- 6) Developing programs to meet the economic, psychological, and social needs of the employees and helping the organization to retain the productive employees
- 7) Ensuring that the organization is in compliance with provincial/territorial and federal laws affecting the workplace (such as human rights, employment equity, occupational health and safety, employment standards, and labour relations legislation). To help the organization to reach its goals
- 8) To provide organization with well-trained and well-motivated employees
- 9) To increase the employees satisfaction and self-actualization
- 10) To develop and maintain the quality of work life
- 11) To communicate HR policies to all employees.
- 12) To help maintain ethical polices and behavior.

The above stated HRM objectives can be summarized under four specific objectives: societal, organizational, and functional and personnel.

Figure 1.2: Objectives of HRM

- 1) **Societal Objectives:** seek to ensure that the organization becomes socially responsible to the needs and challenges of the society while minimizing the negative impact of such demands upon the organization. The failure of the organizations to use their resources for the society's benefit in ethical ways may lead to restriction.

- 2) **Organizational Objectives:** it recognizes the role of HRM in bringing about organizational effectiveness. It makes sure that HRM is not a standalone department, but rather a means to assist the organization with its primary objectives. The HR department exists to serve the rest of the organization.
- 3) **Functional Objectives:** is to maintain the department's contribution at a level appropriate to the organization's needs. Human resources are to be adjusted to suit the organization's demands. The department's value should not become too expensive at the cost of the organization it serves.
- 4) **Personnel Objectives:** it is to assist employees in achieving their personal goals, at least as far as these goals enhance the individual's contribution to the organization. Personal objectives of employees must be met if they are to be maintained, retained and motivated. Otherwise employee performance and satisfaction may decline giving rise to employee turnover.

Table 1.1 HRM Objectives and Functions

HRM Objectives		Supporting Functions
1.	Societal Objectives	Legal compliance Benefits Union- management relations
2.	Organizational Objectives	Human Resource Planning Employee relations Selection Training and development Appraisal Placement Assessment
3.	Functional Objectives	Appraisal Placement Assessment
4.	Personal Objectives	Training and development Appraisal Placement Compensation Assessment

Functions of HRM

Human Resources management has an important role to play in equipping organizations to meet the challenges of an expanding and increasingly competitive sector. Increase in staff numbers, contractual diversification and changes in demographic profile which compel the HR managers to reconfigure the role and significance of human resources management. The functions are responsive to current staffing needs, but can be proactive in reshaping organizational objectives. All the functions of HRM are correlated with the core objectives of HRM (Table 1.1). For example personal objectives is sought to be realized through functions like remuneration, assessment etc.

Figure 1.3 : Functions of HRM

HR management can be thought of as seven interlinked functions taking place within organizations, as depicted in Figure 1.3. Additionally, external forces—legal, economic, technological, global, environmental, cultural/geographic, political, and social—significantly affect how HR functions are designed, managed, and changed. The functions can be grouped as follows:

- **Strategic HR Management:** As a part of maintaining organizational competitiveness, strategic planning for HR effectiveness can be increased through the use of HR metrics and HR technology. Human resource planning (HRP) function determine the number and type of employees needed to accomplish organizational goals. HRP includes creating venture teams with a balanced skill-mix, recruiting the right people, and voluntary team assignment. This function analyzes and determines personnel needs in order to create effective innovation teams. The basic HRP strategy is staffing and employee development.
- **Equal Employment Opportunity:** Compliance with equal employment opportunity (EEO) laws and regulations affects all other HR activities.
- **Staffing:** The aim of staffing is to provide a sufficient supply of qualified individuals to fill jobs in an organization. Job analysis, recruitment and selection are the main functions under staffing.

Workers job design and job analysis laid the foundation for staffing by identifying what diverse people do in their jobs and how they are affected by them.

Job analysis is the process of describing the nature of a job and specifying the human requirements such as knowledge, skills, and experience needed to perform the job. The end result of job analysis is job description. Job description spells out work duties and activities of employees.

Through HR planning, managers anticipate the future supply of and demand for employees and the nature of workforce issues, including the retention of employees. So HRP precedes the actual selection of people for organization. These factors are used when recruiting applicants for job

openings. The selection process is concerned with choosing qualified individuals to fill those jobs. In the selection function, the most qualified applicants are selected for hiring from among the applicants based on the extent to which their abilities and skills are matching with the job.

- **Talent Management and Development:** Beginning with the orientation of new employees, talent management and development includes different types of training. Orientation is the first step towards helping a new employee to adjust himself to the new job and the employer. It is a method to acquaint new employees with particular aspects of their new job, including pay and benefit programmes, working hours and company rules and expectations.

Training and Development programs provide useful means of assuring that the employees are capable of performing their jobs at acceptable levels and also more than that. All the organizations provide training for new and in experienced employee. In addition, organization often provide both on the job and off the job training programmes for those employees whose jobs are undergoing change.

Likewise, HR development and succession planning of employees and managers is necessary to prepare for future challenges. Career planning has developed as result of the desire of many employees to grow in their jobs and to advance in their career. Career planning activities include assessing an individual employee's potential for growth and advancement in the organization.

Performance appraisal includes encouraging risk taking, demanding innovation, generating or adopting new tasks, peer evaluation, frequent evaluations, and auditing innovation processes.

This function monitors employee performance to ensure that it is at acceptable levels. This strategy appraises individual and team performance so that there is a link between individual innovativeness and company profitability. Which tasks should be appraised and who should assess employees' performance are also taken into account.

- **Total Rewards:** Compensation in the form of pay, incentives and benefits are the rewards given to the employees for performing organizational work. Compensation management is the method for determining how much employees should be paid for performing certain jobs. Compensation affects staffing in that people are generally attracted to organizations offering a higher level of pay in exchange for the work

performed. To be competitive, employers develop and refine their basic compensation systems and may use variable pay programs such as incentive rewards, promotion from within the team, recognition rewards, balancing team and individual rewards etc. This function uses rewards to motivate personnel to achieve an organization's goals of productivity, innovation and profitability. Compensation is also related to employee development in that it provides an important incentive in motivating employees to higher levels of job performance to higher paying jobs in the organization.

Benefits are another form of compensation to employees other than direct pay for the work performed. Benefits include both legally required items and those offered at employer's discretion. Benefits are primarily related to the area of employee maintenance as they provide for many basic employee needs.

- **Risk Management and Worker Protection:** HRM addresses various workplace risks to ensure protection of workers by meeting legal requirements and being more responsive to concerns for workplace health and safety along with disaster and recovery planning.
- **Employee and Labor Relations:** The relationship between managers and their employees must be handled legally and effectively. Employer and employee rights must be addressed. It is important to develop, communicate, and update HR policies and procedures so that managers and employees alike know what is expected. In some organizations, union/management relations must be addressed as well. The term labour relation refers to the interaction with employees who are represented by a trade union. Unions are organization of employees who join together to obtain more voice in decisions affecting wages, benefits, working conditions and other aspects of employment. With regard to labour relations the major function of HR personnel includes negotiating with the unions regarding wages, service conditions and resolving disputes and grievances.

Role of HRM

The role of HRM is to plan, develop and administer policies and programs designed to make optimum use of an organizations human resources. It is that part of management which is concerned with the people at work and with their

relationship within enterprises. Its objectives are: (a) effective utilization of human resources, (b) desirable working relationships among all members of the organizations, and (c) maximum individual development. Human resources function as primarily administrative and professional. HR staff focused on administering benefits and other payroll and operational functions and didn't think of themselves as playing a part in the firm's overall strategy.

HR professionals have an all encompassing role. They are required to have a thorough knowledge of the organization and its intricacies and complexities. The ultimate goal of every HR person should be to develop a linkage between the employee and organization because employee's commitment to the organization is crucial.

The first and foremost role of HR personnel is to impart continuous education to the employees about the changes and challenges facing the country in general and their organization in particular. The employees should know about the balance sheet of the company, sales progress, and diversification of plans, share price movements, turnover and other details about the company. The HR professionals should impart such knowledge to all employees through small booklets, video films and lectures.

The primary responsibilities of Human Resource managers are:

- To develop a thorough knowledge of corporate culture, plans and policies.
- To act as an internal change agent and consultant
- To initiate change and act as an expert and facilitator
- To actively involve in company's strategy formulation
- To keep communication line open between the HRD function and individuals and groups both within and outside the organization\
- To identify and evolve HRD strategies in consonance with overall business strategy.
- To facilitate the development of various organizational teams and their working relationship with other teams and individuals.
- To try and relate people and work so that the organization objectives are achieved efficiently and effectively.
- To diagnose problems and determine appropriate solution particularly in the human resource areas.
- To provide co-ordination and support services for the delivery of HRD programmes and services

- To evaluate the impact of an HRD intervention or to conduct research so as to identify, develop or test how HRD In general has improved individual and organizational performance.

Different management gurus have deliberated different roles for the HR manager based on the major responsibilities that they full fill in the organization. Few of the commonly accepted models are enumerated below.

Pat Mc Lagan has suggested nine roles that are played by HR practitioners

1. To bring the issues and trends concerning an organization's external and internal people to the attention of strategic decision makers and to recommend long term strategies to support organizational excellence and endurance.
2. To design and prepare HR systems and actions for implementation so that they can produce maximum impact on organizational performance and development.
3. To facilitate the development and implementation of strategies for transforming one's own organization by pursuing values and visions.
4. To create a positive relationship with the customer's by providing them with the best services; to utilize the resources to the maximum and to create commitment among the people who help the organization to meet the customers needs whether directly connected or indirectly connected to the organization.
5. To identify the learning needs hence to design and develop structured learning programmes and materials to help accelerate learning for individuals and groups.
6. To enable the individuals and groups to work in new situations and to expend \and change their views so that people in power move from authoritarian to participative models of leadership.
7. To help employees to assess their competencies, values and goals so that they can identify, plan and implement development plans.
8. He also assists the individual employee to add values in the workplace and to focus on the interventions and interpersonal skills for helping people change and sustain change.
9. He assesses the HRD practices and programmes and their impact and to communicate results so that the organization and its people accelerate their change and development.

According to Dave Ulrich HR play's four key roles.

1. **Strategic Partner Role**-turning strategy into results by building organizations that create value;
2. **Change Agent Role**- making change happen, and in particular, help it happen fast
3. **Employees Champion Role**—managing the talent or the intellectual capital within a firm
4. **Administrative Role**—trying to get things to happen better, faster and cheaper.

The role HR in organizations has undergone an extensive change and many organizations have gradually oriented themselves from the traditional personnel management to a human resources management approach. The basic approach of HRM is to perceive the organization as a whole. Its emphasis is not only on production and productivity but also on the quality of life. It seeks to achieve the paramount development of human resources and the utmost possible socio-economic development.

Current Classification of HR roles

According to R.L Mathis and J. H. Jackson (2010) several roles can be fulfilled by HR management. The nature and extent of these roles depend on both what upper management wants HR management to do and what competencies the HR staff have demonstrated. Three roles are typically identified for HR. The focus of each of them, as shown in Figure 1. is elaborated below:

Figure 1.4 : Current Classification of HR roles

1. Administrative Role of HR

The administrative role of HR management has been heavily oriented to administration and recordkeeping including essential legal paperwork and policy implementation. Major changes have happened in the administrative role of HR during the recent years. Two major shifts driving the transformation of the administrative role are: Greater use of technology and Outsourcing.

Technology has been widely used to improve the administrative efficiency of HR and the responsiveness of HR to employees and managers, more HR functions are becoming available electronically or are being done on the Internet using Web-based technology. Technology is being used in most HR activities, from employment applications and employee benefits enrollments to e-learning using Internet-based resources.

Increasingly, many HR administrative functions are being outsourced to vendors. This outsourcing of HR administrative activities has grown dramatically in HR areas such as employee assistance (counseling), retirement planning, benefits administration, payroll services, and outplacement services.

2. Operational and Employee Advocate Role for HR

HR managers manage most HR activities in line with the strategies and operations that have been identified by management and serves as employee “champion” for employee issues and concerns.

HR often has been viewed as the “employee advocate” in organizations. They act as the voice for employee concerns, and spend considerable time on HR “crisis management,” dealing with employee problems that are both work-related and not work-related. Employee advocacy helps to ensure fair and equitable treatment for employees regardless of personal background or circumstances.

Sometimes the HR’s advocate role may create conflict with operating managers. However, without the HR advocate role, employers could face even more lawsuits and regulatory complaints than they do now.

The operational role requires HR professionals to cooperate with various departmental and operating managers and supervisors in order to identify and implement needed programs and policies in the organization. Operational activities are tactical in nature. Compliance with equal employment opportunity and other laws is ensured, employment applications are processed, current openings are filled through interviews, supervisors are trained, safety problems are resolved, and wage and benefit questions are answered. For carrying out these activities HR manager matches HR activities with the strategies of the organization.

3. Strategic Role for HR

The administrative role traditionally has been the dominant role for HR. However, as Figure 1.4 indicates that a broader transformation in HR is needed so that significantly less HR time and fewer HR staffs are used just for clerical work.

Differences between the operational and strategic roles exist in a number of HR areas. The strategic HR role means that HR professionals are proactive in addressing business realities and focusing on future business needs, such as strategic planning, compensation strategies, the performance of HR, and measuring its results. However, in some organizations, HR often does not play a key role in formulating the strategies for the organization as a whole; instead it merely carries them out through HR activities.

Many executives, managers, and HR professionals are increasingly seeing the need for HR management to become a greater strategic contributor to the “business” success of organizations. HR should be responsible for knowing what the true cost of human capital is for an employer. For example, it may cost two times key employees’ annual salaries to replace them if they leave. Turnover can be controlled through HR activities, and if it is successful in saving the company money with good retention and talent management strategies, those may be important contributions to the bottom line of organizational performance.

The role of HR as a *strategic business partner* is often described as “having a seat at the table,” and contributing to the strategic directions and success of the organization. That means HR is involved in *devising* strategy in addition to *implementing* strategy. Part of HR’s contribution is to have financial expertise and to produce financial results, not just to boost employee morale or administrative efficiencies. Therefore, a significant concern for chief financial officers (CFOs) is whether HR executives are equipped to help them to plan and meet financial requirements.

However, even though this strategic role of HR is recognized, many organizations still need to make significant progress toward fulfilling it. Some examples of areas where strategic contributions can be made by HR are:

- Evaluating mergers and acquisitions for organizational “compatibility,” structural changes, and staffing needs
- Conducting workforce planning to anticipate the retirement of employees at all levels and identify workforce expansion in organizational strategic plans
- Leading site selection efforts for new facilities or transferring operations to international outsourcing
- locations based on workforce needs
- Instituting HR management systems to reduce administrative time, equipment, and staff by using HR technology

- Working with executives to develop a revised sales
- compensation and incentives plan as new products

It is the era when for the competitive triumph of the organization there is a need to involve HRM significantly in an integrated manner, which demands such capabilities from the HR specialists.

The role of HR shifted from a facilitator to a functional peer with competencies in other functions, and is acknowledged as an equal partner by others. The HR is motivated to contribute to organizational objectives of profitability and customer satisfaction, and is seen as a vehicle for realization of quality development. The department has a responsibility for monitoring employee satisfaction, since it is seen as substitute to customer satisfaction.

According to McKinsey's 7-S framework model HR plays the role of a catalyst for the organization. According to this framework, effective organizational change is a complex relationship between seven S's. HRM is a total matching process between the three Hard S's (Strategy, Structure and Systems) and the four Soft S's (Style, Staff, Skills and Super-ordinate Goals). Clearly, all the S's have to complement each other and have to be aligned towards a single corporate vision for the organization to be effective. It has to be realized that most of the S's are determined directly or indirectly by the way Human Resources are managed, and therefore, *HRM must be a part of the total business strategy.*

FUTURE CHALLENGES BEFORE THE MANAGERS

Because of continuous changing socio-economic, technological and political conditions, the human resource managers of the future shall have to face more problems in the management of labour. The human resource managers of today may find themselves obsolete in the future due to changes in environment if they do not update themselves some of the important challenges which might be faced by the managers in the management of people in business and industry are discussed below:

1. **Increasing Size of Workforce:** The size of organisations is increasing. A large number of multinational organisations have grown over the years. The number of people working in the organisation has also increased. The management of increased workforce might create new problems and challenges as the workers are becoming more conscious of their rights.
2. **Increase in Education Level:** The governments of various countries are taking steps to eradicate illiteracy and increase the education level of their citizens. Educated consumers and workers will create very tough task for the future managers.
3. **Technological Advances:** With the changes coming in the wake of advanced technology, new jobs are created and many old jobs become redundant. There is a general apprehension of immediate unemployment. In the competitive world of today, industry cannot hope to survive for long with old technology. The problem, of unemployment resulting from modernization will be solved by properly assessing manpower needs and training of redundant employees in alternate skills.
4. **Changes in Political Environment:** There may be greater Government's interference in business to safeguard the interests of workers, consumers and the public at large. Government's participation in trade, commerce and industry will also pose many challenges before management. The Government may restrict the scope of private sector in certain areas in public interest. It does not mean chances of co-operation between the Government and private sector are ruled out. In fact, there will be more and more joint sector enterprises.

5. **Increasing Aspirations of Employees:** Considerable changes have been noted in the worker of today in comparison to his counterpart of 1950s. The workers are becoming more aware of their higher level needs and this awareness would intensify further in the future workers.

6. **Changing Psychosocial System:** In future, organisations will be required to make use of advanced technology in accomplishing their goals while satisfying human needs. In the traditional bureaucratic model, the organisations were designed to achieve technical functions with a little consideration given to the psychosocial system. But future management would be required to ensure effective participation of lower levels in the management of the organisation system.

7. **Computerized Information System:** In the past, the automation of manufacturing processes had a major effect upon the systems of production, storage, handling and packaging, etc. More recently, there has been and in the future there will be the impact of revolutionary computerized information system on management. This revolutionary development would cover two primary areas of personnel management which are as follows:

- (a) The use of electronic computers for the collection and processing of data, and
- (b) The direct application of computers in the managerial decision making process.

8. **Mobility of Professional Personnel :** Organisations will expand the use of—boundary agents whose primary function will be achieving coordination with the environment. One interesting fact will be an increase in the mobility of various managerial and professional personnel between organisations. As individuals develop greater technical and professional expertise, their services will be in greater demand by other organisations in the environment.

9. **Changes in Legal Environment:** Many changes are taking place in the legal framework within which the industrial relations systems in the country are now functioning. It is the duty of the human resource or personnel executive to be aware of these changes and to bring about necessary adjustments within the organisations so that greater utilization of human resources can be achieved. This, indeed, is and would remain a major challenge for the personnel executive.

10. **Management of Human Relations:** On the ‘industrial relations’ front, things are not showing much improvement even after so many efforts by the

government in this direction. Though a large number of factors are responsible for industrial unrest but a very significant cause is the growth of multi unions in industrial complexes having different political affiliations. Under the present conditions, it appears that inter-union rivalries would grow more in the coming years and might create more problems in the industry.

Management of human relations in the future will be more complicated than it is today. Many of the new generation of employees will be more difficult to motivate than their predecessors. This will be in part the result of a change in value systems coupled with rising educational levels. Greater skepticism concerning large organizations and less reverence for authority figures will be more common. Unquestioning acceptance of rules and regulations will be less likely.

New Role of Human Resource Management

Human Resource Management in the 'New Millennium' has undergone a great revolution by questioning the accepted practices and re-inventing the organisations as well as structures. Many traditional practices have been thrown out. As an example, it can be seen that hierarchies are vanishing and there is greater emphasis on flat organisations.

It means a great deal of specialisation and skills. It also means upgrading the norms and standards of work as well as performance.

The new role of human resource management is much more strategic than before. Some of the new directions of the role of HRM can be summed up as follows:

A Facilitator of Change: To carry people through upheaval requires the true management of human resources.

An Integrated Approach to Management: Rather than being an isolated function, human resource is regarded as a core activity, one which shapes a company's values. In particular, this can have an impact on customer service.

A Mediator: Establishing and balancing the new and emerging aspirations and requirements of the company and the individual.

These changes, which are taking place, involve more commitment of the organisation to the development of people by improving performance and cutting costs. As a result of this, the duration of tenure, which was traditionally long standing, is now limited, future is becoming less certain, management opportunities are self-determined and motivational factors are more concerned with enhancing future employability rather than loyalty to the company and, at the same time, the rewards are going up in terms of higher salaries. The future creative careers, will require more involved approach to career development, which will include :

- Share employees with strategic partner organisations (customers of suppliers) in lieu of internal moves.
- Encourage independence: Employees may go elsewhere for career development, possibly to return in a few years.
- Fund-groups of employees to set-up as suppliers outside the organisation.
- Encourage employees to think of themselves as a business and of the organization's various departments as customers.
- Encourage employees to develop customers outside the organisation.
- Help employees develop self-marketing, networking and consultancy skills to enable them to search out, recognize or create new opportunities for both themselves and the organisation.
- Identify skilled individuals in other organisations who can contribute on a temporary project basis or part-time.

- Regularly expose employees to new people and ideas to stimulate innovation.
 - Balance external recruitment at all levels against internal promotion to encourage open competition, —competitive tendering for jobs to discourage seeing positions as someone’s territory which causes self-protective conformity.
 - Forster more cross-functional teamwork for self-development.
 - Eliminate the culture of valuing positions as career goals in favour of portraying a career as a succession of bigger projects, achievements and new skills learned. The concept of —position is part of the outside static concept of the organisation. Positions are out. Processes and projects are in.
- Abandon top-down performance appraisal in favour of self- appraisal based on internal customer satisfaction surveys and assessing people as you would suppliers.
 - Replace top-down assessment processes with self- assessment techniques and measure performance in term of results.

Functions of a Human Resource Manager

A human resource manager, charged with fulfilling the objectives of an organisation, should be a leader with high intellectual powers, a visionary and a philosopher who provides the initiative to shape the future in terms of leading the human beings in an organisation towards more prosperous and progressive policies.

- 1. Human Resource Man as an Intellectual:** The basic skill in the human resource field as compared to technologists or financial experts is the skill to communicate, articulate, understand and above all, to be an expert when it comes to putting policies and agreements in black and white. The personnel man’s skill lies in his command over the language. A personnel man has to deal with employees and he must possess the skills of conducting fruitful and systematic discussions and of communicating effectively. He should also be in a position to formulate principles and foresee the problems of the organisation. This means that he would require the mental ability to deal with his people in an intelligent manner as well as to understand what they are trying to say..
- 2. Human Resource Man as an Educator:** It is not enough that a human resource man has command-over the language, which, however, remains

his primary tool. He should be deeply interested in learning and also in achieving growth. Basically, human beings like to grow and realize their full potential. In order to harmonize the growth of individuals with that of the organisation, a personnel administrator must not only provide opportunities for his employees to learn, get the required training and assimilate new ideas but also he himself should be a teacher. A personnel man who simply pushes files and attends labour courts for conciliation purposes and other rituals of legal procedure for the settlement of industrial disputes is not a personnel administrator of the future.

- 3. Human Resource Man as a Discriminator:** A human resource administrator must have the capacity to discriminate between right and wrong, between that which is just and unjust and merit and non-merit. In other words, he should be a good judge when he sits on a selection board, a fair person when he advises on disciplinary matters and a good observer of right conduct in an organisation.
- 4. Human Resource Man as an Executive :** The human resource man must execute the decisions of the management and its policies with speed, accuracy and objectivity. He has to streamline the office, tone up the administration and set standards of performance. He has to coordinate the control functions in relation to the various other divisions and, in doing so he should be in a position to bring unity of purpose and direction in the activities of the personnel department. He must ask relevant questions and not be merely involved in the office routine whereby the status quo is maintained. He should have the inquisitiveness to find out causes of delay, tardy work and wasteful practices, and should be keen to eliminate those activities from the personnel functions which have either outlived their utility or are not consistent with the objectives and purposes of the organisation.
- 5. Human Resource Man as a Leader :**Being basically concerned with people or groups of people, and being placed in the group dynamics of various political and social functions of an organisation, a Human resource man must not shirk the role of leadership in an organisation. He, by setting his own example and by working towards the objectives of sound personnel management practices, must inspire his people and motivate them towards better performance. He should resolve the conflicts of different groups and build up teamwork in the organisation.

6. **Human Resource Man as a Humanist:** Deep faith in human values and empathy with human problems, especially in less developed countries, are the sine qua non for a Human resource man. He has to deal with people who toil at various levels and partake of their joys and sorrows. He must perform his functions with sensitivity and feeling.
7. **Human Resource Man as a Visionary:** While every leading function of an organisation must evolve its vision of the future, the primary responsibility for developing the social organisation towards purposive and progressive action fall on the personnel man. He should be a thinker who sets the pace for policy-making in an organisation in the area of human relations and should gradually work out new patterns of human relations management consistent with the needs of the organisation and the society. He must ponder on the social obligations of the enterprise, especially if it is in the public sector, where one has to work within the framework of social accountability. He should be in close touch with socio-economic changes in the country. He should be able to reasonably forecast future events and should constantly strive to meet the coming challenges.

Role and Challenges of Human Resource Manager

Human Resource (HR) Department is established in every organisation under the charge of an executive known as Human Resource Manager. This department plays an important role in the efficient management of human resources. The human resource department gives assistance and provides service to all other departments on personnel matters. Though personnel or human resource manager is a staff officer in relation to other departments of the enterprise, he has a line authority to get orders executed within his department. The human resource manager performs managerial functions like planning, organizing, directing and controlling to manage his department. He has also to perform certain operative functions like recruitment, selection, training, placement, etc., which the other line managers may entrust to him. He is basically a manager whatever may be the nature of his operative functions. The status of Human Resource Manager in an organisation depends upon the type of organisation structure.

Role of Human Resource Manager in an Organisation

In most of the big enterprises, human resource department is set up under the leadership of personnel manager who has specialised knowledge and skills. The human resource manager performs managerial as well as operative functions.

Since he is a manager, he performs the basic functions of management like planning, organising, directing and controlling to manage his department. He has also to perform certain operative functions of recruitment, selection, training, placement, etc., which the problems to management, the human resource managers attach highest priority to the settlement of industrial disputes than anything else.

The role of human resource management in industry is underlined by the complex and dynamic nature of environment under which the modern large-scale industries function. The impact of technology on organisation structure, politicization of workers' unions, and the growing consciousness of industrial employees about their rights and privileges, have made the role of personnel management increasingly more important in industrial undertakings. The task has also been facilitated by the greater recognition of the value of human resources in industry and application of human resource development (HRD) techniques by the enlightened managers in **modern organizations**.

SUCCESSION PLANNING

Meaning of Succession Planning

Succession planning is the process or activities connected with the succession of persons to fill key positions in the organization hierarchy as vacancies arise. The focus of attention is towards 'which' person the succession planning is needed.

The focus is not more on career development but it is more towards what kind of person is required to fill the future vacancy. Succession planning focuses on identification of vacancies and locating the probable successor. For example in succession planning the key concern can be who will be next CEO or what will happen if the Marketing Manager retires in coming March.

IMPORTANCE OF SUCCESSION PLANNING

- Succession planning helps when there is a sudden need arises due to reason or retirement of a key employee.
- Individual employee comes to know in advance the level to which he can rise if he has the ability and aptitude for it.
- Individual employee or successor feels happy when he feels that organization is taking care of his talents and aspirations.
- Succession planning helps create loyalty towards the organization and improved motivation
- morale of individual employees.
- Organization gains stable workforce

- lesser employee turnover.
- Ultimately organization becomes successful in accomplishing its goals effectively.

CAREER PLANNING

Career planning is the process or activities offered by the organization to individuals to identify strengths, weaknesses, specific goals and jobs they would like to occupy.

Career as a concept means a lifelong sequences of professional, educational and developmental experiences that projects an individual through the world of work. It is a sequence of positions occupied by a person during his life. Career may also be defined as amalgamation of changes in values, attitudes and motivation that occurs as a person grows older.

In career planning, organization is concerned with strategic questions of career development. Further the organization is concerned about if it should employ more graduates, more engineers, more scientists or more accountants etc. Career planning provides picture of succession plan for employees as per organizational needs. It focuses on the basis of performance, experience, could be placed where, when and how.

Career planning is a process of integrating the employees' needs and aspirations with organizational requirements.

Objectives of Career Planning

1. Build commitment in the individual
2. Develop long-range perspective
3. Reduce personal turnover expenses
4. Lessen employee obsolescence
5. Ensure organizational effectiveness
6. Allow individual to achieve personal and work related goals.

Question Bank

1. Majority of the disputes in industries is (are) related to the problem of
 - a. Wages
 - b. Salaries
 - c. Benefits
 - d. All of the aboveanswer - d
2. The _____ programme once installed must be continued on a permanent basis.
 - a. Job evaluation
 - b. Training & Development
 - c. Recruitment
 - d. All of the aboveanswer - a
3. Which of the following is not a function normally performed by HR department?
 - (a) Accounting
 - (b) Recruitment and Selection

- (c) Pay and Reward (d) Employee Relations

answer - a

4. HRM is_____

- (a) Employee oriented
- (b) Employer oriented
- (c) Legally oriented
- (d) None of the above

answer - a

5. Scope of the HRM includes ___

- (a) Retirement and separation of employees
- (b) HR training and development
- (c) Industrial relations
- (d) All of the above

answer -d

6. HRM is_____

- (a) A staff function
- (b) A line function
- (c) A staff function, line function and accounting function
- (d) All of the above

answer a

7. The objectives of HRM are categorized as ___

- (a) Personal objectives
- (b) Functional objectives
- (c) Organisational and social objectives
- (d) All of the above

answer- d

8. The scope of HRM does not include ___

- (a) Retirement of employees
- (b) Manpower planning
- (c) Training of employees
- (d) Maintenance of accounts

answer -b

9 . The meaning of the acronym 'SHRM' is ___

- (a) Short-term Human Resource Management
- (b) Strategic Human Resource Management
- (c) Strategestic Human Resource Management
- (d) Strategic Humane Resource Management

answer - b

10. Recruitment is widely viewed as a ___

- (a) Positive process
- (b) Negative process
- (c) Positive as well as negative process
- (d) None of the above processes

answer - b

11. Recruitment policy usually highlights need for establishing ___

- (a) Job specification
- (b) Job analysis
- (c) Job description
- (d) None of the above

answer - a

12. The process of developing the applicant's pool for job openings in an organization is called_____

- (a) Hiring
- (b) Recruitment
- (c) Selection
- (d) Retention

answer - a

13. A brief write-up of what the job is all about is ___

- (a) Job finding
- (b) Job summary
- (c) Job analysis
- (d) Job specification

answer - d

14. HRM differs from PM both in _____ and _____

- a. Definitions and functions
- b. Scope and orientation
- c. Functions and objectives
- d. None of the above

answer -b

15. Organisations need to evolve HR policies as they ensure _____ and _____ in treating people.

- a. Constancy and similarity
- b. Intention and safety
- c. Consistency and uniformity
- d. None of the above

answer -c

16. In which year did the term HRM emerge?

- a. 1970
- b. 1990

- B. Role analysis
- C. Performance appraisal
- D. All of the above

answer - d

23. _____ can be defined as a written record of the duties, responsibilities and conditions of job.

- A. Job description
- B. Job specification
- C. Job profile
- D. None of the above

answer - a

24. HRD process variable include

- A. Role clarity
- B. Work planning
- C. Better communication
- D. All of the above

answer - d

25- The following is (are) included in salary survey.

- A. Average salary
- B. Inflation indicators
- C. Salary budget averages
- D. All of the above

answer - d

26- The process of analyzing jobs from which job descriptions are developed are called_____.

- A. Job analysis
- B. Job evaluation
- C. Job enrichment
- D. Job enlargement

answer - a

27- Which pay is one of the most crucial pay given to the employee & also shown in the pay structure?

- A. Performance
- B. Strategic
- C. Bonus
- D. Commission

answer - a

28- What is that describes the duties of the job, authority relationship, skills requirement, conditions of work etc.

- A. Job analysis
- B. Job enlargement
- C. Job enrichment
- D. Job evaluation

Answer - a

29) The focus of Human Resource Management revolves around

- A) Machine
- B) Money
- C) Men
- D) none of the above

Answer:- c

30) Demand for human resources and management is created by

- A Expansion of industry
- B Shortage of labor
- C Abundance of capital
- D. none of the above

Answer -a

31. Workforce planning involves all of the following except

- (A) Examining production plans in a factory.
- (B) Organizing the training of staff.
- (C) Forecasting future personnel requirements.
- (D) Preparing and maintaining personnel records.

Answer - a

31. Ineffective planning of workforce would be highlighted by

- (A) Recruitment and selection problems.
- (B) The need to outsource some of the production.
- (C) A need to offer retraining to current employees.
- (D) An opportunity to increase the use of mechanization.

Answer - a

32. An advantage of recruitment from outside the company is

- (A) that it is cheaper than internal recruitment.
- (B) that it brings in new experience and skills to the firm.
- (C) that there is no need to advertise the vacancy.
- (D) that it avoids jealousy within the firm.

Answer - b

33. The first human development report was published in

- A.1990
- B.1991
- C.1992
- D.1993

Answer - a

34. HRD ways in education planning is/are

- A. Manpower approach
- B. Social demand approach
- C. Rate of return approach
- D. All the above

Answer - d

35. The most important indicators of HRD

- A. Those which measure a country's stock of human capital
- B. Those which measure the additions to this stock
- C. Both A and B
- D. None

Answer - c

36. Which of the following term contains information regarding machines and equipments used at workplace

- A. Job analysis
- B. Job specification
- C. Job description
- C. Job evaluation

Answer - c

37. Which of the following is a stated outcome of job analysis?

- A. Job description
- B. Job specification
- C. Job evaluation
- D. All of the given options

Answer - d

38. Job evaluation is based on the

- A. Physical skills required by the job
- B. Relative job worth for an organization
- C. Complexity of the job of perform
- D. Conceptual skill required by the job

Answer - b

39. Reward offered to labors involved in production, are categorized as

- A. Salary
- B. Fringe benefits
- C. Wage
- D. Commission

Answer -c

Self Assessment Questions -

- 1) Explain the functions of human resource management.
- 2) Define HRM? What are its functions and objectives?
- 3) Elucidate the roles of HR manager in an organization.
- 4) Explain the qualities required by a human resource manager to be successful.
- 5) Describe the scope of HR in 21st century
- 6) Explain the future challenges faced by HR manager.
- 7) Describe the importance of HR department to a organization
- 8) Explain the activities performed by HR department

Unit 2 HR Functions

Job Analysis: A Basic Human Resource Tool, Human Resource Planning.. Human Resource Planning Process Recruitment, Methods of recruitment, Selection, Selection process, Orientation ,Socialization Determinants Of Individual Financial Compensation, Compensation Plans & Business Strategy Basic determinants of compensation - Building employer's commitment - Pricing Managerial and Professional jobs - current issues in compensation. Incentive Compensation /Variable Pay various employee benefits and service

UNIT - 2 : HUMAN RESOURCE FUNCTIONS

Introduction

As told in the last chapter Human resource management has started to play a significant role in the overall strategic development of the organization. At present HR strategies are designed in tune with the overall business strategy of the organization. HR strategy should sub serve the interest of the organization, translating firm's goals and objectives into a consistent, integrated and complimentary set of programmes and policies for managing people.

First part of Human resource strategy is HRP – Human Resource Planning. All other HR activities like employee hiring, training and development, remuneration, appraisal and labour relations are derived from HRP. HR planning is important in a wide variety of industries and firms. HR planning affects what employers do when recruiting, selecting, and retaining people, and of course these actions affect organizational results and success. The challenges caused by changing economic conditions during recent year's show why HR workforce planning should occur.

Staffing an organization is an HR activity that is both strategic and operational in nature. As the HR Headline indicates, HR planning is important in a wide variety of industries and firms. HR planning affects what employers do when recruiting, selecting, and retaining people, and, of course these actions affect organizational results and success. Human Resources planning mean different means to different organizations. To some companies, human resources planning mean management development. It involve helping executives to make better decisions, communicate more effectively, and know more about the firm. The purpose of HRP is to make the manager a better equipped for facing the present and future.

Human Resource Planning (HRP)

Human resource planning is important for helping both organizations and employees to prepare for the future. The basic goal of human resource planning is to predict the future and based on these predictions, implement programmes to avoid anticipated problems. Very briefly humans resource planning is the process of examining an organization's or individual's future human resource needs for instance, what types of skills will be needed for jobs of the future compared to future human resource capabilities (such as the types of skilled employees you already have) and developing human resource policies and practices to address potential problems for example, implementing training programmes to avoid skill deficiencies.

Definition of Human Resource Planning

According to Vetter, "HRP is the process by which management determines how the organization should move from its current man power position to desired manpower position. Through planning, management strives to have the right time, doing things which result in both the organization and individual receiving maximum long run benefits".

According to Gordon Mc Beath, "HRP is concerned with two things: Planning of manpower requirements and Planning of Manpower supplies".

According to Beach, "HRP is a process of determining and assuming that the organization will have an adequate number of qualified persons, available at proper times, performing jobs which meet the needs of the enterprise and which provides satisfaction for the individuals involved"

Simply HRP can be understood as the process of forecasting an organization's future demands for and supply of the right type of people in the right number. In other words HRP is the process of determining manpower needs and formulating plans to meet these needs.

HRP is a Four-Phased Process.

- **The first phase** involves the gathering and analysis of data through manpower inventories and forecasts,
 - **The second phase** consists of establishing manpower objectives and policies and gaining top management approval of these.
 - **The third phase** involves designing and implementing plans and promotions to enable the organization to achieve its manpower objectives.
 - **The fourth phase** is concerned with control and evaluation of manpower plans to facilitate progress in order to benefit both the organization and the individual. The long run view means that gains may be sacrificed in the short run for the future grounds. The planning process enables the organization to identify what its manpower needs is and what potential manpower problems required current action. This leads to more effective and efficient performance.
-

Nature of HRP

Human resource planning is the process of analyzing and identifying the availability and the need for human resources so that the organization can meet its objectives. The focus of HR planning is to ensure that the organization has the right number of human resources, with the right capabilities, at the right times, and in the right places. In HR planning, an organization must consider the availability and allocation of people to jobs over long periods of time, not just for the next month or the next year¹.

HRP is a sub system in the total organizational planning. Actions may include shifting employees to other jobs in the organization, laying off employees or otherwise cutting back the number of employees, developing present employees, and/or increasing the number of employees in certain areas. Factors to consider include the current employees' knowledge, skills, and abilities and the expected vacancies resulting from retirements, promotions, transfers, and discharges. To do this, HR planning requires efforts by HR professionals working with executives and managers.

Objectives of Human Resource Planning

-
1. To ensure optimum utilization of human resources currently available in the organization.
 2. To assess or forecast the future skill requirement of the organization.
 3. To provide control measures to ensure that necessary resources are available as and when required.
 4. A series of specified reasons are there that attaches importance to manpower planning and forecasting exercises. They are elaborated below:
 - To link manpower planning with the organizational planning
 - To determine recruitment levels.
 - To anticipate redundancies.
-

- To determine optimum training levels.
- To provide a basis for management development programs.
- To cost the manpower.
- To assist productivity bargaining.
- To assess future accommodation requirement.
- To study the cost of overheads and value of service functions.
- To decide whether certain activity needs to be subcontracted, etc.

HRP exists as a part of planning process of business. This is the activity that aims to coordinate the requirements for the availability of the different types of employers. The major activities are the forecasting, (future requirements), inventorying (present strength), anticipating (comparison of present and future requirements) and planning (necessary program to meet the requirements).

The HR forecasts are responsible for estimating the number of people and the jobs needed by an organization to achieve its objectives and realize its plans in the most efficient and effective manner.

HR needs are computed by subtracting HR supplies or number of the employees available from expected HR demands or number of people required to produce a desired level of outcome. The objective of HR is to provide right personnel for the right work and optimum utilization of the existing human resources.

The objectives of human resource planning may be summarized as below:

- ***Forecasting Human Resources Requirements:*** HRP is essential to determine the future needs of HR in an organization. In the absence of this plan it is very difficult to provide the right kind of people at the right time.
- ***Effective Management of Change:*** Proper planning is required to cope with changes in the different aspects which affect the organization. These changes need continuation of allocation/ reallocation and effective utilization of HR in organization.
- ***Realizing the Organizational Goals:*** In order to meet the expansion and other organizational activities the organizational HR planning is essential.
- ***Promoting Employees:*** HRP gives the feedback in the form of employee data which can be used in decision-making in promotional opportunities to be made available for the organization.
- ***Effective Utilization of HR:*** The data base will provide the useful information in identifying surplus and deficiency in human resources. The objective of HRP is to maintain and improve the organizational capacity to reach its goals by developing appropriate strategies that will result in the maximum contribution of HR.

Need for HRP in Organizations

Major reasons for the emphasis on HRP at the Macro level:

- 1) **Employment-Unemployment Situation:** Though in general the number of educated unemployment is on the rise, there is acute shortage for a variety of skills. This emphasizes on the need for more effective recruitment and employee retention.
- 2) **Technological Change:** The changes in production technologies, marketing methods and management techniques have been extensive and rapid. Their effect has been profound on the job contents and job contexts. These changes have caused problems relating to redundancies, retention and redeployment. All these suggest the need to plan manpower needs intensively and systematically.
- 3) **Demographic Change:** The changing profile of the work force in terms of age, sex, literacy, technical inputs and social background has implications for HRP.
- 4) **Skill Shortage:** Unemployment does not mean that the labour market is a buyer's market. Organizations generally become more complex and require a wide range of specialist skills that are rare and scarce. A problem arises in an organization when employees with such specialized skills leave.
- 5) **Governmental Influences:** Government control and changes in legislation with regard to affirmative action for disadvantaged groups, working conditions and hours of work, restrictions on women and child employment, casual and contract labour, etc. have stimulated the organizations to become involved in systematic HRP.
- 6) **Legislative Control:** The policies of "hire and fire" have gone. Now the legislation makes it difficult to reduce the size of an organization quickly and cheaply. It is easy to increase but difficult to shed the fat in terms of the numbers employed because of recent changes in labour law relating to lay-offs and closures. Those responsible for managing manpower must look far ahead and thus attempt to foresee manpower problems.
- 7) **Impact of the Pressure Group:** Pressure groups such as unions, politicians and persons displaced from land by location of giant enterprises have been raising contradictory pressure on enterprise management such as internal recruitment and promotion, preference to employees' children, displace person, sons of soil etc.
- 8) **Systems Approach:** The spread of system thinking and advent of the macro computer as the part of the on-going revolution in information technology which emphasizes planning and newer ways of handling voluminous personnel records.
- 9) **Lead Time:** The long lead time is necessary in the selection process and training and deployment of the employee to handle new knowledge and skills successfully.

Importance of HRP

HRP is the subsystem in the total organizational planning. Organizational planning includes managerial activities that set the company's objective for the future and determines the appropriate means for achieving those objectives. The importance of HRP is elaborated on the basis of the key roles that it is playing in the organization.

- 1. Future Personnel Needs:** Human resource planning is significant because it helps to determine the future personnel needs of the organization. If an organization is facing the problem of either surplus or deficiency in staff strength, then it is the result of the absence of effecting HR planning. All public sector enterprises find themselves overstaffed now as they never had any planning for personnel requirement and went of recruitment spree till late 1980's. The problem of excess staff has become such a prominent problem that many private sector units are resorting to VRS 'voluntary retirement scheme'. The excess of labor problem would have been there if the organization had good HRP system. Effective HRP system will also enable the organization to have good succession planning.
- 2. Part of Strategic Planning:** HRP has become an integral part of strategic planning of strategic planning. HRP provides inputs in strategy formulation process in terms of deciding whether the organization has got the right kind of human resources to carry out the given strategy. HRP is also necessary during the implementation stage in the form of deciding to make resource allocation decisions related to organization structure, process and human resources. In some organizations HRP play as significant role as strategic planning and HR issues are perceived as inherent in business management.
- 3. Creating Highly Talented Personnel:** Even though India has a great pool of educated unemployed, it is the discretion of HR manager that will enable the company to recruit the right person with right skills to the organization. Even the existing staff hope the job so frequently that organization face frequent shortage of manpower. Manpower planning in the form of skill development is required to help the organization in dealing with this problem of skilled manpower shortage
- 4. International Strategies:** An international expansion strategy of an organization is facilitated to a great extent by HR planning. The HR department's ability to fill key jobs with foreign nationals and reassignment of employees from within or across national borders is a major challenge that is being faced by international business. With the growing trend towards global operation, the need for HRP will as well will be the need to integrate HRP more closely with the organizations strategic plans. Without effective HRP and subsequent attention to employee recruitment, selection, placement, development, and career planning, the growing competition for foreign executives may lead to expensive and strategically descriptive turnover among key decision makers.
- 5. Foundation for Personnel Functions:** HRP provides essential information for designing and implementing personnel functions, such as recruitment, selection, training and development, personnel movement like transfers, promotions and layoffs.
- 6. Increasing Investments in Human Resources:** Organizations are making increasing investments in human resource development compelling the increased need for HRP. Organizations are realizing that human assets can increase in value more than the physical assets. An employee who gradually develops his/ her skills and abilities become a valuable asset for the organization. Organizations can make investments in its personnel either through direct training or job assignment and

the rupee value of such a trained, flexible, motivated productive workforce is difficult to determine. Top officials have started acknowledging that quality of work force is responsible for both short term and long term performance of the organization.

7. **Resistance to Change:** Employees are always reluctant whenever they hear about change and even about job rotation. Organizations cannot shift one employee from one department to another without any specific planning. Even for carrying out job rotation (shifting one employee from one department to another) there is a need to plan well ahead and match the skills required and existing skills of the employees.
8. **Uniting the Viewpoint of Line and Staff Managers:** HRP helps to unite the viewpoints of line and staff managers. Though HRP is initiated and executed by the corporate staff, it requires the input and cooperation of all managers within an organization. Each department manager knows about the issues faced by his department more than anyone else. So communication between HR staff and line managers is essential for the success of HR Planning and development.
9. **Succession Planning:** Human Resource Planning prepares people for future challenges. The 'stars' are picked up, trained, assessed and assisted continuously so that when the time comes such trained employees can quickly take the responsibilities and position of their boss or seniors as and when situation arrives.
10. **Other Benefits:** (a) HRP helps in judging the effectiveness of manpower policies and programmes of management. (b) It develops awareness on effective utilization of human resources for the overall development of organization. (c) It facilitates selection and training of employees with adequate knowledge, experience and aptitudes so as to carry on and achieve the organizational objectives (d) HRP encourages the company to review and modify its human resource policies and practices and to examine the way of utilizing the human resources for better utilization.

Factors Affecting HRP

HRP is influenced by several factors. The most important of the factors that affect HRP are (1) type and strategy of organization (2) organizational growth cycles and planning (3) environmental uncertainties (4) time horizons (5) type and quality of forecasting information (4) nature of jobs being filled and (5) off loading the work.

1. **Type and Strategy of the Organization:** Type of the organization determines the production processes involve, number and type of staff needed and the supervisory and managerial personnel required. HR need is also defined by the strategic plan of organization. If the organization has a plan for organic growth then organization need to hire additional employees. On the other hand If the organization is going for mergers and acquisition, then organization need to plan for layoffs, as mergers can create, duplicate or overlap positions that can be handled more efficiently with fewer employees.

Organization first decides whether to be reactive or proactive in HRP. Organizations either carefully anticipate the needs and systematically plan to fill the need in advance (proactive) or can simply react to the needs as they arise (reactive). Likewise, the organization must determine the width of the HR plan. Organization can choose a narrow focus by planning in only one or two HR areas like recruitment and selection or can have a broad perspective by planning in all areas including training and remuneration.

The nature of HR plan is also decides upon the formality of the plan. It can decides to have an informal plan that lies mostly in the minds of the managers and personnel staff or can have a formal plan which is properly documented in writing

The nature of HR plan is also depended upon the flexibility that is practiced in the organization. HR plan should have the ability to anticipate and deal with contingencies. Organizations frame HRP in such a way that it can contain many contingencies, which reflect different scenarios thereby assuring that the plan is flexible and adaptable.

Figure 2.1 : Factors Affecting HRP.

Figure 2.1 summarizes the five factors that influence an organization while framing its strategic HRP.

2. Organizational Growth Cycles and Planning: All organizations pass through different stages of growth from the day of its inception. The stage of growth in which an organization is determines thenature and extends of HRP. Small organizations in the earlier stages ofgrowth may not have well defined personnel planning. But as the organization enters the growth stage they feel the need to plan its human resource. At this stage organization gives emphasis upon employee development. But as the organization

reaches the mature stage it experience less flexibility and variability resulting in low growth rate. HR planning becomes more formalized and less flexible and less innovative and problem like retirement and possible retrenchment dominate planning.

During the declining stage of the organization HRP takes a different focus like planning to do the layoff, retrenchment and retirement. In declining situation planning always becomes reactive in nature towards the financial and sales distress faced by the company.

3. Environmental Uncertainties: Political, social and economic changes affect all organizations and the fluctuations that are happening in these environments affect organizations drastically. Personnel planners deal with such environmental uncertainties by carefully formulating recruitment, selection, training and development policies and programmes. The balance in the organization is achieved through careful succession planning, promotion channels, layoffs, flexi time, job sharing, retirement, VRS and other personnelrelated arrangements.

4. Time Horizons: HR plans can be short term or long term. Short term plans spans from six months to one year, while long term plans spread over three to twenty years. The extent of time period depends upon the degree of uncertainty that is prevailing in an organizations environment. Greater the uncertainty, shorter the plan time horizon and vice versa.

Table 2.1 : Degree of Uncertainty and Length of Planning Period

Short Planning period- uncertainty/ instability	Long planning period- certainty/ stability
Many new competitors Rapid changes in social and economic Conditions	Strong competitive position Evolutionary, rather than rapid social, political and technological change
Unstable product/ service demand patterns Small organizational size, poor management practices (crisis Management)	Stable demand patterns Strong management practices.

Source: Elmer H. Burack and Nicholas J. Mathis, *Human Resource Planning- A Pragmatic approach to manpower Staffing and development*, Illinois, Brace- Park Press, 1987, p. 129.

5. Type and Quality of information: The information used to forecast personnel needs originates from a multitude of sources. The forecast depends to a large extent upon the type of information and the quality of data that is available to personnel planners. The quality and accuracy of information depend upon the clarity with which the organizational decision makers have defined their strategy, structure, budgets, production schedule and so on.

Table 2.2 : Levels of HRP Information

Strategic Information	General Organizational	Specific Information Necessary for HRP

	Information	
Product mix	Organizational structure	Job analysis
Customer mix	Information flows	Skills inventories
Competitive emphasis	Operating and capital budgets Functional area objectives	Management inventories
Geographic limits of market	Production schedules Distribution channels	Available training and development programmes
	Sales territories Production processes	Recruitment sources
	Level of technology Planning horizons	Labour market analysis Compensation programmes Constitutional provisions and labour laws
		Retirement plans Turnover data.

Source: Leap & Crino, *Personnel/ Human Resource Management*, p. 161.

6. Nature of Jobs Being Filled: Personnel planners need to be really careful with respect to the nature of the jobs being filled in the organization. Employees belonging to lower level who need very limited skills can be recruited hastily but, while hiring employees for higher posts, selection and recruitment need to be carried out with high discretion. Organization need to anticipate vacancies far in advance as possible, to provide sufficient time to recruit suitable candidate. **Outsourcing:** Several organizations outsource part of their work to outside parties in the form of subcontract. Outsourcing is a regular feature both in the public sector as well as in the private sector companies. Many of the organizations have surplus labour and hence instead of hiring more people they go for outsourcing. Outsourcing is usually done for non critical activities. Outsourcing of non-critical activities through subcontracting determines HRP.

HRP Process

HRP effectively involves forecasting personnel needs, assessing personnel supply and matching demand– supply factors through personnel related programmes. The HR planning process is influenced by overall organizational objectives and environment of business.

Figure 2.2 : The HRP Process

Environmental Scanning:

It refers to the systematic monitoring of the external forces influencing the organization. The following forces are essential for pertinent HRP.

- Economic factors, including general and regional conditions.
- Technological changes
- Demographic changes including age, composition and literacy,
- Political and legislative issues, including laws and administrative rulings
- Social concerns, including child care, educational facilities and priorities.

By scanning the environment for changes that will affect an organization, managers can anticipate their impact and make adjustments early.

Organizational Objectives and Policies: HR plan is usually derived from the organizational objectives. Specific requirements in terms of number and characteristics of employees should be derived from organizational objectives

Once the organizational objectives are specified, communicated and understood by all concerned, the HR department must specify its objective with regard to HR utilization in the organization.

HR Demand Forecast:

Demand forecasting is the process of estimating the future quantity and quality of people required to meet the future needs of the organization. Annual budget and long-term corporate plan when translated into activity into activity form the basis for HR forecast.

For eg: in the case of a manufacturing company, the sales budget will form the basis for production plan giving the number and type of products to be produced in each period. This will form the basis upon which the organization will decide the number of hours to be worked by each skilled category of workers. Once the number hours required is available organization can determine the quality and quantity of personnel required for the task.

Demand forecasting is influenced by both internal factors and external factors: external factors include- competition, economic climate, laws and regulatory bodies, changes in technology and social factors whereas internal factors are budget constraints, production level, new products and services, organizational structure and employee separations.

Demand forecasting is essential because it helps the organization to 1. Quantify the jobs, necessary for producing a given number of goods, 2. To determine the nature of staff mix required in the future, 3. To assess appropriate levels in different parts of organization so as to avoid unnecessary costs to the organization,

4. To prevent shortages of personnel where and when, they are needed by the organization. 5. To monitor compliances with legal requirements with regard to reservation of jobs.

Techniques like managerial judgment, ratio- trend analysis, regression analysis, work study techniques, Delphi techniques are some of the major methods used by the organization for demand forecasting.

HR Supply Forecast:

Supply forecast determines whether the HR department will be able to procure the required number of workers. Supply forecast measures the number of people likely to be available from within and outside an organization, after making allowance for absenteeism, internal movements and promotions, wastage and changes in hours, and other conditions of work.

Supply forecast is required because it is needed as it 1. Helps to quantify the number of people and positions expected to be available in future to help the organization realize its plans and meet its objectives

2. Helps to clarify the staff mixes that will arise in future 3. It assesses existing staffing in different parts of the organization. 4. It will enable the organization to prevent shortage of people where and when they are most needed. 5. It also helps to monitor future compliance with legal requirements of job reservations.

Supply analysis covers the existing human resources, internal sources of supply and external sources of supply.

HR Programming:

Once an organization's personnel demand and supply are forecasted the demand and supply need to be balanced in order that the vacancies can be filled by the right employees at the right time.

HR Plan Implementation:

HR implementation requires converting an HR plan into action. A series of action are initiated as apart of HR plan implementation. Programmes such as recruitment, selection and placement, training and development, retraining and redeployment, retention plan, succession plan etc when clubbed together form the implementation part of the HR plan.

Control and Evaluation:

Control and evaluation represent the final phase of the HRP process. All HR plan include budgets, targets and standards. The achievement of the organization will be evaluated and

monitored against the plan. During this final phase organization will be evaluating on the number of people employed against the established (both those who are in the post and those who are in pipe line) and on the number recruited against the recruitment targets. Evaluation is also done with respect to employment cost against the budget and wastage accrued so that corrective action can be taken in future.

Requisites for Successful HRP

1. HRP must be recognized as an integral part of corporate planning
 2. Support of top management is essential
 3. There should be some centralization with respect to HRP responsibilities in order to have co-ordination between different levels of management.
 4. Organization records must be complete, up to date and readily available.
 5. Techniques used for HR planning should be those best suited to the data available and degree of accuracy required.
 6. Data collection, analysis, techniques of planning and the plan themselves need to be constantly revised and improved in the light of experience.
-

Barriers to HRP

Human Resource Planners face significant barriers while formulating an HRP. The major barriers are elaborated below:

- 1) HR practitioners are perceived as experts in handling personnel matters, but are not experts in managing business. The personnel plan conceived and formulated by the HR practitioners when enmeshed with organizational plan, might make the overall strategic plan of the organization ineffective.
- 2) HR information often is incompatible with other information used in strategy formulation. Strategic planning efforts have long been oriented towards financial forecasting, often to the exclusion of other types of information. Financial forecasting takes precedence over HRP.
- 4) Conflict may exist between short term and long term HR needs. For example, there can be a conflict between the pressure to get the work done on time and long term needs, such as preparing people for assuming greater responsibilities. Many managers are of the belief that HR needs can be met immediately because skills are available on the market as long as wages and salaries are competitive. Therefore, long times plans are not required, short planning are only needed.
- 5) There is conflict between quantitative and qualitative approaches to HRP. Some people view HRP as a number game designed to track the flow of people across the department. Others take a qualitative approach and focus on individual employee concerns such as promotion and career development. Best result can be achieved if there is a balance between the quantitative and qualitative approaches.

- 6) Non-involvement of operating managers renders HRP ineffective. HRP is not strictly an HR department function. Successful planning needs a co-ordinated effort on the part of operating managers and HR personnel.

JOB ANALYSIS

Manpower planning is concerned with determination of quantitative and qualitative requirements of manpower for the organization. Determination of manpower requirements is one of the most important problems in manpower planning. Job analysis and job design, provide this knowledge. Before going through the mechanism of job analysis and job design, it is relevant to understand the terms which are used in job analysis and job design.

Job: A job may be defined as a “collection or aggregation of tasks, duties and responsibilities which as a whole, are regarded as a regular assignment to individual employees,” and which is different from other assignments, In other words, when the total work to be done is divided and grouped into packages, we call it a “job.” Each job has a definite title based upon standardized trade specifications within a job; two or more grades may be identified, where the work assignment may be graded according to skill, the difficulty of doing them, or the quality of workmanship. Thus, it may be noted that a position is a “collection of tasks and responsibilities regularly assigned to one person;” while a job is a “group of position, which involve essentially the same duties, responsibilities, skill and knowledge.” A position consists of a particular set of duties assigned to an individual.

Decenzo and P. Robbins define other terms as follows:

Task: It is a distinct work activity carried out for a distinct purpose.

Duty: It is a number of tasks.

Position: It refers to one or more duties performed by one person in an organization, There are at least as many positions as there are workers in the organization; vacancies may create more positions than employees.

Job: It is a type of position within the organization.

Job Family: It is group of two or more jobs that either call for similar worker characteristics or contain parallel work tasks as determined by job analysis.

Occupation: It is a group of similar jobs found across organizations.

Career: It represents a sequence of positions, jobs, or occupations that a person has over his working life.

Figure 3.1: Job Analysis Information Hierarchy

(Adapted from Decenzo and P. Robbins, Personnel/Human Resource Management)

Job Analysis Defined

Recruitment & selection

Developing an organizational structure, results in jobs which have to be staffed. Job analysis is the procedure through which you determine the duties and nature of the jobs and the kinds of people (in terms of skills and experience) who should be hired for them. It provides you with data on job requirements, which are then used for developing job descriptions (what the job entails) and job specifications (what kind of people to hire for the job). Some of the definitions of job analysis are given as follows, to understand the meaning of the term more clearly:

According to Michael L. Jucius, “Job analysis refers to the process of studying the operations, duties and organizational aspects of jobs in order to derive specifications or as they called by some, job descriptions.”

According to DeCenzo and P. Robbins, “A job analysis is a systematic exploration of the activities within a job. It is a basic technical procedure, one that is used to define the duties, responsibilities, and

accountabilities of a job.” **According to Herbert G Herman** “A job is a collection of tasks that can be performed by a single employee to contribute to the production of some product or service provided by the organization. Each job has certain ability requirements (as well as certain rewards) associated with it. Job analysis process used to identify these requirements.”

Flippo has offered a more comprehensive definition of job analysis as, “Job analysis is the process of studying and collecting information relating to the operations and responsibilities of a specific job. The immediate products of the analysis are job descriptions and job specifications”

Thus, job analysis involves the process of identifying the nature of a job (job description) and the qualities of the likely job holder (job specification).

Uses of Job Analysis

As summarized in Figure 3.2 the information generated by the job analysis is used as a basis of several interrelated personnel management activities:

Figure 3.2 : Uses of Job Analysis

1. Achievement of Goals: Weather and Davis have stated, “Jobs are at the core of every organization’s productivity, if they are designed well and done right, the organization makes progress towards its objectives. Otherwise, productivity suffers, profits fall, and the organization is less able to meet the demands of society, customer, employees, and other with a stake in its success.”

2. Organizational Design: Job analysis will be useful in classifying the jobs and the interrelationships among the jobs. On the basis of information obtained through job

analysis, sound decisions regarding hierarchical positions and functional differentiation can be taken and this will improve operational efficiency.

3. Organization and Manpower Planning: It is helpful in organization planning, for it defines labour in concrete terms and co-ordinates the activities of the work force, and clearly divides duties and responsibilities.

4. Recruitment and Selection: Job analysis provides you with information on what the job entails and what human requirements are required to carry out these activities. This information is the basis on which you decide what sort of people to recruit and hire.

5. Placement and Orientation: Job analysis helps in matching the job requirements with the abilities, interests and aptitudes of people. Jobs will be assigned to persons on the basis of suitability for the job. The orientation programme will help the employee in learning the activities and understanding duties that are required to perform a given job more effectively.

6. Employee Training and Management Development: Job analysis provides the necessary information to the management of training and development programmes. It helps in to determine the content and subject matter of in training courses. It also helps in checking application information, interviewing test results and in checking references.

7. Job Evaluation and Compensation: Job evaluation is the process of determining the relative worth of different jobs in an organization with a view to link compensation, both basic and supplementary, with the worth of the jobs. The worth of a job is determined on the basis of job characteristics and job holder characteristics. Job analysis provides both in the forms of job description and job specification.

8. Performance Appraisal: Performance appraisal involves comparing each employee's actual performance with his or her desired performance. Through job analysis industrial engineers and other experts determine standards to be achieved and specific activities to be performed.

9. Health and Safety: It provides an opportunity for identifying hazardous conditions and unhealthy environmental factors so that corrective measures may be taken to minimize and avoid the possibility of accidents.

10. Employee Counselling: Job analysis provides information about career choices and personal limitation. Such information is helpful in vocational guidance and rehabilitation counselling. Employees who are unable to cope with the hazards and demands of given jobs may be advised to opt for subsidiary jobs or to seek premature retirement.

Steps in Job Analysis

The six steps of job analysis are shown in figure 3.3:

Figure 3.3 : Job Analysis Process

1. Determine the Use of the Job Analysis Information: Start by identifying the use to which the information will be put, since this will determine the type of data you collect and the technique you use to collect them.

2. Collection of Background Information: According to Terry, “The make-up of a job, its relation to other jobs, and its requirements for competent performance are essential information needed for a job evaluation. This information can be had by reviewing available background information such as organization charts (which show how the job in question relates to other jobs and where they fit into the overall organization); class specifications (which describe the general requirements of the class of job to which the job under analysis belongs); and the existing job descriptions which provide a starting point from which to build the revised job description”.

3. Selection of Jobs for Analysis: To do job analysis is a costly and time consuming process. It is hence, necessary to select a representative sample of jobs for purposes of analysis. Priorities of various jobs can also be determined. A job may be selected because it has undergone undocumented changes in job content. The request for analysis of a job may originate with the employee, supervisor, or a manager.

When the employee requests an analysis it is usually because new job demands have not been reflected in changes in wages. Employee’s salaries are, in part, based upon the nature of the work that they perform. Some organizations establish a *time cycle for the analysis of each job*. For example: A job analysis may be required for all jobs every three years. New jobs must also be subjected to analysis.

4. Collection of Job Analysis Data: Job data on features of the job, required employee qualification and requirements, should be collected either from the employees who actually perform a job; or from other employees (such as foremen or supervisors) who watch the workers doing a job and thereby acquire knowledge about it; or from the outside persons, known as the trade job analysis who are appointed to watch employees performing a job. The duties of such a trade job analyst are (i) to outline the complete scope of a job and to consider all the physical and mental activities involved in determining what the worker does.; (ii) find out why a worker does a job; and for this purpose he studies why each task is essential for the overall result; and (iii) the skill factor which may be needed in the worker to differentiate between jobs and establish the extent of the difficulty of any job.

5. Processing the Information: Once job analysis information has been collected, the next step is to place it in a form that will make it useful to those charged with the various personnel functions. Several issues arise with respect to this. First, how much detail is needed? Second, can the job analysis information be expressed in quantitative terms? These must be considered properly.

6. Preparing Job Descriptions and Job Classifications: Job information which has been collected must be processed to prepare the job description form. It is a statement showing full details of the activities of the job. Separate job description forms may be used for various activities in the job and may be compiled later on. The job analysis is

made with the help of these description forms. These forms may be used as reference for the future.

7. Developing Job Specifications: Job specifications are also prepared on the basis of information collected. It is a statement of minimum acceptable qualities of the person to be placed on the job. It specifies the standard by which the qualities of the person are measured. Job analyst prepares such statement taking into consideration the skills required in performing the job properly. Such statement is used in selecting a person matching with the job.

Methods for Collecting Job Analysis Data

As discussed earlier, information is to be collected for job analysis. Such information may be collected by the trained job analysis, superiors concerned and job holders themselves. Job information is collected through the following methods:

1. Participant Diary/Logs: Workers can be to keep participant diary/long or lists of things they do during the day. For every activity he or she engages in, the employee records the activity (along with the time) in a log. This can provide you with a very comprehensive picture of the job, especially when it's supplemented with subsequent interviews with the worker and his or her supervisor. This method provides more accurate information if done faithfully. However, it is quite time consuming. Further, each jobholder may maintain records according to his own way which presents problems in analysis at later stage. Therefore, it has limited application.

2. Interview: There are three types of interviews you can use to collect job analysis data: individual interviews with each employee; group interviews with groups of employees having the same job; and supervisor interviews with one or more supervisors who are thoroughly knowledgeable about the job being analyzed. The group interview is used when a large number of employees are performing similar or identical work, since this can be a quick and inexpensive way of learning about the job. As a rule, the worker's immediate supervisor would attend the group session; if not, you should interview the supervisor separately to get that person's perspective on the duties and responsibilities of the job.

3. Critical Incidents: In this method, job holders are asked to describe incidents concerning the job on the basis of their past experience. The incidents so collected are analyzed and classified according to the job areas they describe, A fairly picture of actual job requirements can be obtained by distinguishing between effective and ineffective behaviors of workers on the job. However, this method is time consuming. The analyst requires a high degree of skill to analyze the contents of descriptions given by workers.

4. Technical Conference Method: This method utilizes supervisors with extensive knowledge of the job. Here, specific characteristics of a job are obtained from the "experts." Although it is a good data gathering method, it often overlooks the incumbent worker's perception about what they do on their job.

5. Job Performance: Under this method, the job analyst actually performs the job under study to get first-hand experience of the actual tasks, and physical and social demands of the job. This method can be used only for jobs where skill requirements are low and can be learnt quickly and easily. This is a time-consuming method and is not appropriate for jobs requiring extensive training.

6. Functional Job Analysis: Functional job analysis (FJA) is employee-oriented analytical approach of job analysis. This approach attempts to describe the whole person on the job. The main features of FJA include the following:

- The extent to which specific instructions are necessary to perform the task
- The extent to which reasoning and judgment are required to perform the task
- The mathematical ability required to perform the task and
- The verbal and language facilities required to perform the task.

7. Observation Method: Using this method, a job analyst watches employees directly on the job. Observations are made on various tasks, activities, the pace at which tasks are carried out, and the way different activities are performed. This method is suitable for jobs that involve manual, standardized, and short job cycle activities. This method also requires that the entire range of activities be observable; possible with some jobs.

8. Questionnaires: The method is usually employed by engineering consultants. Properly drafted questionnaires are sent out to job-holders for completion and are returned to supervisors. However, the information received is often unorganized and incoherent. The idea in issuing questionnaire is to elicit the necessary information from job-holders so that any error may first be discussed with the employee and, after corrections, may be submitted to the job analyst.

Questionnaire for Job Analysis	
1.	Your Name
2.	Title or Designation of your job
3.	Regular or Extra
4.	Your Department
5.	To whom do you report directly (Name and Title):
6.	Description of work: (a) Daily Duties: (b) Periodical Duties: (c) Occasional Duties:
8.	What Equipment do you use?
9.	What Materials do you work with or sell?
10.	If you supervise the work of others, state how many and what their jobs are.
11.	To what job would you normally expect to be promoted?

This technique is time consuming and generally does not yield satisfactory results because many employees do not complete the questionnaire or furnish incorrect information because of their own limitations. The use of questionnaire is recommended only in case of those technical jobs where the job contents are not completely known to the supervisor or the operation is too complex to observe.

There are certain standardized questionnaires developed by a few agencies which are used by various organizations for job analysis. Most of these questionnaires are of two types: position analysis questionnaire and management position description questionnaire that are described as follows:

a. Position Analysis Questionnaire. Position analysis questionnaire (PAQ) is a highly specialized instrument for analyzing a job in terms of employee activities. The PAQ developed by Purdue University is a comprehensive questionnaire for collecting information for job analysis.

In this questionnaire, various job elements have been grouped into six categories with each category containing relevant job elements resulting into 195 elements as shown in Table 3.1.

Table 3.1 : Position Analysis Questionnaire

Job Aspects	No. of elements
Information input - Where and how do employee get information to do their job?	35
Mental processes- what reasoning, planning, organizing, and decision making is done?	14
Work output – what physical activities, tools and machines are used?	49
Relationships – what contact with other people, both in the company and outside is maintained or developed?	36
Job context- what is the physical and social context in which the job is maintained?	19
Other job characteristics – what other activities, conditions or Characteristics not covered by the categories are relevant?	42

The advantage of PAQ is that it provides a quantitative score or profile of any job in terms of how that job rates on the basic activities. The PAQ's real strength is, thus, in classifying jobs. PAQ's results can be used to compare the jobs relative to one another and pay levels can be assigned for each job.

The major problem with PAQ is the time it takes for a job analyst to fill out the ratings. However, PAQ has been widely researched and tested and appears to be both reliable and valid.

b. Management Position Description Questionnaire: Management position description is a highly structured questionnaire containing 208 items relating to managerial responsibilities, restrictions, demands and other miscellaneous position characteristics. W.W. Tomov and P.R. Pinto have developed the following Management position Description factors:

- Product, marketing and financial strategy planning.
- Coordination of other organization units and personnel
- Internal business Control
- Products and services responsibility
- Public and customer relations
- Advanced consulting
- Autonomy of actions
- Approval of financial commitments
- Staff Service
- Supervision
- Complexity and stress
- Advanced financial responsibility
- Broad personnel responsibility

The above methods are the most popular ones for gathering job analysis data. They all provide realistic information about what job incumbents actually do. They can thus be used for developing job descriptions and job specifications. Carroll L. Shartle, Otis and Lenhart have provided the following suggestions for making the job analyst's task simple.

- Introduce yourself so that the worker knows who you are and why you are there.
- Show a sincere interest in the worker and the job that is analyzed;
- Do not try to tell the employee how to do his job.
- Try to talk to the employee and supervisors in their own language;
- Do a complete job study within the objectives of the programmer: and
- Verify the job information obtained.

Job Description

Job description is the immediate product of job analysis process; the data collected through job analysis provides a basis for job description and job specification.

Job Description: is a written record of the duties, responsibilities and requirements of a particular job. It is concerned with the job itself and not with the job holders. It is a statement describing the job in such terms as its title, location, duties, working conditions and hazards.

Flippo has Defined Job Description as, "A job description is an organized, factual statement of duties and responsibilities of a specific job. In brief, it should tell what is to be done. How it is done why. It is a standard of function, in that defines the appropriate and authorized content of a job.

According to Pigors and Myres, "Job description is a pertinent picture (in writing) of the organizational relationships, responsibilities and specific duties that constitutes a given job or position. It defines a scope of responsibility and continuing work assignments that are sufficiently different from that of other jobs to warrant a specific title."

According to Zerga, who analyzed 401 articles on job description about 30 years ago. A job description helps us in:

- (i) Job grading and classification
- (ii) Transfers and promotions.
- (iii) Adjustments of grievances;
- (iv) Defining and outlining promotional steps:
- (v) Establishing a common understanding of a job between employers and employees;
- (vi) Investigation accidents;
- (vii) Indicating faulty work procedures or duplication of papers;
- (viii) Maintaining, operating and adjusting machinery;

- (ix) Time and motion studies;
- (x) Defining the limits of authority;
- (xi) Indicating case of personal merit;
- (xii) Studies of health and fatigue;
- (xiii) Scientific guidance;
- (xiv) Determining jobs suitable for occupational therapy;
- (xv) Providing hiring specifications; and
- (xvi) Providing performance indicators.

“Job description” is different from “performance assessment.” The former concerns such functions as planning, co-ordination, and assigning responsibility; while the latter concerns the quality of performance itself. Though job description is not assessment, it provides an important basis establishing assessment standards and objectives.

Writing Job Description

A Job description is a written statement of what the job holder actually does, how he or she does it, and under what conditions the job is performed. This information is in turn used to write a job specification. This lists the knowledge, abilities, and skills needed to perform the job satisfactorily. While there is no standard format you must use in writing a job description, most descriptions contain at least sections on:

1. Job Identification: It includes the job title, alternative title, department, division, and plant and code number of the job. The job title identifies and designates the job properly, the department, division, etc., indicate the name of the department where it is situated – whether it is the maintenance department, mechanical shop etc. Location gives the name of the place. This portion of job description gives answer to two important questions: to what higher level job is this job accountable. And who is supervised directly?

2. Job Summary: Job summary describes the contents of the jobs in terms of activities or tasks performed. Job summary should clear the nature of the job. Primary, secondary and other duties to be performed on the job should clearly be indicated separately.

3. Duties and Responsibilities: This is the most important phase of job description and should be prepared very carefully. It describes the duties to be performed along with frequency of each major duty. Responsibilities concerning custody of money, supervision and training of staff etc. are also described in this

part.

Example of a Job Description

Job Title: Record Clerk 011 Supervisor: Record Supervisor Grand –III Supervises: None 2/21/12 Job Summary: Originate, process, and maintain comprehensive records; implement required controls; collect and summarize data as requested. Job Duties and Responsibilities : <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Review a variety of documents, listings, summarizes, etc, for completeness and accuracy.• Check records against other current sources such as reports or summaries; investigate differences and take required action to ensure that records are accurate and up to date; compile and summarize data report format as required.• Implement controls or obtaining, preserving, and supplying a variety of information. Prepare simple requisitions, forms, and other routine memoranda.• Provide functional guidance to lower-level personnel as required. Working Conditions: Normal working conditions. But visits sites on average twice a week. Eight hours per day Relationships: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• With equivalent officers in other departments.	Job No. Job Date:
---	--

- Maintains formal and social contacts with local officials.

Job Characteristics: Skilled operation of computer, calculating machine, or key punch machine is not necessarily a requirement of this job.

The above information is correct and approved by:

(Signed)
Job Analyst
Manager

(Signed)
In charge

4. Supervision: Under it is given number of persons to be supervised along with their job titles, and the extent of supervision involved –general, intermediate or close supervision.

5. Relation to Other Jobs: It describes the vertical and horizontal relationships of work flow. It also indicates to whom the jobholder will report and who will report to him. It gives an idea of channels of promotion.

6. Machine, tools and equipment define each major type or trade name of the machines and tools and the raw materials used.

7. Working Conditions: The working environment in terms of heat, light, noise, dust and fumes etc, the job hazards and possibility of their occurrence and working conditions should also be described. It will be helpful in job evaluation.

8. Social Environment: It specifies the social conditions under which the work will be performed. In this part the size of work group, interpersonal interactions required to perform the job and development facilities are mentioned

Job Specification

The job specification states the minimum acceptable qualifications that the incumbent must possess to perform the job successfully. Based on the information acquired through job analysis, the job specification identifies the knowledge, skills, and abilities needed to do the job effectively. Individuals possessing the personal characteristics identified in the job specification should perform the job more effectively than individuals lacking these personal characteristics. The job specification, therefore, is an important tool in the selection process, for it keeps the selector's attention on the list of qualifications necessary for an incumbent to perform the job and assists in determining whether candidates are qualified.

According to Dale Yoder, "The job specification, as such a summary properly described is thus a specialized job description, emphasizing personnel requirement and designed especially to facilitate selection and placement."

Flippo has defined job specification as, "Job specification is a statement of the minimum acceptable human qualities necessary to perform a job properly.....It is a standard of personnel and designates the qualities required for acceptable performance."

It is clear from the above definitions that job specification is a statement of summary of personnel requirements for a job. It may also be called "standard of personnel for the selection"

A Job Specification should include:

- (i) **Physical characteristics**, which include health, strength, endurance, age, height, weight, vision, voice, eye, hand and foot co-ordination, motor co-ordination, and colour discrimination.
- (ii) **Psychological and social characteristics** such as emotional stability, flexibility, decision making ability, analytical view, mental ability, pleasing manners, initiative, conversational ability etc.
- (iii) **Mental Characteristics** such as general intelligence, memory, judgement, ability to concentrate, foresight etc.
- (iv) **Personal Characteristics** such as sex, education, family background, job experience, hobbies, extracurricular activities etc.

All these characteristics must be classified into three categories:

- Essential attributes which a person must possess.
- Desirable attributes which a person ought to possess.
- Contra indicators which will become a handicap to successful job performance.

Job Design

Job design is of comparatively recent origin. The human resource managers have realized that the design of a job has considerable influence on the productivity and job satisfaction; poorly designed jobs often result in boredom to the employees, increased turnover, job dissatisfaction, low productivity and an increase in overall costs of the organization. All these negative consequences can be avoided with the help of proper job design.

According to Jon Werner and DeSimone, “Job design is the development and alteration of the components of a job (such as the tasks one performs, and the scope of one’s responsibilities) to improve productivity and the quality of the employees’ work life.”

Job design has been defined by **Davis (1966)** as: “The specification of the contents, methods, and relationships of jobs in order to satisfy technological and organizational requirements as well as the social and personal requirements of the job-holder.”

Milkovich and Boudreau defined job design as, “Job design integrates work content (tasks, functions, and relationships), the rewards (extrinsic and intrinsic) and the qualifications required (skills, knowledge, abilities) for each job in a way that meets the needs of employees and the organization.”

Michael Armstrong has defined job design as “the process of deciding on the content of a job in terms of its duties and responsibilities, on the methods to be used in carrying out the job, in terms of techniques, systems and procedures, and on the relationships that should exist between the job holder and his superiors, subordinates and colleagues.”

Job design is an attempt to create a match between job requirements and human attributes. It involves organizing the components of the job and the interaction patterns among the members of a work group. It helps in developing appropriate design of job to improve efficiency and satisfaction.

Principles of Job Design:

Principles are the bases of the approach used in job design. Robertson and Smith (1985) have suggested the following five principles of job design:

- To influence skill variety, provide opportunities for people to do several tasks and combine tasks.
- To influence task identity, combine tasks and form natural work units.
- To influence task significance, form natural work units and inform people of the importance of their work.
- To influence autonomy, give people responsibility for determining their own working systems.

- To influence feedback; establish good relationship and open feedback channels.
-

Methods of Job Design

The various techniques of job design and redesign are discussed below:

1. Job Simplification: In job simplification, the complete job is broken down into small subparts; this is done so that employee can do these jobs without much specialized training. Moreover, small operations of the job can also be performed simultaneously so that the complete operation can be done more quickly. For job simplification, generally time and motion studies are used.

2. Job Rotation: Another technique designed to enhance employee motivation is job rotation, or periodically assigning employees to alternating jobs or tasks. For example, an employee may spend two weeks attaching bumpers to vehicles and the following two weeks making final checks of the chassis. During the next month, the same employee may be assigned to two different jobs. Therefore, the employee would be rotated among four jobs. The advantage of job rotation is that employees do not have the same routine job day after day. Job rotation only addresses the problem of assigning employees to jobs of limited scope; the depth of the job does not change. The job cycle of the actual daily work performed has not been lengthened or changed. Instead, employees are simply assigned to different jobs with different cycles.

Because job rotation does not change the basic nature of jobs, it is criticized as nothing more than having an employee perform several boring and monotonous jobs rather than one. Some employees dislike job rotation more than being assigned to one boring job because when they are assigned to one job they know exactly where to report and what work to expect each day. Workers quickly realize that job rotation does not increase their interest in their work.

Although it seldom addresses the lack of employee motivation, it give managers a means of coping with frequent absenteeism and high turnover. Thus when absenteeism or turnover occurs in the work force, managers can quickly fill the vacated position because each employee can perform several jobs.

Job rotation is often effectively used as a training technique for new, inexperienced employees. At higher organizational levels, rotation also helps to develop managerial generalists because it exposes them to several different operations.

Advantage of Job Rotation Technique:

- The employee experiences variety of work, workplace and peer group.
- Job rotation helps to broaden the knowledge and skills of an employee.
- The main advantage of job rotation is that it relieves the employee from the boredom and monotony of doing the same job.
- With the help of this method, people become more flexible. They are prepared to assume responsibility especially at other positions.

- Job rotation broadens the work experience of employees and turns specialists into generalists.
- It is beneficial for the management also as the management gets employees who can perform a variety of tasks to meet the contingencies.
- This method improves the self image and personal worth of the employee.

Disadvantage of Job Rotation Technique:

- Job rotation also creates disruptions. Members of the work group have to adjust to the new employee.
- Productivity is reduced by moving a worker into new position just when his efficiency at the prior job was creating organizational economies.
- Training costs are increased.
- The supervisor may also have to spend more time answering question and monitoring the work of the recently rotated employee.
- It can demotivate intelligent and ambitious trainees who seek specific responsibilities in their chosen

specialty.

3. Job Enlargement: Another means of increasing employee's satisfaction with routine jobs is job enlargement, or increasing the number of tasks performed (i.e. increasing the scope of the job). Job enlargement, like job rotation, tries to eliminate short job cycles that create boredom. Unlike job rotation, job enlargement actually increases the job cycle. When a job is enlarged, either the tasks being performed are enlarged or several short tasks are given to one worker. Thus, the scope of the job is increased because there are many tasks to be performed by the same worker. Job enlargement programs change

many methods of operation- in contrast to job rotation, in which the same work procedures are used by workers who rotate through work stations. Although job enlargement actually changes the pace of the work and the operation by reallocating tasks and responsibilities, it does not increase the depth of a job.

The focus of designing work for job enlargement is the exact opposite of that for job specialization. Instead of designing jobs to be divided up into the fewest of tasks per employee, a job is designed to have many tasks for the employee to perform. An enlarged job requires a longer training period because there are more tasks to be learned. Worker satisfaction should increase because it is reduced as the job scope is expanded. However, job enlargement programs are successful with jobs that have increased scope; such workers are less prone to resort to absenteeism, grievances, slowdowns and other means of displaying job dissatisfaction.

Enlargement is done only on the horizontal level. Thus, the job remains the same, but becomes of a larger scale than before. In the words of Geroge Strauss and L.R. Sayles “Job enlargement implies that instead of assigning one man to each job, a group of men can be assigned to a group of jobs and then allowed to decide for themselves how to organize the work. Such changes permit more social contacts and control over the work process.”

Job enlargement has the following advantages:

- Increase in diversity of jobs
- Job satisfaction
- Provides wholeness and identity with the task and increases the knowledge necessary to perform it.
- Provides variety of skills.
- Reduces tension and boredom.
- Trains and develops more versatile employees.

Despite these advantages this is not a completely satisfactory method of job design as it does not increase the depth of a job. Enlarged jobs require longer training period as there are more tasks to be learned.

4. Job Enrichment: The concept of job enrichment has been derived from Herzberg’s two-factor theory of motivation in which he has suggested that job content is one of the basic factors of motivation. If the job is designed in such a manner that it becomes more interesting and challenging to the job performer and provides him opportunities for achievement, recognition, responsibility, advancement and growth, the job itself becomes a source of motivation to the individual.

According to Richard W. Beatty and Graig Eric. Schneider, “Job enrichment is a motivational technique which emphasizes the need for challenging and interesting work. It suggests that jobs be redesigned so that intrinsic satisfaction is derived from doing the job. In its best applications it leads to a vertically enhanced job by adding function from other organizational levels, making it contain more variety and challenge and offer autonomy and pride to the employee.”

According to P. Robbins, “Job enrichment refers to the vertical expansion of the jobs. It

increases the degree to which the worker controls the planning, execution and evaluation of his work.”

In the words of Robert Albanese, “Job enrichment sometimes called. “vertical job leading’ is a job redesign strategy that focuses on job depth.”

According to Mondy, Holmes, and Flippo, “Job enrichment refers to basic changes in the content and level of responsibility of a job so to provide for the satisfaction of the motivation needs of personnel. **Robert Ford**, who was associated with designing of jobs to make them more enriched, has provided some bases (though not exhaustive) for job enrichment as shown in Table 3.3.

Table 3.2 : Job Enrichment Bases

Tasks	Motivator involved
Assign specific or specialized task to individuals enabling them to become expert	Responsibility, growth, advancement
Making periodic reports directly available to the individual himself rather than to the supervisor.	Internal recognition
Giving a person a whole, natural unit of work (module, exchange district, division, area, etc.)	Responsibility, achievement, recognition
Increasing the accountability of individuals for own work	Responsibility, recognition

Techniques of Job Enrichment: In order to enrich the jobs. The management should adopt the following measures:

- Freedom indecisions
- Assign a natural work unit to an employee.
- Encouraging participation
- Allow the employee to set his own standards of performance.
- Minimize the controls to provide freedom to the employees
- Make an employee directly responsible for his performance.
- Encourage participation of employees in deciding organizational goals and policies.
- Expand job vertically
- Introducing new, difficult and creative tasks to the employees.
- Sense of achievement.

Advantages of Job Enrichment: The advantages of job enrichment are as follows:

- It enriches therole.
- Job enrichment is the most widely used of job design as it provides a meaningful learning to employees.
- It makes the work interesting and employee get motivated.
- It helps in reducing the rate of labour turnover and absenteeism.
- It increases skills of the employees.
- It increases morale and performance.
- Reduce Boredom and dissatisfaction.
- Increase in output both qualitative and quantitative.

Disadvantages of Job Enrichment: Dunham and Newstrom state, “Even the strongest supporters of job enrichment readily admit that there are limitations in its application.” Newstrom and Keith Davis also write, “Employees are the final judges of what enriches their jobs. All that management can do is to gather information about what tends to enrich jobs, try these changes in the job system, and then determine whether employees feel that enrichment has occurred.” A few limitations of or problems with job enrichment are as follows:

- Increase cost
- Need more employee counseling, training, and guidance.
- Not applicable to all jobs.
- Negative impact on personnel.
- Imposed on people.
- Objected by unions
- Pay dissatisfaction

JOB ENLARGEMENT vs. JOB ENRICHMENT

Job enlargement and job enrichment are both important forms of job design in order to enhance productivity and satisfaction of the employees. They differ from each other in the following respects:

1. Nature of Job: The major difference between job enrichment and enlargement lies in the nature of additions to the job. Enlargement involves a horizontal loading or expansion, or addition of tasks of the same nature. Enrichment involves vertical loading of tasks and responsibility of the job holder; it improves the quality of the job in terms of its intrinsic worth.

2. Purpose: The purpose of job enlargement is to reduce the monotony in performing repetitive jobs by lengthening the cycle of operation. On the other hand, the purpose of job enrichment is making the job lively, challenging and satisfying. It satisfies the higher level needs such as ego satisfaction, self expression, sense of achievement and advancement of Job holders.

3. Skill Requirement: Job enlargement may not necessarily require the use of additional skills which the job holder was using in performing the job before the enlargement. This is due to similarity of additional tasks. Enrichment calls for development and utilization of higher skills, initiative, and innovation on the part of the job holder in performing the job.

4. Direction and Control: Job enlargement requires direction and control from external sources, say supervisor. In fact, the job holder may require more direction and control because of enlargement of his responsibility. Enrichment does not require external direction and control as these come from the job holder himself. He requires only feedback from his supervisor.

Summary

- The purpose of an organization is to give each person a separate distinct job and to ensure that these jobs are coordinated in such a way that the organization accomplishes its goals.
- Developing an organization structure results in jobs that have to be staffed. Job

analysis is the procedure through which you find out (1) what the job entails, and (2) what kinds of people should be hired for the job. It involves six steps: (1) determine the use of the job analysis information;

(2) collection of background information; (3) selection of jobs for analysis; (4) collection of job analysis data; (5) processing the information; (6) preparing job descriptions and job classifications; and (7) developing job specifications.

- Techniques of job analysis are – observation method, questionnaires, participant diary/logs, interview, critical incidents, technical conference method, and job performance.
- Job description and job specification are products of job analysis. Job description should indicate: duties to be performed by the job holder and the manner he should complete the tasks. Job specification: answer the question “what human traits and experience are necessary to do the job. It portrays what kind of person to recruit and for what qualities that person should be tested”.

- Job design is an attempt to create a match between job requirements and job attribute. Job rotation implies transfer to a job of same level and status. Job simplification enables the employees to do the without much specialized training
 - Job enlargement is the process of increasing the scope of job of a particular by adding more tasks to it. And job enrichment implies increasing the contents of a job or the deliberate upgrading of responsibility scope and challenge in work.
 - Job enlargement and job enrichment are both important forms of job design in order to enhance the productivity and satisfaction of the job holders.
-

RECRUITMENT

Definition Of Recruitment: *Finding and Attracting Applications*

“Recruitment is the Process of finding and attracting capable applicants for employment. The Process begins when new recruits are sought and ends when their applications are submitted. The result is a pool of application from which new employees are selected.”

MEANING OF RECRUITMENT:

Recruitment is understood as the process of searching for and obtaining applicants for jobs, from among them the right people can be selected. Though theoretically recruitment process is said to end with the receipt of applications, in practice the activity extends to the screening of applications so as to eliminate those who are not qualified for the job.

PURPOSE AND IMPORTANCE OF RECRUITMENT: -

1. Determine the present and future requirements in conjunction with personnel planning and job analysis activities
2. Increase the pool of job candidates at minimum cost
3. Help increase success rate of selection process by reducing number of under-qualified or over-qualified applications.
4. Reduce the probability that job applicants once selected would leave shortly
5. Meet legal and social obligations
6. Identify and prepare potential job applicants
7. Evaluate effectiveness of various recruitment techniques and sources for job applicants.

FACTORS GOVERNING RECRUITMENT

External Factors:

- Demand and Supply (Specific Skills)
- Unemployment Rate (Area-wise)
- Labor Market Conditions

- Political and Legal Environment (Reservations, Labor laws)
- company Image

Internal Factors

- Recruitment Policy (Internal Hiring or External Hiring?)
- Human Resource Planning (Planning of resources required)
- Size of the Organization (Bigger the size lesser the recruitment problems)
- Cost
- Growth and Expansion Plans

RECRUITMENT PROCESS

Recruitment Planning

- Number of contacts
- Types of contacts

Recruitment Strategy Development

- Make or Buy Employees
- Technological Sophistication
- Where to look
- How to look

Internal Recruitment (Source 1)

Management should be able to identify current employees who are capable of filling positions as they become available.

Job posting—A procedure for informing employees that job openings exist. Management and skills inventories, job posting, and job bidding procedures are helpful tools for internal recruitment.

Job bidding—A technique that permits individuals in the organization who believe that they possess the required qualifications to apply for the posted job.

External Recruitment (Source 2)

There are some employee needs that a firm must fill through external recruitment. Among them are: filling entry-level jobs, acquiring skills not possessed by current employees, and obtaining employees with different backgrounds to provide new ideas.

Colleges and universities—colleges and universities represent a major source of recruitment for many organizations. Potential professional, technical, and management employees are typically found in these institutions.

Competitors and other firms—competitors and other firms in the industry or geographic area may be the most important source of recruits for positions in which recent experience is highly desired.

Unemployed—individuals who are unemployed, regardless of the reason, often provide a valuable source of recruitment.

Older individuals—older workers, including those retired, may also comprise a valuable source of employees.

Military personnel—using this source may make sense to many employers because these individuals typically have a proven work history, and are flexible, motivated, and drug free.

Self-employed workers—these individuals may provide a source of applicants to fill any number of jobs requiring technical, professional, administrative, or entrepreneurial expertise.

EXTERNAL RECRUITMENT METHODS

Recruitment methods are the specific means through which potential employees are attracted to the firm.

Advertising—a way of communicating the employment needs within the firm to the public through media such as radio, newspaper, television, industry publications, and the internet.

Employment agencies—an organization that helps firms recruit employees and, at the same time, aids individuals in their attempt to locate jobs.

Recruiters—the most common use of recruiters is with technical and vocational schools, community colleges, colleges, and universities.

Special events—a recruiting method that involves an effort on the part of a single employer or group of employers to attract a large number of applicants for interviews.

Internships—a special form of recruiting that involves placing a student in a temporary job. There is no obligation on the part of the company to permanently hire the student and no obligation on the part of the student to accept a permanent position with the firm.

Executive search firms—organizations that seek the most-qualified executive available for a specific position and are generally retained by the company needing a specific type of individual.

Professional associations—associations in many business professions such as finance, marketing, information technology, and human resources provide recruitment and placement services for their members.

Employee referrals—many firms have found that their employees can assist in the recruitment process. Employees may actively solicit applications from their friends and associates.

Unsolicited walk-in applicants—if an organization has the reputation of being a good place to work, it may be able to attract good prospective employees without extensive recruitment efforts.

Open houses—firms pair potential hires and managers in a warm, casual environment that encourages on-the-spot job offers.

Event recruiting—attending events that the people you are seeking go to.

Virtual job fairs—individuals meet recruiters face-to-face in interviews conducted over special computers that have lenses that transmit head-and-shoulder images of both parties.

Sign-on bonuses—some firms are offering sign-on bonuses to high-demand prospects.

Fig. 6.1: Recruitment Sources

Evaluation and Cost Control

- Salary Cost
- Management & Professional Time spent
- Advertisement Cost
- Producing Supporting literature
- Recruitment Overheads and Expenses
- Cost of Overtime and Outsourcing
- Consultant's fees

Evaluation of Recruitment Process

- Return rate of applications sent out
- Suitable Candidates for selection
- Retention and Performance of selected candidates
- Recruitment Cost
- Time lapsed data
- Image projection

INTERNAL RECRUITMENT

Advantages	Disadvantages
<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Less Costly2. Candidates already oriented towards organization3. Organizations have better knowledge about internal candidates4. Employee morale and motivation is enhanced	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Old concept of doing things2. It abets raiding3. Candidates current work may be affected4. Politics play greater roles5. Morale problem for those not promoted.

EXTERNAL RECRUITMENT	
Advantages	Disadvantages
<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Benefits of new skills and talents2. Benefits of new experiences3. Compliance with reservation policy becomes easy4. Scope for resentment, jealousies, and heartburn are avoided.	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Better morale and motivation associated with internal recruiting is denied2. It is costly method3. Chances of creeping in false positive and false negative errors4. Adjustment of new employees takes longer time.

Alternatives to recruitment

A firm should consider the following alternatives before engaging in recruitment.

- **Outsourcing**—the process of transferring responsibility for an area of service and its objectives to an external provider.

- **Contingent workers**—also known as part-timers, temporaries, and independent contractors, comprise the fastest-growing segment of our economy.
- **Professional employer organization (employee leasing)**—using this approach, a firm terminates some or most of its employees. A leasing company then hires them, usually at the same salary, and leases them back to the former employer, who becomes the client.
- **Overtime**—perhaps the most commonly used method of meeting short-term fluctuations in work volume is through the use of overtime.

Tailoring recruitment methods to sources

For recruitment efforts to be successful, they must be tailored to meet the needs of each firm. In addition, recruitment sources and methods of recruitment may vary according to the position being filled.

Ethics in recruitment

Realistic job previews (RJP)

Providing realistic and complete information to job applicants about the job and organization in order to increase post-hire job satisfaction and adjustment.

A. Types of RJP information:

- Information about Job Duties And Tasks.
- Qualifications Required (Knowledge, Skills, And Abilities).
- Work Schedules and Other Demands.
- Promotion Opportunities and Organizational Rewards (Bonuses).
Employee Benefits .
- Organizational Goals and Culture.

2.2 SELECTION: -

MEANING OF SELECTION:

Selection is the process of picking up individuals (out of the pool of job applicants) with requisite qualifications and competence to fill jobs in the organization. A formal definition of Selection is as under

Definition of Selection: *Process of differentiating*

“Selection is the process of differentiating between applicants in order to identify and hire those with a greater likelihood of success in a job.”

DIFFERENCE BETWEEN RECRUITMENT AND SELECTION:

Recruitment	Selection
1. Recruitment refers to the process of identifying and encouraging prospective employees to apply for jobs. 2. Recruitment is said to be positive in its approach as it seeks to attract as many candidates as possible.	1. Selection is concerned with picking up the right candidates from a pool of applicants. 2. Selection on the other hand is negative in its application in as much as it seeks to eliminate as many unqualified applicants as possible in order to identify the right candidates.

ENVIRONMENTAL FACTORS AFFECTING THE SELECTION PROCESS

A permanent, standardized screening process could greatly simplify the selection process. However, development of such a process—even if it were possible and desirable—would not eliminate deviations to meet the unique needs of particular situation.

Legal considerations—legislation, executive orders, and court decisions have a major impact on human resource management. It is important for hiring managers to see the relationship between useful and legally defensible selection tools.

Speed of decision making—the time available to make the selection decision can have a major effect on the selection process. Closely following selection policies and procedures can provide greater protection against legal problems; however, there are times when the pressure of business will dictate that exceptions be made.

Organizational hierarchy—different approaches to selection are generally taken for filling positions at different levels in the organization.

Applicant pool—the number of applicants for a particular job can also affect the selection process. The process can be truly selective only if there are several qualified applicants for a particular position. The number of people hired for a particular job compared to the individuals in the applicant pool is often expressed as a selection ratio.

Type of organization—the sector of the economy in which individuals are to be employed—private, governmental, or not-for-profit—can also affect the selection process.

Probationary period— many firms use a probationary period that permits evaluating an employee’s ability based on performance. This may be either a substitute for certain phases of the selection process or a check on the validity of the process.

THE SELECTION PROCESS

The selection process typically begins with the preliminary interview; next, candidates complete the application for employment. They progress through a series of selection tests, the employment interview, and reference and background checks. The successful applicant receives a company physical examination and is employed if the results are satisfactory.

Several external and internal factors impact the selection process, and the manager must take them into account in making selection decisions.

Steps in the selection process

1. **Preliminary Interview:** The purpose of preliminary interviews is basically to eliminate unqualified applications based on information supplied in application forms. The basic objective is to reject misfits. On the other hands preliminary interviews is often called a courtesy interview and is a good public relations exercise.

2 **Selection Tests:** Jobseekers who past the preliminary interviews are called for tests. There are various types of tests conducted depending upon the jobs and the company. These tests can be Aptitude Tests, Personality Tests, and Ability Tests and are conducted to judge how well an individual can perform tasks related to the job. Besides this there are some other tests also like Interest Tests (activity preferences), Graphology Test (Handwriting), Medical Tests, Psychometric Tests etc.

TYPES OF EMPLOYMENT TESTS

Individuals differ in characteristics related to job performance. These differences, which are measurable, relate to cognitive abilities, psychomotor abilities, job knowledge, work samples, vocational interests, and personality. Various tests measure these differences.

Cognitive aptitude tests—measure an individual’s ability to learn, as well as to perform a job. Job-related abilities may be classified as verbal, numerical, perceptual speed, spatial, and reasoning.

Psychomotor abilities tests—measure strength, coordination, and dexterity. It is feasible to measure many abilities that are involved in many routine production jobs and some office jobs.

Job knowledge tests—designed to measure a candidate's knowledge of the duties of the position for which he or she is applying.

Work-sample tests (simulations)—identify a task or set of tasks that are representative of the job. The evidence concerning these tests, to date, is that they produce high predictive validity, reduce adverse impact, and are more acceptable to applicants.

Vocational interest tests—indicate the occupation in which a person is most interested and is most likely to receive satisfaction.

Personality tests—as selection tools, personality tests have not been as useful as other types of tests. They are often characterized by low reliability and low validity. Because some personality tests emphasize subjective interpretation, the services of a qualified psychologist are required.

Drug and alcohol testing—few issues generate more controversy today than drug testing. Proponents of drug-testing programs contend that it is necessary to ensure workplace safety, security, and productivity.

Genetic testing—as genetic research progresses, confirmed links between specific gene mutations and diseases are emerging. Genetic testing can now determine whether a person carries the gene mutation for certain diseases, including heart disease, colon cancer, breast cancer, and huntington's disease.

Internet testing—the internet is increasingly being used to test various skills required by applicants.

2.3 Interviewing candidates

3 Employment Interview: The next step in selection is employment interview. Here interview is a formal and in-depth conversation between applicant's acceptability. It is considered to be an excellent selection device. Interviews can be One-to-One, Panel Interview, or Sequential Interviews. Besides there can be Structured and Unstructured interviews, Behavioral Interviews, Stress Interviews. A goal-oriented conversation in which the interviewer and applicant exchange information. The employment interview is especially significant because the applicants who reach this stage are considered to be the most promising candidates.

Interview Planning—Interview planning is essential to effective employment interviews. The physical location of the interview should be both pleasant and private, providing for a minimum of interruptions. The interviewer should possess a pleasant personality, empathy and the ability to listen and communicate effectively. He or she

should become familiar with the applicant's qualifications by reviewing the data collected from other selection tools. In preparing for the interview, a job profile should be developed based on the job description.

Determining the Content of the Interview—The specific content of employment interviews varies greatly by organization and the level of the job concerned.

- **Occupational experience:** Exploring an individual's occupational experience requires determining the applicant's skills, abilities, and willingness to handle responsibility.
- **Academic achievement:** In the absence of significant work experience, a person's academic background takes on greater importance.
- **Interpersonal skills:** If an individual cannot work well with other employees, chances for success are slim. This is especially true in today's world with increasing emphasis being placed on the use of teams.
- **Personal qualities:** Personal qualities normally observed during the interview include physical appearance, speaking ability, vocabulary, poise, adaptability, and assertiveness.
- **Organizational fit:** A hiring criterion that is not prominently mentioned in the literature is *organizational fit*. Organizational fit is ill-defined but refers to management's perception of the degree to which the prospective employee will fit in with, for example, the firm's culture or value system.

TYPES OF INTERVIEWS

Interviews may be classified by the degree to which they are structured.

The unstructured (nondirective) interview—an interview where probing, open-ended questions are asked. This type of interview is comprehensive, and the interviewer encourages the applicant to do much of the talking.

The structured (directive or patterned) interview—an interview consisting of a series of job-related questions that are asked consistently of each applicant for a particular job. A structured interview typically contains four types of questions.

1. **Situational questions:** pose a hypothetical job situation to determine what the applicant would do in that situation.
2. **Job knowledge questions:** probe the applicant's job-related knowledge.

3. **Job-sample simulation questions:** involve situations in which an applicant may be actually required to perform a sample task from the job.
4. **Worker requirements questions:** seek to determine the applicant's willingness to conform to the requirements of the job.

Behavior description interviewing—a structured interview that uses questions designed to probe the candidate's past behavior in specific situations. It avoids making judgments about applicants' personalities and avoids hypothetical and self-evaluative questions. Benchmark answers derived from behaviors of successful employees are prepared for use in rating applicant responses. Questions asked in behavior description interviewing are legally *safe* because they are job related.

Methods of interviewing

Interviews may be conducted in several ways.

One-on-one interview—in a typical employment interview, the applicant meets one-on-one with an interviewer. As the interview may be a highly emotional occasion for the applicant, meeting alone with the interviewer is often less threatening.

Group interview—several applicants interact in the presence of one or more company representatives.

Board interview—one candidate is interviewed by several representatives of the firm.

Stress interview—intentionally creates anxiety to determine how an applicant will react to stress on the job.

Realistic job previews—conveys job information to the applicant in an unbiased manner, including both positive and negative factors.

Assessment centers

An *assessment center* is a selection technique used to identify and select employees for positions in the organization and requires individuals to perform activities similar to those they might encounter in an actual job.

4 Reference & Background Checks: Reference checks and background checks are conducted to verify the information provided by the candidates. Reference checks can be through formal letters, telephone conversations. However it is merely a formality and selections decisions are seldom affected by it.

5 Selection Decision: After obtaining all the information, the most critical step is the selection decision is to be made. The final decision has to be made out of applicants who

have passed preliminary interviews, tests, final interviews and reference checks. The views of line managers are considered generally because it is the line manager who is responsible for the performance of the new employee.

6 Physical Examination: After the selection decision is made, the candidate is required to undergo a physical fitness test. A job offer is often contingent upon the candidate passing the physical examination.

7 Job Offer: The next step in selection process is job offer to those applicants who have crossed all the previous hurdles. It is made by way of letter of appointment.

8 Contract of Employment: After the job offer is made and candidates accept the offer, certain documents need to be executed by the employer and the candidate. Here is a need to prepare a formal contract of employment, containing written contractual terms of employment etc.

CHARACTERISTICS OF PROPERLY DESIGNED SELECTION TESTS

properly designed selection tests are standardized, objective, based on sound norms, reliable and—of utmost importance—valid.

- 1. Standardization:** Refers to the uniformity of the procedures and conditions related to administering tests. It is necessary for all to take the test under conditions that are as close to identical as possible.
- 2. Objectivity:** Achieved when all individuals scoring a given test obtain the same results.
- 3. Norms:** Provide a frame of reference for comparing applicants' performance with that of others. A norm reflects the distribution of scores obtained by many people similar to the applicant being tested. The prospective employee's test score is compared to the norm, and the significance of the test score is determined.
- 4. Reliability:** The extent to which a selection test provides consistent results. If a test has low reliability, its validity as a predictor will also be low. To validate reliability, a test must be verified.
- 5. Validity:** The extent to which a test measures what it purports to measure. If a test cannot indicate ability to perform the job, it has no value as a predictor.

Types of validation studies

The *uniform guidelines* established three approaches that may be followed to validate selection tests: criterion-related validity, content validity, and construct validity.

A. Criterion-related validity—determined by comparing the scores on selection tests to some aspect of job performance. A close relationship between the score on the test and job performance suggests the test is valid.

- 1. Concurrent validity:** the test scores and the criterion data are obtained at essentially the same time.

2 .**Predictive validity**: administering a test and later obtaining the criterion information.

B. Content validity—test validation methods whereby a person performs certain tasks that are actually required by the job or completes a paper-and-pencil test that measures relevant job knowledge.

C. Construct validity— a test validation method to determine whether a test measures certain traits or qualities that are important in performing the job. However, traits or qualities such as teamwork, leadership, and planning or organization ability must first be carefully identified through job analysis.

ESSENTIALS OF A GOOD SELECTION PRACTICE

1. Detailed job descriptions and job specifications prepared in advance and endorsed by personnel and line management
2. Train the selectors
3. Determine aids to be used for selection process
4. Check competence of recruitment consultants before retention
5. Involve line managers at all stages
6. Attempt to validate the procedure
7. Help the appointed candidate to succeed by training and management development

BARRIERS TO EFFECTIVE SELECTION: -

1. **Perception**: We all perceive the world differently. Our limited perceptual ability is obviously a stumbling block to the objective and rational selection of people.
2. **Fairness**: Barriers of fairness includes discrimination against religion, region, race or gender etc.
3. **Validity**: A test that has been validated can differentiate between the employees who can perform well and those who will not. However it does not predict the job success accurately.
4. **Reliability**: A reliable test may fail to predict job performance with precision.
5. **Pressure**: Pressure brought on selectors by politicians, bureaucrats, relatives, friends and peers to select particular candidate are also barriers to selection.

Negligent hiring and retention

Negligent hiring has become a critical concern in the selection process. An employer can be held responsible for an employee's unlawful acts if it does not reasonably investigate applicants' backgrounds and then assigns potentially dangerous persons to positions where they can inflict harm. This liability exists for an employer even if the employee's actions are not job related. Negligent retention, a related potential liability, involves keeping persons on the payroll whose records indicate strong potential for wrongdoing.

Employers are beginning to be held responsible for actions outside the scope of the employee's duties. Employers are required by law to provide employees a safe place to work. This has been extended to include providing safe employees because a dangerous worker is comparable to a defective machine.

Placement – Orientation - Socialization

After an employee has been recruited he is provided with basic background information about the employer, working conditions and the information necessary to perform his job satisfactorily. The new employee's initial orientation helps him perform better by providing him information of the company rules, and practices.

According to Pigors and Myers, "Placement consists in matching what the supervisor has reason to think the new employee can do with what the job demands (job requirements), imposes (in strain, working conditions, etc.), and offers (in the form of pay rate, interest, companionship with other, promotional possibilities, etc.)" They further state that it is not easy to match all these factors for a new worker who is still in many ways an unknown quantity. For this reason, the first placement usually carries with it the status of probationer.

A few basic principles should be followed at the time of placement of an employee on the job. These may be enumerated as below:

- The job should be offered to the man according to his qualifications. The placement should neither be higher nor lower than the qualifications.
- While introducing the job to the new employee, an effort should be made to develop a sense of loyalty and cooperation in him so that he may realise his responsibilities better towards the job and the organisation.
- The employee should be made conversant with the working conditions prevailing in the industry and all things relating to the job. He should also be made aware of the penalties if he commits a wrong.
- Man should be placed on the job according to the requirements of the job. The job should not be adjusted according to the qualifications or requirements of the man. Job first; man next, should be the principle of placement.
- The placement should be ready before the joining date of the newly selected person.
- The placement in the initial period may be temporary as changes are likely after the completion of training. The employee may be later transferred to the job where he can do better justice.

In the words of John M. Ivancevich, "Orientation orients, directs, and guides employees to understand the work, firm, colleagues, and mission. It introduces new employees to the organisation, and to his new tasks, managers, and work groups."

According to John Bernardin, "Orientation is a term used for the organizationally sponsored, formalized activities associated with an employee's socialisation into the

organisation.”

Billimoria has defined orientation as, “Induction (orientation) is a technique by which a new employee is rehabilitated into the changed surroundings and introduced to the practices, policies, and purposes of the organisation.”

Orientation is one component of the new employee socialization process. Socialization is the ongoing process of instilling in all new employees prevailing attitudes, standards, values, patterns of behaviour that are expected by the organisation and its departments.

Thus, orientation is a process through which a new employee is introduced to the organisation. It is the process wherein an employee is made to feel comfortable and at home in the organisation. The new employee is handed over a rulebook, company booklets, policy manuals, progress reports and documents containing company information which are informational in nature. It is responsibility of the humanresource department to execute the orientation programme.

Self Assessment Questions

1. Explain the role of HR professional in human resource planning process in organizations.
- 2 Describe the various forecasting techniques and how these techniques are being used in human resource planning.
- 3 Explain the barriers to HRP. Bring out the requisites for effective planning.
- 4 White short note on
 1. Job analysis
 2. Succession planning
 3. Career planning
- 5 Explain the implementation of HR Planning.
- 6 Describe the importance of Human resource planning
- 7 Elucidate the purpose of job analysis
- 8 Explain specification.
- 9 Define recruitment and identify the various factors which affect recruitment.
- 10 Discuss the steps of recruitment process. How will you reconcile the internal and external sources of recruitment?
- 11 Discuss various sources of recruitment.
- 12 What do you mean by recruitment policy? Explain the prerequisites of a good recruitment policy.
- 13 Write short notes on following.
 - Advantages and disadvantages of internal sources of recruitment.
 - Advantages and disadvantages of external source of recruitment.
- 14 Explain the direct, indirect and third party methods of recruitment.
- 15 What do you understand by selection process? Discuss various steps involved in it.
- 16 What are the steps in job analysis
- 17 Describe the features of good job description.
- 18 Explain the elements in HRP system
- 19 Describe manpower forecasting techniques used in organization.
- 20 Explain the need for training and developing of employee resource.

- 21 What do you understand by job analysis? What is its importance in the management of human resources?
- 22 What is job analysis? What steps are involved in the preparation of job analysis?
- 23 What is job description? How is it prepared?
- 24 Define job specification? How is it different from job description?
- 25 Write notes on :
 - i. Job Rotation
 - ii. Job Simplification
- 26 Distinguish between :
 - i. Job description and job specification
 - ii. Job enlargement and job enrichment
- 27 “Job analysis is the most basic personnel management function.” Discuss.
- 28 Clearly define and discuss the relationship among job analysis, job description and job.
- 29 Discuss the characteristics of a good test. Explain various types of tests used in the selection process.
- 30 What is an interview? What purpose does it serve? Discuss various types of interviews.
- 31 Discuss various guidelines to be followed for an interview.
- 32 Explain various steps involved in the selection of personnel.
- 33 What do you understand by placement and orientation?

1. Which of these is the purpose of recruitment?

- a. Make sure that there is match between cost and benefit
- b. Help increase the success rate of the selection process by reducing the number of visibly under qualified or over qualified job applicants.
- c. Help the firm create more culturally diverse work - force
- d. None of the above

ANSWER - B

2. The poor quality of selection will mean extra cost on _____ and supervision.

- a. Training
- b. Recruitment
- c. Work quality
- d. None of the above

ANSWER -A

3. Which of these is the most important external factor governing recruitments?

- a. Sons of soil
- b. Labour market
- c. Unemployment rate
- d. Supply and demand

ANSWER -D

4. While recruiting for non - managerial, supervisory and middle - management positions which external factor is of prime importance?

- a. Political - Legal
- b. Unemployment rate
- c. Labour market
- d. Growth and Expansion

ANSWER - C

5. Which of the following act deals with recruitment and selection?

- a. Child labour act
- b. The apprentices act
- c. Mines act
- d. All of the above

ANSWER -D

6. A major internal factor that can determine the success of the recruiting programme is whether or not the company engages in _____.

- a. HRP
- b. Selection
- c. Induction
- d. None of the above

ANSWER-A

7. _____ refers to the process of identifying and attracting job seekers so as to build a pool of qualified job applicants.

- a. Selection
- b. Training
- c. Recruitments
- d. Induction

ANSWER -C

8. How many stages does the recruitment process comprise of?

- a. 2
- b. 6
- c. 9
- d. 5

ANSWER -D

9. Rearrange the following steps of recruitment.

I. Searching

II. Evaluation and control

III. Planning

IV. Screening

V. Strategy development

a. III, II, I, V, IV

b. III, V, I, IV, II

c. IV, V, III, I, II

d. II, I, IV, V, III

ANSWER -B

10. _____ express the relationship of applicant inputs to outputs at various decision points.

a. Number of contacts

b. Yield Ratios

c. Type of contacts

d. Technological sophistication

ANSWER-B

11. Which of the following are the decisions to be made while devising the strategies to hire?

a. Geographic distribution of labour markets comprising job seekers

b. Make or buy employees

c. Sequencing the activities in the recruitment process

d. All of the above

ANSWER -D

12. What is the main objective of the recruitment and selection process?

a. Recruit the right candidates

b. Meet the high labour turnover

c. To reduce the costs of recruiting

d. None of the above

ANSWER -B

13-The Recruitment and Selection process aimed at right kind of people

(A) At right place

(B) At right time

(C) To do right things

(D) all of the above

ANSWER -D

14 -Recruitment or manpower selection process is the first step in the employment of _____.

(A) Labour

- (B) Management
- (C) Both (A) and (B)
- (D) None of the above

ANSWER- D

15. The firm must go to external sources for

- (A) Lower entry jobs
- (B) For expansion
- (C) For positions whose specifications cannot be met by present personnel.
- (D) All of the above

ANSWER - D

16-The _____ unit acts as a clearing house in screening applications that are unrealistic.

- (A) Personnel
- (B) Selection
- (C) Production
- (D) all of the above

ANSWER -A

17 _____ are firms that are looked upon as ‘head hunters’, ‘raiders’ and ‘pirates’ by organizations which lose personnel through their efforts.

- (A) Professional institutions
- (B) Labour unions
- (C) Recruiting firms
- (D) Employment agencies

ANSWER -C

18-To adjust to _____ fluctuations in personnel needs, the possibility of leasing personnel by the hour or day should be considered.

- (A) Short-term
- (B) Mid-term
- (C) Long-term
- (D) Any of the above

ANSWER-A

19-_____ is the hiring of relatives which will be an inevitable component of recruitment programmes in family owned firms.

- (A) Leasing
- (B) Nepotism
- (C) Loyalty
- (D) None of the above

ANSWER -B

20. The _____ and the job applicant are interrelated at each step in the selection procedure.

- (A) Job specification
- (B) Job evaluation
- (C) Both (A) and (B)
- (D) None of the above

ANSWER-A

21-The standard of Personnel is represented by the job specification, as developed through

- (A) Job evaluation
- (B) Job analysis
- (C) Job satisfaction
- (D) all of the above

ANSWER -B

22. Which mode of recruitment is through advertisements, newspapers and want ads?

- a. Direct
- b. Indirect
- c. On payroll
- d. None of the above

ANSWER-B

23. _____ is the process of differentiating between applicants in order to identify and hire those with a greater likelihood of success in a job.

- a. False negative error
- b. Training
- c. Selection
- d. None of the above

ANSWER- C

24. _____ provides complete job related information (both positive and negative) to the applicants so that they can make right decisions before taking the job.

- a. Job Compatibility Questionnaire
- b. Realistic job preview
- c. Market survey
- d. None of the above

ANSWER -B

25. Which of these is an alternative to recruitments?

- a. Employee leasing
- b. Contractors
- c. Trade associations
- d. None of the above

ANSWER -A

Unit 3 Human resource Development

Purposes of Training, need and rationale.- Role of Training - Training process Purposes of Performance Evaluation. Methods of Performance Appraisal Common Appraisal Problems Career Planning, career stages,. Factors Affecting Career Planning Essentials of success in career planning,

Unit 4 Employee safety and Health

The Nature And Role Of Safety And Health , Developing Safety Programs workplace Violence, Types of Working Environment, Safety Education Occupational Safety - causes of accidents and its prevention - supervisor's role in safety - an overview Labor welfare activities. Sources of Stress, Methods of Stress relievers, Role of HR Managing Stress

TRAINING

Human Resource Management is concerned with the planning, acquisition, training & developing human beings for getting the desired objectives & goals set by the organization. The employees have to be transformed according to the organizations' & global needs. This is done through an organized activity called Training.

Training is a process of learning a sequence of programmed behavior. It is the application of knowledge & gives people an awareness of rules & procedures to guide their behavior. It helps in bringing about positive change in the knowledge, skills & attitudes of employees. Thus, training is a process that tries to improve skills or add to the existing level of knowledge so that the employee is better equipped to do his present job or to mould him to be fit for a higher job involving higher responsibilities. It bridges the gap between what the employee has & what the job demands.

Need for training

Training is crucial for organizational development and success. It is fruitful to both employers and employees of an organization. An employee will become more efficient and productive if he is trained well.

Training is given on four basic grounds:

1. New Hire Orientation

Training is particularly important for new employees. This can be conducted by someone within the company and should serve as a platform to get new employees up to speed with the processes of the company and address any skill gaps.

2. Tackle shortcomings

Every individual has some shortcomings and training and development helps employees iron them out. For example divide the entire headcount in several groups to provide focused

training which is relevant to those groups - sales training, first time managers, middle management, senior leadership, executive leadership.

3. Improvement in performance

If shortcomings and weaknesses are addressed, it is obvious that an employee's performance improves. Training and development, however, also goes on to amplify your strengths and acquire new skill sets. It is important for a company to break down the training and development needs to target relevant individuals.

4. Employee satisfaction

A company that invests in training and development generally tends to have satisfied employees. However, the exercise has to be relevant to the employees and one from which they can learn and take back something. It will be futile if training and development become tedious and dull, and employees attend it merely because they have to. As a company, we should stress on industry specific training and send many employees for international seminars and conferences that can be beneficial to them.

5. Increased productivity

In a rapidly evolving landscape, productivity is not only dependent on employees, but also on the technology they use. Training and development goes a long way in getting employees up to date with new technology, use existing ones better and then discard the outdated ones. This goes a long way in getting things done efficiently and in the most productive way.

Objectives of Training Programme

- i) To impart basic knowledge and skills to new entrants
- ii) To assist the employees to function more effectively in their present position by exposing them to the latest concepts, information and techniques and developing in them the skills required in their fields,
- iii) To build up a second line of competent officers and prepare them as a part of their career progression to occupy more responsible positions.
- iv) To broaden the minds of the senior managers by providing them opportunities for interchange of experiences within and outside with a view to correct the narrow outlook that may arise from over specialization.
- (v) To impart customer education.

Objectives and Process of Employee Training

The training design process refers to a systematic approach for developing training programs. It includes the seven steps in this process. Training is one of the most profitable investments an organization can make. No matter what business or industry you are in the steps for an

effective training process are the same and may be adapted anywhere. If you have ever thought about developing a training program within your organization consider the following four basic training steps. You will find that all four of these steps are mutually necessary for any training program to be effective and efficient.

Step 1 is to conduct a needs assessment, which is necessary to identify whether training is needed. This step identifies activities to justify an investment for training. The techniques necessary for the data collection are surveys, observations, interviews, and customer comment cards. Several examples of an analysis outlining specific training needs are customer dissatisfaction, low morale, low productivity, and high turnover.

The objective in establishing a needs analysis is to find out the answers to the following questions:

- “Why” is training needed?
- “What” type of training is needed?
- “When” is the training needed?
- “Where” is the training needed?
- “Who” needs the training? and “Who” will conduct the training?
- “How” will the training be performed?

By determining training needs, an organization can decide what specific knowledge, skills, and attitudes are needed to improve the employee’s performance in accordance with the company’s standards.

The needs analysis is the starting point for all training. The primary objective of all training is to improve individual and organizational performance. Establishing a needs analysis is, and should always be the first step of the training process.

Step 2 is to ensure that employees have the motivation and basic skills necessary to master training content. This step establishes the development of current job descriptions and standards and procedures. Job descriptions should be clear and concise and may serve as a major training tool for the identification of guidelines. Once the job description is completed, a complete list of standards and procedures should be established from each responsibility outlined in the job description. This will standardize the necessary guidelines for any future training.

Step 3 is to create a learning environment that has the features necessary for learning to occur. This step is responsible for the instruction and delivery of the training program. Once you have designated your trainers, the training technique must be decided. One-on-one training, on-the-job training, group training, seminars, and workshops are the most popular methods.

Before presenting a training session, make sure you have a thorough understanding of the following characteristics of an effective trainer. The trainer should have:

- A desire to teach the subject being taught.

- A working knowledge of the subject being taught.
- An ability to motivate participants to “want” to learn.
- A good sense of humour.
- A dynamic appearance and good posture.
- A strong passion for their topic.
- A strong compassion towards their participants.
- Appropriate audio/visual equipment to enhance the training session.

For a training program to be successful, the trainer should be conscious of several essential elements, including a controlled environment, good planning, the use of various training methods, good communication skills and trainee participation.

Step 4 is to ensure that trainees apply the training content to their jobs.

This step will determine how effective and profitable your training program has been. Methods for evaluation are pre-and post- surveys of customer comments cards, the establishment of a cost/benefit analysis outlining your expenses and returns, and an increase in customer satisfaction and profits. The reason for an evaluation system is simple. The evaluations of training programs are without a doubt the most important step in the training process. It is this step that will indicate the effectiveness of both the training as well as the trainer.

There are several obvious benefits for evaluating a training program. First, evaluations will provide feedback on the trainer’s performance, allowing them to improve themselves for future programs. Second, evaluations will indicate its cost-effectiveness. Third, evaluations are an efficient way to determine the overall effectiveness of the training program for the employees as well as the organization.

The importance of the evaluation process after the training is critical. Without it, the trainer does not have a true indication of the effectiveness of the training. Consider this information the next time you need to evaluate your training program. You will be amazed with the results.

The need for training your employees has never been greater. As business and industry continues to grow, more jobs will become created and available. Customer demands, employee morale, employee productivity, and employee turnover as well as the current economic realities of a highly competitive workforce are just some of the reasons for establishing and implementing training in an organization. To be successful, all training must receive support from the top management as well as from the middle and supervisory levels of management. It is a team effort and must be implemented by all members of the organization to be fully successful.

Training Methods: On Job Training and off the Job

A large variety of methods of training are used in business. Even within one organization different methods are used for training different people. All the methods are divided into two classifications for:

A. On-the-job Training Methods:

1. Coaching

2. Mentoring
3. Job Rotation
4. Job Instruction Technology
5. Apprenticeship
6. Understudy

B. Off-the-Job Training Methods:

1. Lectures and Conferences
2. Vestibule Training
3. Simulation Exercises
4. Sensitivity Training
5. Transactional Training

A. On-the-job training Methods:

Under these methods new or inexperienced employees learn through observing peers or managers performing the job and trying to imitate their behaviour. These methods do not cost much and are less disruptive as employees are always on the job, training is given on the same machines and experience would be on already approved standards, and above all the trainee is learning while earning. Some of the commonly used methods are:

1. Coaching:

Coaching is a one-to-one training. It helps in quickly identifying the weak areas and tries to focus on them. It also offers the benefit of transferring theory learning to practice. The biggest problem is that it perpetrates the existing practices and styles. In India most of the scooter mechanics are trained only through this method.

2. Mentoring:

The focus in this training is on the development of attitude. It is used for managerial employees. Mentoring is always done by a senior inside person. It is also one-to-one interaction, like coaching.

3. Job Rotation:

It is the process of training employees by rotating them through a series of related jobs. Rotation not only makes a person well acquainted with different jobs, but it also alleviates boredom and allows to develop rapport with a number of people. Rotation must be logical.

4. Job Instructional Technique (JIT):

It is a Step by step (structured) on the job training method in which a suitable trainer (a) prepares a trainee with an overview of the job, its purpose, and the results desired, (b) demonstrates the task or the skill to the trainee, (c) allows the trainee to show the demonstration on his or her own, and (d) follows up to provide feedback and help. The trainees are presented the learning material in written or by learning machines through a

series called 'frames'. This method is a valuable tool for all educators (teachers and trainers). It helps us:

- a. To deliver step-by-step instruction
- b. To know when the learner has learned
- c. To be due diligent (in many work-place environments)

5. Apprenticeship:

Apprenticeship is a system of training a new generation of practitioners of a skill. This method of training is in vogue in those trades, crafts and technical fields in which a long period is required for gaining proficiency. The trainees serve as apprentices to experts for long periods. They have to work in direct association with and also under the direct supervision of their masters.

The object of such training is to make the trainees all-round craftsmen. It is an expensive method of training. Also, there is no guarantee that the trained worker will continue to work in the same organization after securing training. The apprentices are paid remuneration according to the apprenticeship agreements.

6. Understudy:

In this method, a superior gives training to a subordinate as his understudy like an assistant to a manager or director (in a firm). The subordinate learns through experience and observation by participating in handling day to day problems. Basic purpose is to prepare subordinate for assuming the full responsibilities and duties.

B. Off-the-job Training Methods:

Off-the-job training methods are conducted in separate from the job environment, study material is supplied, there is full concentration on learning rather than performing, and there is freedom of expression. Important methods include:

1. Lectures and Conferences:

Lectures and conferences are the traditional and direct method of instruction. Every training programme starts with lecture and conference. It's a verbal presentation for a large audience. However, the lectures have to be motivating and creating interest among trainees. The speaker must have considerable depth in the subject. In the colleges and universities, lectures and seminars are the most common methods used for training.

2. Vestibule Training:

Vestibule Training is a term for near-the-job training, as it offers access to something new (learning). In vestibule training, the workers are trained in a prototype environment on specific jobs in a special part of the plant. An attempt is made to create working condition similar to the actual workshop conditions. After training workers in such condition, the trained workers may be put on similar jobs in the actual workshop.

This enables the workers to secure training in the best methods to work and to get rid of initial nervousness. During the Second World War II, this method was used to train a large

number of workers in a short period of time. It may also be used as a preliminary to on-the-job training. Duration ranges from few days to few weeks. It prevents trainees to commit costly mistakes on the actual machines.

3. Simulation Exercises:

Simulation is any artificial environment exactly similar to the actual situation. There are four basic simulation techniques used for imparting training: management games, case study, role playing, and in-basket training.

(a) Management Games:

Properly designed games help to ingrain thinking habits, analytical, logical and reasoning capabilities, importance of team work, time management, to make decisions lacking complete information, communication and leadership capabilities. Use of management games can encourage novel, innovative mechanisms for coping with stress.

Management games orient a candidate with practical applicability of the subject. These games help to appreciate management concepts in a practical way. Different games are used for training general managers and the middle management and functional heads – executive Games and functional heads.

(b) Case Study:

Case studies are complex examples which give an insight into the context of a problem as well as illustrating the main point. Case Studies are trainee centered activities based on topics that demonstrate theoretical concepts in an applied setting. A case study allows the application of theoretical concepts to be demonstrated, thus bridging the gap between theory and practice, encourage active learning, provides an opportunity for the development of key skills such as communication, group working and problem solving, and increases the trainees’ enjoyment of the topic and hence their desire to learn.

(c) Role Playing:

Each trainee takes the role of a person affected by an issue and studies the impacts of the issues on human life and/or the effects of human activities on the world around us from the perspective of that person.

It emphasizes the “real- world” side of science and challenges students to deal with complex problems with no single “right” answer and to use a variety of skills beyond those employed in a typical research project.

In particular, role-playing presents the student a valuable opportunity to learn not just the course content, but other perspectives on it. The steps involved in role playing include defining objectives, choose context & roles, introducing the exercise, trainee preparation/research, the role-play, concluding discussion, and assessment. Types of role play may be multiple role play, single role play, role rotation, and spontaneous role play.

(d) In-basket training:

In-basket exercise, also known as in-tray training, consists of a set of business papers which may include e-mail SMSs, reports, memos, and other items. Now the trainer is asked to priorities the decisions to be made immediately and the ones that can be delayed.

4. Sensitivity Training:

Sensitivity training is also known as laboratory or T-group training. This training is about making people understand about themselves and others reasonably, which is done by developing in them social sensitivity and behavioral flexibility. It is ability of an individual to sense what others feel and think from their own point of view.

Meaning and Definition of Compensation

In layman's language the word 'compensation' means something, such as money, given or received as payment for service. The word compensation may be defined as money received in the performance of work, plus the many kinds of benefits and services that organization provides their employee. It refers to wide range of financial and non-financial rewards to employee for their service rendered to the organization. It is paid in the form of wages, salaries, special allowance and employee benefits such as paid vacation, insurance, maternity leaves, free travel facility, retirement benefits etc.

According to Wendell French,” Compensation is a comprehensive term which includes wages, salaries and all other allowance and benefits.”

Wages are the remuneration paid for skilled, semi-skilled and unskilled operative workforce. Salary is the remuneration of those employees who provides mental labour to the employer such as supervisor, office staff, executive etc wages are paid on daily or hourly basis where as salary is paid on monthly basis.

COMPENSATION MANAGEMENT

The term compensation is used to indicate the employee’s gross earnings in the form of financial rewards and benefits.

Compensation can also be defined as follows:

1. A system of rewards that can motivate the employees to perform.
2. A tool that is used to foster values and culture.
3. An instrument that enables an organization to achieve its objectives.

The management should ensure that compensation structure is designed after taking into account certain factors such as qualification, experience, attitude and prevailing rates in the markets. Compensation means the reward that is received by an employee for the work performed in an organization. It is an important function of human resource management. Employees may receive financial and non-financial compensations for the work performed by them.

Financial compensation includes salary, bonus, and all the benefits and incentives, whereas non-financial compensation includes awards, rewards, citation, praise, recognition, which can motivate the employees towards highest productivity.

Objectives of Compensation:

1. The compensation should be paid to each employee on the basis of their abilities and training.
2. Compensation should be in the form of package.
3. It should motivate the employees towards increasing productivity.
4. It should be capable of taking care of employees for safety and security needs also.
5. It should be flexible and clear.
6. It should not be excessive.
7. Compensation should be decided by the management as per the norms fixed by the legislations in consultation with the union.

FACTORS AFFECTING WAGES AND SALARY LEVELS

The wage payment is an important factor affecting the labor management relations. Workers are very much concerned with the rates of wages as their standard of living

is linked to the amount of remuneration they get. Managements, however, do not come forward to pay higher wages because cost of production goes up and profits decrease to that extent. A number of factors, thus, influence the remuneration payable to the employees. The factors influencing Wage and Salary Administration can be categorized into (i) External Factors and (ii) Internal Factors.

Factors That Influence Compensation and Benefits

1. External factors influencing Wage and Salary Administration

- Demand and supply : The labor market conditions or demand and supply forces operate at the national and local levels and determine organizational wage structure. When the demand of a particular type of labor is more and supply is less then the wages will be more. On the other hand, if supply of labor is more demand on the other hand, is less then persons will be available at lower wage rates also. In the words of Mescon, 'the supply and demand compensation criterion is very closely related to the prevailing pay, comparable wage and on going wage concepts since, in essence all of these remuneration standards are determined by immediate market forces and factors.

- **Cost of living :** The wage rates are directly influenced by cost of living of a place. The workers will accept a wage which may ensure them a minimum standard of living. Wages will also be adjusted according to price index number. The increase in price index will erode the purchasing power of workers and they will demand higher wages. When the prices are stable then frequent wage increases may not be undertaken.
- **Trade unions bargaining power :** The wage rates are also influenced by the bargaining power of trade unions. Stronger the trade union higher will be the wage rates. The strength of a trade union is judged by its membership, financial position and type of leadership. Union's last weapon is strike which may also be used for getting wage increases. If the workers are disorganized and disunited then employers will be successful in offering low wages.
- **Government legislation :** To improve the working conditions of workers, government may pass a legislation for fixing minimum wages of workers. This may ensure them a minimum level of living. In under developed countries bargaining power of labor is weak and employers try to exploit workers by paying them low wages. In India, Minimum Wages Act, 1948 was passed to empower government to fix minimum wages of workers.
- **Psychological and social factors :** Psychological the level of compensation is perceived as a measure of success in life. Management should take into consideration the psychological needs of the employees while fixing the wage rates so that the employees take pride in their work. Sociologically and ethically, the employees want that the wage system should be equitable, just and fair. These factors should also be taken into consideration while devising a wage programme.
- **Economy :** Economy also has its impact on wage and salary fixation. While it may be possible for some organizations to thrive in a recession, there is no doubt that economy affects remuneration decisions. A depressed economy will probably increase the labor supply. This, in turn, should lower the going wage rate.
- **Technological development:** With the rapid growth of industries, there is a shortage of skilled resources. The technological developments have been affecting skills levels at faster rates. Thus, the wage rates of skilled employees constantly change and an organization has to keep its level up-to the mark to suit the market needs.
- **Prevailing market rates:** No enterprise can ignore prevailing or comparative wage rates. The wage rates paid in the industry or other concerns at the same place will form a base for fixing wage rates. If a concern pays low rates then workers leave

their jobs whenever they get a job somewhere else. It will not be possible to retain good workers for long.

2. Internal factors influencing Wage and Salary Administration

- **Ability to pay:** The ability to pay of an enterprise will influence wage rates to be paid. If the concern is running into losses then it may not be able to pay higher wage rate. A profitable concern may pay more to attract good workers. During the period of prosperity, workers are paid higher wages because management wants to share the profits with labor.

- **Job requirements:** Basic wages depend largely on the difficulty level, and physical and mental effort required in a particular job. The relative worth of a job can be estimated through job evaluation. Simple, routine tasks that can be done by many people with minimum skills receive relatively low pay. On the other hand, complex, challenging tasks that can be done by few people with high skill levels generally receive high pay.

- **Management strategy:** The overall strategy which a company pursues should determine to remuneration to its employees. Where the strategy of the organization is to achieve rapid growth, remuneration should be higher than what competitors pay. Where the strategy is to maintain and protect current earnings, because of the declining fortunes of the company, remuneration level needs to be average or even below average.

- **Employee:** Several employee related factors interact to determine his remuneration.

1. Performance or productivity is always rewarded with a pay increase. Rewarding performance motivates the employees to do better in future.

2. Seniority. Unions view seniority as the most objective criteria for pay increases whereas management prefer performance to effect pay increases.

3. Experience. Makes an employee gain valuable insights and is generally rewarded.

4. Potential. Organization do pay some employees based on their potential. Young managers are paid more because of their potential to perform even if they are short of experience.

METHODS OF WAGE PAYMENT

Wage payment concept is not only important for the employees but also for the employers as they are interesting in paying fewer wages. But paying low wages are not economical as they can prove to be costly for the employer. Employer is morally responsible to pay fair wages to his employees.

There are generally two methods of wage payment

- i) time wage system
- ii) piece wage system

Time wage system: in this method worker is paid for the amount of time he has spent on the job. The period of time may be an hour, a day, a week, a month and the wages depend upon the period of time. Here wages are paid for the amount of time spent not on the basis of output. Thus, it is a non variable method of wage payment.

Wages= number of hours worked* rate per hour

Suppose the worker is paid rs 10 per hour and he worked for 15 hours so his wages will be $15 * 10 = \text{rs } 150$

Applicability of time wage system:

- i) This method is used when it is difficult to fix standard time for the job.
- ii) When production process is complicated and requires high degree of skill.
- iii) When machines used are costly.
- iv) When quality of work is important.
- v) When mental work is involved.

CONCEPT OF MINIMUM WAGE ,FAIR WAGE ,LIVING WAGE

Wages have been classified into three categories:

- (1) Living wages
- (2) Minimum wages
- (3) Fair wages

(1) Living Wages-Living wages has been defined differently by different people in different countries. The best definition is given by Justice Higgins which reads

"Living wage is a wage sufficient to ensure the workman food, shelter, clothing, frugal comfort, provision for evil days etc. as regard for the skill of an artisan, if he is one". According to Fair Wages Committee Report:"

The living wage should enable the male earner to provide himself and his family not merely the basic essentials of food, clothing and shelter but a measure of frugal comfort including education for the children, protection against ill-health, requirement of essential social needs and measures of insurance against old age." Thus living wages means the provision for the bare necessities plus certain amenities considered necessary for the wellbeing of the workers in terms of his social status.

Article 43 of the Constitution of India states that the state shall endeavour to secure by suitable legislation or economic organisation or in any other way to all workers a living wage, conditions of work ensuring a decent standard of life and full enjoyment of pleasure and social and cultural opportunities. Thus, Government of India has adopted as one of the directives of the principle of state policy to ensure living wages.

(2) Minimum Wages—The minimum wage may be defined as the lowest wage necessary to maintain a worker and his family at the minimum level of subsistence, which includes food, clothing and shelter. When the government fixes minimum wage in a particular trade, the main objective is not to control or determine wages in general but to prevent the employment of workers at a wage below an amount necessary to maintain the worker at the minimum level of subsistence.

Minimum wage in a country is fixed by the government in consultation with business organisations and trade unions. The law relating to the minimum wage either states definitely the wage considered to be the minimum or the determination of the wage left to an administrative commission which from time to time determines the minimum wage according to the varying economic conditions, e.g., variation in the price level should be compensated with the variation in the wage rates because the prime aim of the minimum wage law is just to cover "minimum living cost."

The authority entrusted with the task of fixing of minimum wage should consider such factors as local economic conditions, transportation cost and the size of the units in the industry in fixing minimum wages.

The Government of India passed a Minimum Wage Act in 1948 under which farm labourers were to be paid a minimum wage between 66 paise and Rs. 1.50 per day, keeping in view local costs and standards of living. Since conditions in various parts of the country were different, the law allowed different rates of wages to be fixed in a poor country such as India. In practice, it was very difficult to enforce minimum wages effectively. Fortunately, the recent inflationary situation had pushed up the rural wages much above the minimum wages fixed by law.

Minimum wages legislation is supposed to have the following benefits:

- (i) These laws prevent unscrupulous employers from exploiting ignorant persons who possess very little bargaining power.
- (ii) These abolish the competition of the lower strata of workers with the upper grades and tend to prevent depressing of wages.
- (iii) The productivity of industry is increased by foreign employers to use the most efficient production methods and the most modern equipment, in order to enable employees to earn the living wage. But at the same time, the workers are stimulated to increase his efficiency in order to hold his job.
- (iv) Employers with high standards are protected against underselling by competitors with low standards.

But some critics of the minimum wage assert that it is impossible for a group of men to control the wages of labour by law because wages depend upon the supply and demand of labour. Minimum wages are a heavy burden to the society because persons unable to earn a living wage will be unemployed whereas earning of small wage is preferred to idleness or living on charity. However, basically, minimum wage laws are not wrong if they are wisely framed and applied. It is perfectly feasible to fix a minimum wage and forbid employment below that figure. Some industries that cannot profitably pay the wages fixed may be forced to wind up because of the financial burden. But, then, what is the use of an industry if it cannot even pay a living wages to its workers and it is better to dispense with it. Industries that can pay a living wage should, if necessary be forced to do so. The difficulties to be encountered are rather those of practical operation. The administration of the modern industry is very tedious due to the complexity of the wage system. However, if the wage limit is fixed at the very lowest minimum, the risk is slight.

(3) Fair Wages—A fair wage is something more than the minimum wages. Fair wage is a mean between the living wage and the minimum wage. While the lower limit of the fair wage must obviously be the minimum wage, the upper limit is the capacity of the industry to pay fair wage compares reasonably with the average payment of similar task in other trades or occupations requiring the same amount of ability. Fair wage depends on the present economic position as well as on its future prospects. Thus the fair wages depends upon the following factors :

- (1) Minimum Wages
- (2) Capacity of the industry to pay
- (3) Prevailing rates of wages in the same or similar occupations in the same or neighboring localities
- (4) Productivity of labour
- (5) Level of national income and its distribution.
- (6) The place of the industry in the economy of the country.

Fringe Benefits

Fringe benefits refer to the extra benefits provided to the employees in addition of normal compensation paid in terms of wages or salary. Many years ago these benefits and services were labelled "Fringe benefits" because these benefits were relatively insignificant or fringe components of the compensation. But now a days the situation is not the same. Fringe benefits are now a days a great motivator to the employees.

Features of Fringe Benefits:

1. They are supplementary forms of compensation.
2. They are paid to all the employees (unlike incentives which are paid only to the extra ordinary performers) based on their membership in the organisation.
3. Fringe benefits are indirect compensation because they are extended as a condition for employment and are not directly related with the performance.
4. These benefits may be statutory or voluntary. For example Provident funds are statutory but the transportation facility is voluntary.
5. These benefits help raise the living standards of the employees.

Types of Fringe benefits:

1. Payment for Time not worked:

- Hours of work: Factory's Act , 1948 specifies that no adult workers shall be required to work in factory more than 48 hours a week. In some organizations number of working hours per week are less than the legal requirements.
- Paid Holidays: According to Factory's Act, 1948 an adult worker shall have a weekly paid holiday, normally Sunday. When a worker is deprived of weekly paid holidays he/ she is to be compensated with the same number of holidays in the same month. Some organisations offer two weekly paid holidays.
- Shift Premium: Workers working on odd shift are to be compensated with more than the normal wage rate, generally known as premium.
- Holiday Pay: Generally organisations offer double the normal rate to those workers who work on holidays.
- Paid Vacation: Workers in mining , manufacturing and plantation who have worked for 240 days in year are entitled for paid vacations at a rate of 1 day for every 20 days worked in case of adult workers and 1 day for every 15 days worked in case of child workers.

2. Employee Security:

Physical and job security to the employees should also be provided with a view to ensure security to the employee and his family members. When the employee's services get confirmed, his job becomes secure. Further, a minimum and continuous wage or salary gives a sense of security to the life.

- **Retrenchment Compensation:** The Industrial Disputes Act, 1947 provides for the payment of compensation in case of lay off and retrenchment. Thenon-seasonal industrial establishment employing 50 or more workers have to give one month's advance notice or one month's wages to all the employees who are retrenched after one year's continuous service. The compensation is paid at the rate of 45 day wage for every completed year of service. Workers are eligible for compensation as stated above in case of closing down of undertakings.
- **Lay Off Compensation:** In case of lay off the employees are entitled to lay off compensation at the rate equal to 50% of the total of the basic wage and dearness allowance for the period of their lay off except for the weekly holidays. Lay off compensation can normally be paid up to 45 days a year.

3. Safety and Healthy:

Employee's safety and health should be taken care in order to protect the employees against accidents, unhealthy working conditions and to protect the worker's productive capacity. In India, Factory's Act, 1948 stipulated certain requirements regarding working conditions with a view to provide safe working environment. These provisions relate to cleanliness, disposal of waste and effluents, ventilation and temperature, dust and fumes, artificial humidification, overcrowding, lighting, urinals, drinking water, latrines, spittoons etc.

Provisions relating to safety measures include fencing of machinery, work on or near machinery in motion, employment of young persons on dangerous machines, self acting machines, casing of new machinery, hoists and lifts excessive weights, lifting machines, chains, ropes explosive or inflammable dust , gas etc.

4. Workmen's Compensation:

In addition to safety and health measures, provisions for payments of compensation has also been made under the Workmen's Compensation Act, 1923. The Act is intended to meet the contingencies of death and invalidity of worker due to employment injury and occupational diseases specified under the Act as the sole responsibility of employer.

Under the Act the amount of compensation depends upon the nature of injury and monthly wages of the employee. Dependents of the employee are eligible for compensation in case of death of the employee.

BENEFITS OF FRINGE BENEFITS

- **Sickness benefits:** Sickness benefit is roughly 50% of average daily wages and is payable for 91 days during 2 consecutive benefit period.
- **Medical benefit:** The Employee's state Insurance Scheme provides full medical care in the form of medical attendance, treatments, drugs and injections, specialist consultation, and hospitalization to insured person and also to members of their families where the facility has been extended to the families.
- **Temporary Disablement benefits:** TDB is payable to an employee suffers from employment injury or occupational diseases and is certified to temporarily incapable of work.
- **Permanent Disablement Benefit:** PDB is payable to an employee who suffers permanent residual disablement as a result of employment accident or occupational diseases. The maximum rate of PDB can be equal to TDB.
- **Maternity Benefits:** Maternity benefits is payable to and insured women in the following cases subject to contributory conditions: – (a) Confinement, (b) Miscarriage or medical termination of pregnancy (MTP), (c) sickness arising out of pregnancy.

6. Voluntary Arrangement:

However, most of the large organisations provide health services over and above the legal requirements to their employees free of cost by setting up hospitals, clinics, dispensaries, and homeopathic dispensaries. Company's elaborate health service programmes includes:

1. Providing health maintenance services, emergency care, on the job treatment for minor complaints, health counselings, medical supervision in rehabilitation, accidents and sickness prevention, health education programmes, treatment in employee colonies etc.
2. Medical benefits are extended to employee family members and to the retired employees and their family members.
3. Small organisations which cannot setup hospitals provide the medical services through local hospitals and doctors. Sometimes they provides reimbursements of medical expenses borne by the employee.

7. Welfare and Recreational facilities:

These benefits include canteens, consumer stores, credit societies, housing, legal aids, employee counselling, welfare organisation, holiday homes, educational facilities, transportation, picnics and parties etc.

Compensation Plans & Business Strategy

The general practice in devising remuneration is to pay what competitors pay or to adhere to the 'corporate policy' but the actual remuneration plan should be integrated with the business strategy of every organization, and should not be strictly a matter of what is being paid in the market place. It should be an assessment of what must be paid to attract and retain the right people, what the organisation can afford, and what will be required to meet the organisation's strategic goals.

Business Strategy	Market Position & Maturity	Remuneration Strategy	Blend Of Remuneration
Investing to grow	Rapid growth to maturity	Stimulate entrepreneurship	High cash with above average incentive for individual performance. Modest benefits.
Manage earnings & protect markets	Normal growth to maturity	Reward management skills	Average cash with moderate incentives on individual, unit, or corporate performance. Standard benefits.
Harvest earnings – reinvest elsewhere	No real growth or decline	Stress on cost control	Below-average cash with small incentive tied to cost control. Standard benefits.

In companies that are growing rapidly, business strategy focuses on investing to grow. The remuneration strategy should stimulate an enterprising and entrepreneurial style of management, with high cash payments, above-average incentives and modest benefits.

In companies witnessing a normal growth to maturity, business strategy is oriented primarily towards managing earnings and protecting markets. The remuneration strategy

should aim at rewarding management skills and should be a blend of average cash payments, moderate incentives and standard benefits.

In companies where there is no real growth or decline, the most appropriate strategy is to harvest earnings and reinvest them elsewhere. The remuneration strategy should stress on control of costs, with below-average cash payments, modest incentives are tied directly to control costs and standard benefits.

Thus, companies do the following, viewing remuneration from a strategic perspective:

1. They recognise remuneration as a pivotal control and incentive mechanism that can be used flexibly by the management to attain business objectives.
2. They make the pay system an integral part of strategy formulation.
3. They integrate pay considerations into strategic decision-making processes, such as those that involve planning and control.

They view the company's performance as the ultimate criterion of the success of the strategic pay decisions and operational remuneration programs.

Devising a Remuneration Plan

Any remuneration plan must be understandable, workable and acceptable. The remuneration scheme must have two components – a base rate and the scope for increasing the base rate. The remuneration plan must be determined keeping in mind the requisites and the components.

Remuneration Model

Job Description: Job description are crucial in designing pay systems, for, they help to identify important job characteristics. They also help determine, define and weigh compensable factors (factors for which an organization is willing to pay-skill, experience, effort and working environment).

Job Evaluation: The next step in pay fixation is to establish relative worth of jobs by employing job evaluation. A number of techniques are available to evaluate jobs. For example, in the point-ranking method of job evaluation, each job is analysed and defined in terms of the compensable factors an organization has agreed to adopt. Points are assigned to each degree of a compensable factor, such as responsibility.

Job Hierarchy: The points assigned to all compensable factors are aggregated. The total points scored will help to establish the hierarchy of job worth, starting from the highest point total to the lowest point total.

Pay Surveys: Job hierarchy being established, the next step is to establish pay differentials. Before fixing wage and salary differentials, prevailing wage and salary rates in the labour market need to be ascertained. Hence the relevance of pay surveys.

One way of collecting pay details is to conduct a survey. This requires that a sample of key jobs and a sample of companies need to be selected. Questionnaires could be mailed to select companies, requesting them to furnish pay details relating to key jobs. Information can also be collected over the telephone.

There are also other sources of collecting pay details. Labour departments of the government, trade unions, and professional bodies, and consulting firms provide copious amount of information about the prevailing wage and salary rates.

Job evaluation helps establish job hierarchy. Through surveys, the rate for key jobs in the labour market is also known. The next logical step is to determine pay structures.

Pricing Jobs: In pricing jobs, the job evaluation worth is matched with the labour market worth. Two activities need to be performed: (i) establishing the appropriate pay level for each job, and (ii) grouping the different pay levels into pay grades.

Pay levels: in order to set a pay level, the points assigned and the survey wage rates are combined through the use of a graph called scatter gram. In the figure below, the vertical axis represent pay rates. The horizontal axis is used for points. The total points and the wage rates for each key job are plotted to obtain the scatter gram.

The development of a wage-trend line

Thus, each dot in the above figure represents the intersection of the point value and the market-determined wage rate for a particular key job. For example, key job A is worth 500 points and is paid Rs. 60 per hour. Similarly, key job B earns 700 points and has a prevailing rate of Rs. 70 per hour.

The dots that represent key jobs can be used to draw a wage-trend line as close to as many points as possible, employing a statistical technique called *least squares method of regression*. This method relates point values to wage rates in the labour market. If the employer wants to lead or lag behind in the market rate by a given percentage, the wage-trend line can be moved up or down by the same percentage.

Determining pay grades: A pay grade comprises jobs of approximately equal difficulty or importance. Where point-ranking method of job evaluation is used, the grade consists of jobs falling within a range of points. It is convenient to organize jobs into groups, also called classes, so that there are limited number of wage rates. Where individual jobs are retained, an organization will have hundreds of remuneration rates. The existence of hundreds of separate wage rates would be meaningless as differences between jobs might be just a few rupees.

Where grouping of jobs is done, the wage-curve line is to be replaced with a series of ascending dashes, as shown in the figure below. Thus all jobs in the same class will receive the same wage rate. A job valued at 105 points, for example, receives the same pay as a job with 145 points.

Question bank

1-Compensation can be _____ benefits.

- | | |
|-----------------|----------------------|
| a. Monetary | c. both 'a' and 'b' |
| b. Non-monetary | d. None of the above |

(Ans: c)

2-Wages represents _____ rates of pay.

- | | |
|-----------|------------|
| a. Hourly | c. Weekly |
| b. Daily | d. Monthly |

(Ans: a)

3-_____ are also called 'payments by results'.

- | | |
|---------------|--------------------|
| a. Allowances | c. incentives |
| b. Claims | d. fringe benefits |

(Ans: c)

4-Incentives depends upon

- | | |
|-----------------|---------------------|
| a. productivity | c. profits |
| b. sales | d. All of the above |

(Ans: d)

5-The following is paid only at the time of employees exit after serving more than five years

- | | |
|----------------|-------------|
| a. Perquisites | c. Gratuity |
|----------------|-------------|

- b. Claims
(Ans: c)
- d. Allowances

6-The following is a perquisites.

- a. Club membership
b. Provident fund
(Ans: a)
- c. Medical allowance
d. Group insurance

7- 'A behaviour which has rewarding experience is likely to be repeated' is postulated by

- a. Reinforcement and expectancy theory
b. Equity theory
(Ans: a)
- c. Agency theory
d. None of the above

8- 'A fair day work for fair day pay' denotes a sense of _____ felt by employees.

- a. Responsibility
b. Equity
(Ans: b)
- c. Happiness
d. Respect

9-The remuneration system needs to meet the following type(s) of equity

- a. Internal
b. External
(Ans: d)
- c. Individual
d. All of the above

10-Which of the following factor influence(s) employee compensation?

- a. Labour market
b. Cost of living.
(Ans: d)
- c. Labour unions
d. All of the above

11-Match the following

- | Business strategy | Compensation strategy |
|--|---------------------------------|
| A. Invest to grow | 1. Stress on cost control |
| B. Manage earnings – protect markets | 2. Stimulate entrepreneurialism |
| C. Harvest earnings – reinvest elsewhere | 3. Reward management skills |

- a. A-1, B-2, C-3
b. A-2, B-1, C-3
(Ans: c)
- c. A-2, B-3, C-1
d. A-3, B-1, C-2

12-Any compensation plan must be

- a. Understandable, workable, acceptable
b. Reasonable, workable, acceptable.
compensable
- c. Understandable, feasible,
acceptable
- d. Understandable, workable,

(Ans: a)

13-The following is not a part of remuneration model

- a. Job description
- b. Job evaluation
- c. Job hierarchy
- d. Job analysis

(Ans: d)

14-Elitist remuneration systems are prevalent among

- a. Well established firms
- b. Companies with mature products
- c. Companies with limited competition
- d. All of the above

(Ans: d)

15-In organized industrial establishments pay review takes place once in ____ years.

- a. Three
- b. Seven
- c. Ten
- d. Fifteen

(Ans: a)

16-Equal remuneration Act 1976, prohibits discrimination in matters relating to remuneration on the basis of

- a. Religion
- b. Region
- c. Sex
- d. All of the above

(Ans: d)

17-The following is not a concept of wage

- a. Daily wages
- b. Minimum wages
- c. Fair wages
- d. Living wages

(Ans: a)

18-_____ can be fixed by comparison with an accepted standard wage

- a. Minimum wages
- b. Fair wages
- c. Living wages
- d. All of the above

(Ans: b)

19-A _____ must be fixed considering the general economic conditions of the country.

- c. Minimum wages
- d. Fair wages
- c. Living wages
- d. All of the above

(Ans: c)

20- How many components are there in remuneration?

- a. 4
- b. 5
- c. 6
- d. 7

ANSWER: b

21- Which of the following option is a component of remuneration?

- a. Fringe Benefits
- b. Commitment
- c. External equity
- d. Motivation

ANSWER: a

22- What is the alternate name for incentives?

- a. Gratuity
- b. Paid holidays
- c. Payments by result
- d. None of the above

23. Compensation quartile strategy in which 75% of employers pays below than market and remaining 25% pays compensations higher than market is called

- A. forth quartile strategy
- B. third quartile strategy
- C. second quartile strategy
- D. first quartile strategy

•Answer: B

24. Concept in which whole or part of yearly pay increase is paid as single payment is called

- A.consumer price index adjustment
- B.lump sum increase
- C.cost of living adjustment
- D.all of above

Answer: D

25. Factors such as earnings level, discretionary authority and percentage of time spent time in manual work are factors that must be held to define

- A.overtime pay status
- B.exempt status
- C.non-exempt status
- D.distributive status

• Answer: C

26. Perceived fairness between what person receives and what person did is classified as

- A.procedural justice
- B.distributive justice
- C.recency justice
- D.equity

• Answer: D

27. Key issues related to internal equity are

- A.distributive justice
- B.procedural justice
- C.primacy justice
- D.both a and b

• Answer: D

28. Collection of data consisting compensation rates of all workers who performs similar jobs in other organizations classified as

- A.KSA survey
 - B.pay survey
 - Answer: B
 - C.job survey
 - D.skills survey
29. Basic compensations given to employees as salaries or wages are called
- A.base pay
 - B.wages
 - Answer: A
 - C.variable pay
 - D.salaries
30. Situation in organization in which differences of individual pay with different level of performance becomes small is classified as
- A.pay compression
 - B.grade compression
 - Answer: A
 - C.equity compression
 - D.matrix compression
31. Perceived fairness of all procedures and process that are considered to make decisions about employees and their pay is called
- A.primacy justice
 - B.rency justice
 - Answer: C
 - C.procedural justice
 - D.distributive justice
32. Factors that are common in group of jobs and are used to identify value of job are called
- A.primacy factors
 - B.exemption factors
 - Answer: C
 - C.compensable factors
 - D.equity factors
33. Situation occur when creditor wants employer to pays off debt by deducting portion of amount from wages of employees as ordered by law court is called
- A.distributive state laws
 - B.procedural state laws
 - Answer: C
 - C.garnishment laws
 - D.state laws
34. Tangible components of compensation programs usually designed by organization consists of
- A.indirect compensation
 - B.rency compensation
 - Answer: D
 - C.direct compensation
 - D.both a and c
35. Multiple plans specifying business unit and family while giving compensation are considered in approach called
- A.rency compensation approach
 - B.traditional compensation approach
 - Answer: B
 - C.total rewards approach
 - D.primacy compensation approach

36. Graph which shows relationship between job value which is determined rates of pay survey and job evaluation points is classified as

- A.market line
- B.pay line
- C.regression line
- D.pay structure line
- Answer: A

37. Compensation quartile strategy in which 50% of employers pays below than market and remaining pays compensations higher than market is called

- A.second quartile strategy
- B.forth quartile strategy
- C.first quartile strategy
- D.third quartile strategy
- Answer: A

38. Position such as administrative, professionals and executive are classified as

- A.exempt employees
- B.non-exempt employees
- C.salaried exempt employees
- D.salaried nonexempt employees
- Answer: A

39. Jobs in organization that require similar knowledge, abilities and skills and are performed by individuals having similar duties are classified as

- A.benchmark job
- B.job promotion structure
- C.compensable evaluation
- D.job evaluation
- Answer: A

40. Group of all jobs which have same worth of job are classified as

- A.non-exemption grade
- B.regression grade
- C.exemption grade
- D.pay grade
- Answer: D

41. Employees to whom overtime is not paid under restriction of Fair Labor Standards Act are called

- A.exempt employees
- B.non-exempt employees
- C.salaried exempt employees
- D.salaried nonexempt employees
- Answer: A

42. Concept in which pay for jobs that require similar skills, abilities and knowledge without taking duties into consideration is called

- A.pay equity
- B.pay exemption
- C.pay primacy
- D.distributive pay
- Answer: A

43. Type of rewards employees get in form of monetary or non-monetary benefits are classified as

- A.extrinsic rewards
- B.leniency rewards
- C.primacy rewards
- D.intrinsic rewards

- Answer: A

44. According to total rewards approach, variable pay of employee is

- A.added into base pay
- B.subtracted from base pay
- C.multiplied to base pay
- D.divided to base pay
- Answer: A

45. Payments made to employees for amount of time in which employee has worked are classified as

- A.variable pay
- B.salaries
- C.base pay
- D.wages
- Answer: D

46. Compensation philosophy according to which compensations are not paid according to span of service but consider performance level is called

- A.performance orientation philosophy
- B.rency orientation philosophy
- C. primacyorientation philosophy
- D. entitlement orientation philosophy
- Answer: OptionA

47. Systematic way of determining worth of all jobs within any organization is called

- A.compensable evaluation
- B.job evaluation
- C.benchmark job
- D.job promotion structure
- Answer: B

Self-Assessment Questions:

1. What do you understand about compensation? Explain the objectives of compensation.
2. State the objectives of compensation administration.
3. What is compensation? Explain the factors affecting wage and salary.
4. What is compensation administration? Explain the methods of wage payment.
5. Explain the concept of wage.
6. Explain the concept of minimum wage and fair wage system.
7. What are fringe benefits? Explain the features of fringe benefits.
8. What do you mean by fringe benefits? Explain briefly the types of fringe benefits.
9. State the meaning of fringe benefits. Explain briefly the benefits of fringe benefits.
10. Explain the role of wage and salary in compensation administration.
11. Explain the features of fringe benefits.
12. Explain the different methods of wage payment.

UNIT IV -

Employee participation and relation

Managing Employee Attitudes - Participation and motivation - Types and degree of participation - Benefits of participation - Managing grievances and Discipline - Grievance Procedure – collective Bargaining - Settlement of Disputes, Industrial Relations

Future Challenges of HR

Managing Human Resources in future - Managing Human Resources in International Business - Human Resource Accounting and Audit - Globalization and HRM - International Assignments and Political Instability Technology and HRM - HR Legislation and the Future of HRM - Generational Differences - Future Trends in Human Capital and Talent Management

Introduction

The importance of Human Resource Management can be traced back to Vedic ages! Yes, in the Bhagavad Gita, Lord Krishna not only makes Arjuna spiritually enlightened, but also teaches him the art of self management, anger management, stress management, conflict management, transformational leadership, motivation, goal setting and many other aspects which are now essential parts of any HRM curriculum. Human resource management is a process of bringing people and organizations together so that the goals of each other are met. The role of HR manager is shifting from that of a protector and screener to the role of a planner and change agent. Personnel directors are the new corporate heroes. The name of the game today in business is Personnel. Nowadays it is not possible to show a good financial or operating report unless your personnel relations are in order.

Significance of Human Resource Management

The Human Resources (HR) function provides significant support and advice to line management. The attraction, preservation and development of high calibre people are a source of competitive advantage for our business, and are the responsibility of HR. Industries in India in general and Human Resources function in particular, will open new avenues in future. One clear trend concerns joint decision making. From largely paternalistic efforts to help needy employees solve their personnel problems, industrial organizations in India have moved to a joint consultative process of decision making which influences employees.

The scope of Human Resource function depends, to a large extent, on its importance in the organization and the attitude of the top management to executives in the HR department. The basic objectives of Human Resource Department of an organization are an effective and efficient utilization of human resources, harmonious relations among all employees and maximum development of individuals. These objectives are generally achieved by hiring capable people, using their efforts effectively and encouraging a willingness to work kind of environment to achieve organization's goals.

Human Resources manager's style of supervision, his plans, policies and procedures have a significant impact on an individual's performance. Changes in HR function, to a large extent reflect changing needs of the organization. Changes in the organizational atmosphere, hopes and aspirations of the workforce, and the external environment all demand an innovative problem-solving approach from the personnel department.

The functions of HR manager in future will definitely be enhanced from traditional areas such as management of manpower planning, recruitment, selection, training, internal mobility and welfare.

Role of HR Managers in Present Times

HR Managers today are focusing attention on the following-

Policies- HR policies are based on trust, openness, equity and consensus.

Motivation- Create conditions in which people are willing to work with zeal, initiative and enthusiasm; make people feel like winners.

Relations- Fair treatment of people and prompt redress of grievances which would pave the way for healthy work-place relations.

Change Agent- Prepare workers to accept technological changes by clarifying doubts.

Quality Consciousness- Commitment to quality in all aspects of personnel administration will ensure success.

Due to the new trends in HR, in a nutshell the HR manager should treat people as resources, reward them equitably, and integrate their aspirations with corporate goals through suitable HR policies.

Traditionally, the role of the Human Resource professional in many organizations has been to serve as the systematizing, policing arm of executive management.

In this role, the HR professional served executive agendas well, but was frequently viewed as a road block by much of the rest of the organization. The role of the HR manager must

parallel the needs of his or her changing organization. Successful organizations are becoming more adaptive, resilient, quick to change direction and customer-centered. Within this environment, the HR professional, who is considered necessary by line managers, is a strategic partner, an employee sponsor or advocate and a change mentor.

Strategic Partner

In today's organizations, to guarantee their viability and ability to contribute, HR managers need to think of themselves as strategic partners. In this role, the HR person contributes to the development of and the accomplishment of the organization-wide business plan and objectives.

The HR business objectives are established to support the attainment of the overall strategic business plan and objectives. The tactical HR representative is deeply knowledgeable about the design of work systems in which people succeed and contribute. This strategic partnership impacts HR services such as the design of work positions; hiring; reward, recognition and strategic pay; performance development and appraisal systems; career and succession planning; and employee development.

Employee Advocate

As an employee sponsor or advocate, the HR manager plays an integral role in organizational success via his knowledge about and advocacy of people. This advocacy includes expertise in how to create a work environment in which people will choose to be motivated, contributing, and happy.

Fostering effective methods of goal setting, communication and empowerment through responsibility, builds employee ownership of the organization. The HR professional helps establish the organizational culture and climate in which people have the competency, concern and commitment to serve customers well.

In this role, the HR manager provides employee development opportunities, employee assistance programs, gain sharing and profit-sharing strategies, organization development interventions, due process approaches to problem solving and regularly scheduled communication opportunities.

Change Agent

People often resist change. A significant change occurs when an individual moves from his home environment to work environment, or when there is a transition from a traditional work method to an advanced technological method. Technological advancement brings about changes which a worker may resist. At this point, the personnel manager has a crucial role to play. He has to convince workers of the need for automation and prepare them to accept changes well before they are introduced. Implementation is mainly a method of getting new methods and ideas accepted and used with the least friction but with ample scope of improvement. Hence changes should be phased gradually and thoughtfully without provoking negative reactions from the workers.

The constant evaluation of the effectiveness of the organization results in the need for the HR professional to frequently support change. Both knowledge about and the ability to execute successful change strategies make the HR professional exceptionally valued. Knowing how to link change to the strategic needs of the organization will minimize employee dissatisfaction and resistance to change.

The HR professional contributes to the organization by constantly assessing the effectiveness of the HR function. He also sponsors change in other departments and in work practices. To promote the overall success of his organization, he supports the identification of the organizational mission, vision, values, goals and action plans. Finally, he helps determine the measures that will tell his organization how well it is succeeding in all of this.

Activity A:

Prepare the activity report of an HR manager of a company known for its proactive HR Practices.

Recent Trends In HRM

Over the years, highly skilled and knowledge based jobs are increasing while low skilled jobs are decreasing. This calls for future skill mapping through proper HRM initiatives. Indian organizations are also witnessing a change in systems, management cultures and philosophy due to the global alignment of Indian organizations. There is a need for multi skill development. Role of HRM is becoming all the more important.

Some of the recent trends that are being observed are as follows:

The recent quality management standards ISO 9001 and ISO 9004 of 2000 focus more on people centric organizations. Organizations now need to prepare themselves in order to address people centered issues with commitment from the top management, with renewed thrust on HR issues, more particularly on training.

To move ahead of competition in this world of uncertainty, organizations have introduced six- sigma practices. Six- sigma uses rigorous analytical tools with leadership from the top and develops a method for sustainable improvement. These practices improve organizational values and helps in creating defect free product or services at minimum cost.

Human resource outsourcing is a new accession that makes a traditional HR department redundant in an organization. Exult, the international pioneer in HR BPO has already roped in Bank of America, international players BPA moco & over the years plan to spread their business to most of the Fortune 500 companies.

With the increase of global job mobility, recruiting competent people is also increasingly becoming difficult, especially in India. Therefore by creating an enabling culture, organizations are also required to work out a retention strategy for the existing skilled manpower.

Forces Changing HRM

In the 1990s several forces were shaping the broad field of HRM. The first key force, new technologies— particularly information technology—brought about the decentralization of communications and the shake- up of existing paradigms of human interaction and organizational theory. Satellite communications, computers and networking systems, fax machines, and other devices were facilitating rapid change. Moreover, since these technologies helped blur the lines between work time and personal time by enabling employees to work at home, Human Resource Management professionals began adopting “Management by Objective” approaches to human resources instead of the traditional “management by Sight” method.

A second important change affecting HRM was new organizational structures that began to emerge during the 1980s and continued through the 1990s. Because many companies began expanding their operations and diversifying their products and services, the central decision-making system failed to respond quickly enough to managers’ needs and concerns. Therefore, companies started scrapping traditional, hierarchical organizational structures in favor of flatter, decentralized management systems. Consequently, fewer managers were involved in the decision-making process and companies were adopting more of a team approach to management. HRM professionals, as the agents of change, were charged with reorganizing workers and increasing their efficiency. These efforts also resulted in the proliferation of part-time, or contract, employees, which required human resource strategies that contrasted with those applicable to full time workers.

A third change factor was accelerating market globalization, which was increasing competition and demanding greater performance out of workers, often at diminished levels of compensation. To compete abroad, companies were looking to their HRM professionals to enhance initiatives related to quality, productivity, and innovation.

Other factors changing HRM include: an accelerating rate of change and turbulence, resulting in higher employee turnover and the need for more responsive, open-minded workers; rapidly changing demographics; and increasing income disparity as the demand for highly educated workers increases at the expense of lower-wage employees.

Emerging Concepts

Of late, a number of new concepts have emerged in the management field to improve the overall effectiveness of the organizations. The HR manager not only has to know them well but has to prepare himself/herself to implement some of these new ideas.

Total Quality Management

The concept of TQM is based on the 14 principles of Deming that deal with this subject. Deming was born and brought up in USA and migrated to Japan in the early 50's, where he evolved these total quality principles. TQM is a culture based on the realization that the high quality of products and services and associated customer satisfaction are the keys to organizational survival.

At its core, Total Quality Management (TQM) is a management approach to long-term success through customer satisfaction.

In a TQM effort, all members of an organization participate in improving processes, products, services and the culture in which they work.

The methods for implementing this approach come from the teachings of such quality leaders as Philip B. Crosby, W. Edwards Deming, Armand V. Feigenbaum, Kaoru Ishikawa and Joseph M. Juran.⁴

A core concept in implementing TQM is Deming's 14 points, a set of management practices to help companies increase their quality and productivity:

Create constancy of purpose for improving products and services.

Adopt the new philosophy.

Cease dependence on inspection to achieve quality.

End the practice of awarding business on price alone; instead, minimize total cost by working with a single supplier.

Improve constantly and forever every process for planning, production and service.

Institute training on the job.

Adopt and institute leadership.

Drive out fear.

Break down barriers between staff areas.

Eliminate slogans, exhortations and targets for the workforce.

Eliminate numerical quotas for the workforce and numerical goals for management.

Remove barriers that rob people of pride of workmanship, and eliminate the annual rating or merit system.

Institute a vigorous program of education and self-improvement for everyone.

Put everybody in the company to work accomplishing the transformation.

Assessment Centres

An assessment centre is a comprehensive, standardized procedure in which multiple assessment techniques such as situational exercises and job simulation (business games, discussions, reports, and presentations) are used to evaluate employees for a variety of manpower decisions.

“An assessment centre consists of a standardized evaluation of behaviour based on multiple inputs. Several trained observers and techniques are used. Judgments about behaviour are made by these specially trained observers. At the end of the assessment the assessors get together to share their data which is scientifically recorded on a set of evaluation forms. They come to a consensus on the assessments of each candidate. Most frequently the approach has been applied to individuals being considered for selection, promotion, placement, or special training and development in management.

History of Assessment Centres: Assessment centres methodology is known to have been used or recommended at least 1500 years ago in India as mentioned in Kautilya’s Arthashastra. Different methods of assessing a candidate for ministerial positions have been spelt out in the Arthashastra including: observation, performance appraisal, assessment by those who knew him, interviewing, and other forms of testing.

Early application of assessment centres can be traced to the German military assessment programme developed for selection of officers for the German Army. Both multiple assessment techniques and multiple assessors to evaluate complex behaviour with special focus on leadership were used. Assessment was based on subjective opinions and very little rating was done.

How are Assessment Centres Different Now?: Early assessment centres were used essentially for selection purposes since the traditional methods were thought to be inadequate. The assessment centre method since then has been subjected to scrutiny and research much more than any other personnel practice.⁵ Because of the high quality research and high reported validity, the methodology finds widespread use in a number of organizations. Besides selection, it is used for early identification of management talent, promotion, and diagnosis of developmental needs.

The basic purpose of Assessment Centre is:

Making selection and promotion decisions; and

Identify the strengths and weaknesses of an individual for development purposes. The requirements of Assessment Centre are listed below:

Multiple assessment techniques must be used like in basket exercises, management games, leaderless group discussions, tests, personality inventories etc.

Multiple assessors must be used. They can be line managers who are two to three levels senior to the candidate and or professional psychologists.

Judgment should be based on pooling of information among assessors.

An overall evaluation of behavior should be made, separate from the observation of behavior.

Simulation exercises must be used.

Quality Circles

Quality Circles are (informal) groups of employees who voluntarily meet together on a regular basis to identify, define, analyze and solve work related problems.

Usually the members of a particular team (quality circle) should be from the same work area or who do similar work so that the problems they select will be familiar to all of them. In addition, interdepartmental or cross functional quality circles may also be formed.

An ideal size of quality circle is seven to eight members. But the number of members in a quality circle can vary.

The Main Objectives of Quality Circles are

Promote job involvement

Create problem solving capability

Improve communication

Promote leadership qualities

Promote personal development

Develop a greater awareness for cleanliness

Develop greater awareness for safety

Improve morale through closer identity of employee objectives with organization's objectives

Reduce errors.

Enhance quality

Inspire more effective team work

Build an attitude of problem prevention

Promote cost reduction

Develop harmonious manager, supervisor and worker relationship

Improve productivity

Reduce downtime of machines and equipment

Increase employee motivation

Problem Solving Tools and Techniques Used by Quality Circles: Given below are the most commonly used tools and techniques. These are called the old QC tools:

Brainstorming.

Pareto analysis.

Cause and effect diagram (or fish bone diagram or Ishikawa diagram).

Histogram.

Scatter diagram

Stratification

Check sheet

Control charts and graphs

New QC Tools: Quality circles started using additional seven tools as they started maturing. These are:

Relations diagram.

Affinity diagram.

Systematic diagram or Tree diagram.

Matrix diagram.

Matrix data analysis diagram.

PDPC (Process Decision Program Chart).

Arrow diagram.

Benefits of QC:

Self development.

Promotes leadership qualities among participants.

Recognition.

Achievement satisfaction.

Promotes group/team working.

Serves as cementing force between management/non-management groups.

Promotes continuous improvement in products and services.

Brings about a change in environment of more productivity, better quality, reduced costs, safety and corresponding rewards.

While some of the organizations have started practicing these ideas, a large number are still waiting to see the effects elsewhere.

Given their significance in quality improvement and involvement of people, these ideas show tremendous potential for widespread acceptance. The HR managers have the responsibility to educate other managers about benefits coming from them and help them implement these ideas.

The HR manager faces challenge to involve himself in all functional areas of an organization. He will need training not only in human resources but in production, marketing, finance, etc., to give him a greater understanding of the problems of employees in various functional areas.

Impact of Technology on HRM

Technological advances in office equipment over the past thirty years have enabled organizations to improve operating efficiencies, improve communications, reduce costs, increase their global presence, and gain competitive advantage through the implementation of information technology systems.

Since the 1960's, Information Technology has dramatically changed the landscape of the workplace through advances in office equipment, speed of information transmission and methods of communication. From a human capital perspective, Information Technology has allowed companies and their employees to increase efficiencies, communicate more rapidly, and work from remote locations. The ability of the workforce to perform organizational tasks from a remote location also known as "Telecommuting" has enabled employees to improve quality of life and manage the professional and personal aspects of their lives.

From an operational perspective, investments in Information Technology by organizations willing to embrace technology have resulted in increased efficiencies, cost reductions, global expansion, improved intra-company and customer communications, improved reporting and tracking methods, and increased competitive advantage in the market place.

Computers loaded with word processing, spreadsheet analysis and presentation software programs have become standard fixtures on each employee's desk. Some of the workforce became mobile, conducting business outside of the traditional office settings through the use of Personal Digital Assistants (PDAs), cellular phones and laptop computers. The initial users of mobile technology were salespeople and executive management; however, easier access to

the internet allowed more employees to become “Telecommuters,” who conducted work-related activities either from their homes or from some other remote location.

Technological advances in electronic communication may continue to decrease the need for traditional office setting while increasing the number of telecommuters. Electronic capabilities will also continue to affect outsourcing, off-shoring and globalization efforts by many organizations.

Collaboration technologies, currently being enhanced by Microsoft and IBM, enables companies to conduct “virtual meetings” . In a virtual meeting, employees from remote locations conduct real-time meetings from their own computers using peer-to-peer software. Participants can see one another on computer screens, share computer space and make to product designs or contract documents via a “virtual whiteboard.”

Workforce Trends

Telecommuting: Telecommuting is working from one’s home or some other remote location outside the company’s office. Telecommuting offers benefits to both employees and companies. For employees, telecommuting increases quality of life by enabling a meshing of personal and professional lives. The ability to work from home can assist workers with child/elder care issues, transportation restrictions, or employees who may be physically unable to report to work on a daily basis due to health-related issues (e.g., need for regular medical treatments such as dialysis or chemotherapy). Other economic benefits that companies can realize from telecommuting include productivity gains, reduced absenteeism, reduced employee turnover costs, reduced real estate costs, and reduced relocation costs to name a few.

Globalization: In the future, multinational companies (corporations operating in more than one country) may utilize telecommuting to attract local talent that can work effectively across international borders through electronic communication. Training such “home grown talent” can allow companies to reduce international relocation expenses, manage competition levels for talented resources, and reduce issues related to working in foreign countries such as personal safety, security, political, and regulatory issues.

Reducing globalization efforts through telecommuting can help to address some of the issues related to dealing with international workforces, such as language barriers, cultural relationship differences, and time zone differences that often lead to companies needing to maintain continuous operations known as “24/7”.

Outsourcing/Off-shoring: Outsourcing is defined as “turning over all or part of an organization’s information systems operation to outside contractors or service providers”. Outsourcing seems to be the wave of the future. Many companies are outsourcing parts of

their operations in order to move parts of their businesses off site in order to focus on their core competencies and try to give them an advantage over their peers. One of the more popular departments which are outsourced is the Human Resources Department. This is because most companies aren't focused on HR and their needs might be better served by an outside company. There are advantages and disadvantages to outsourcing this vital department.

Offshoring refers to outsourcing in another country. Conceptually, outsourcing and offshoring can be viewed together, since both involve employing individuals outside of the organization to handle operational work.

There are some major drawbacks to sending operations overseas, such as a loss of domestic talent, loss of intellectual assets, decreased levels of customer satisfaction resulting from diminished organizational values that do not translate across cultures, and threats to organizational performance

Advantages of Outsourcing

Cost Savings: The main benefit to outsourcing the HR department is the cost savings which will be associated with such a move. These cost savings can manifest themselves in several ways. Many times a company can get the same level of service for less cost. They can then use the savings to reinvest in their business. By doing this, they might be able to hire more people or operate more efficiently which might put them a step above their competitors.

Regaining Primary Focus: Outsourcing also allows a company to regain its primary focus. When there is an internal HR department, senior management may have to spend some time dealing with that department's issues. This is time which might be better spent on whatever business the company is in. The company as a whole will begin to shift toward its primary business.

Disadvantages of Outsourcing

Employee Morale: There are some drawbacks to outsourcing, however. The biggest of these is the morale of the employees of the outsourcing company. "Outsourcing" is a loaded word which brings connotations of sending jobs overseas and the loss of income. If the employees aren't behind the move to an offsite HR department, there may be less productivity from them. Any company considering moving the HR department off site should carefully gauge the attitude of the employees to get a feel for how this will affect them.

Loss of Expertise: Another disadvantage to this process is a loss of in-house expertise. When there is an in-house HR department, any questions related to labor laws or benefits can be answered quickly and sufficiently. If the HR is done off-site, it can cause a delay in knowing how to proceed in an employee issue, or worse, a manager may act in conflict with the law, opening the company up to bigger issues in the workplace.

Issues with the Workplace of the Future: Security is the main issue facing companies with mobile workforces. Employees in the field, such as salespeople or telecommuters, have access to “mission critical” data and pose a significant threat to organizational systems security. There are numerous potential breaches of security related to mobile electronic devices such as PDAs and laptop computers that can be misplaced, stolen or damaged. The challenge facing IT departments is to protect sensitive company data, enable secure remote access, and provide user-friendly and productive electronic tools for its mobile workforce. IT departments must also implement an education process for training employees not to use unauthorized devices or install any unauthorized programs that might threaten the integrity of company data.

E-Human Resource Management

Nature of e-HRM

E-HRM is the relatively new term for this IT supported HRM, especially through the use of web technology. The major goals of e-HRM are mainly to improve HR's administrative efficiency/to achieve cost reduction. Next to these goals, international companies seem to use the introduction of e-HRM to Standardize/ harmonize HR policies and processes.

Though e- HRM hardly helped to improve employee competences, but resulted in cost reduction and a reduction of the administrative burden.

There is a fundamental difference between HRIS and e-HR in that basically HRIS are directed towards the HR department itself. Users of these systems are mainly HR staff. These types of systems aim to improve the processes within the HR departments itself, although in order to improve the service towards the business. With e-HR, the target group is not the HR staff but people outside this department: the employees and management.

HRM services are being offered through an intranet for use by employees. The difference between HRIS and e-HR can be identified as the switch from the automation of HR services towards technological support of information on HR services.

HRM is a way of implementing HR strategies, policies, and practices in organizations through a conscious and directed support of and/or with the full use of web-technology-based channels. The word ‘implementing’ in this context has a broad meaning, such as making something work, putting something into practice, or having something realized. e-HRM, therefore, is a concept - a way of ‘doing’ HRM.

The e-HRM business solution is designed for human resources professionals and executive managers who need support to manage the work force, monitor changes and gather the information needed in decision-making. At the same time it enables all employees to participate in the process and keep track of relevant information.

The e-HRM business solution excels in:

Modularity

The solution can be accessed and used in a web browser

Security of data, protected levels of access to individual modules, records documents and their component parts

Parametric and customizability

Access to archived records and documents

User-friendly interface

Connectivity with the client's existing information system (payroll accounting, ERP, attendance registration, document systems...)

Multi-language support

Advantages of the e-HRM business solution:

Gradual implementation

Adaptability to any client

Collection of information as the basis for strategic decision-making

Integral support for the management of human resources and all other basic and support processes within the company

Prompt insight into reporting and analysis

A more dynamic workflow in the business process, productivity and employee satisfaction

A decisive step towards a paperless office

Lower business costs

e-HR Activities

We talk about using technology in HR functions. Here we focus on recruitment, selection, training, performance management and compensation.

1. e- Recruitment: e- recruitment strategy is the integration and utilization of internet technology to improve efficiency and effectiveness of the recruitment process. Most companies understand this and have begun the evolution by integrating e-recruitment strategy into their hiring process.

e-Recruitment Methods: Methods of E-recruitment are many, among those the more important ones are:

Job Boards: These are the places where the employers post jobs and search for candidates. Candidates become aware of the vacancies. One of the disadvantages is, it is generic in nature.

Employer Websites: These sites can be of the company owned sites, or a site developed by various employers. For an example, Directemployers.com is the first cooperative, employer-owned e-recruiting consortium formed by Direct Employers Association. It is a non profit organization formed by the executives from leading U.S corporations.

Professional Websites: These are for specific professions, skills and not general in nature. For an example, for HR jobs Human Resource Management sites to be visited like www.shrm.org. The professional associations will have their own site or society.

Advantages of e-Recruitment: e-recruiting offers several benefits to the firms practising it

Centralised Platform

Collects candidate information in a standard format.

Consolidate data from multiple recruitment sources.

Streamline Workflow

Automates workflow from job requisition to completion of the hiring process.

Captures and files candidate information and history for future retrieval by all users of the system.

Better Communication and Increased Productivity

Shares knowledge and information between hiring team members online in real time.

Collaboration with colleagues to increase productivity.

Less Wastage of Paper

Electronically collects and files information to reduce paper usage.

Reduces manual administrative workload.

Candidates Pool

Locates qualified candidates within a private pool of talent with precision.

Centralized database collects and provides candidate information for various units and location.

Centralised Reports

Provides consolidated HR reports for the entire organization.

Save Cost and Time

Improves productivity and reduces hiring expenses in the long run.

Drawbacks of E-Recruitment

Require being Computer Savvy: The process is restricted within computer savvy candidates.

Legal Consequences: Alike other recruitment sources this source also should be aware of the words used in the advertisements otherwise it may lead to the charge of discrimination.

Vast Pool of Applicants: This benefits the Organizations as well as it is disadvantage to them also. Because the huge database cannot be scanned in depth. Either first few candidates are called for interview or the resumes are screened based on some key words.

Non-serious Applicants: Lot of applicants forward their resumes just to know their market value.

Disclosure of Information: Candidates profile and company details are available to public. The applicants do not want their employer to know that they are looking for a change. Phone number, address information has lead to many security problems. Again the companies do not want their competitors always to know the current scenario.

Activity B:

Analyse the emerging trends in e-recruitment and prepare the report detailing the challenges and opportunities for the organization.

e- Selection: Usually it is difficult to decide where recruiting ends and selection begins. The main purpose of selection process is to distinguish individuals on the basis of important characteristics. In a changing environment, the speed of selection process becomes very important. There are many formal selection tools available to measure applicants on the characteristics:

Work Samples

Structured Interviews

Personality inventories

Situational Judgment Tests

Cognitive Ability Tests

e-selection process is a paperless process where electronic documents and information can be quickly disseminated nationwide or worldwide.

e- Performance Management: e-performance management also known as Business Intelligence (BI) or Business Performance Management is a growing field. Use of technology

in performance management leads to increment in productivity, enhances competitiveness, and motivates employees. This is possible through two ways:

Technology become a tool to facilitate the process of writing reviews or generating performance feedback.

Technology may facilitate measuring individual's performance via computer monitoring activities. Examples here include multirater appraising that supervisors or team members generate online, as well as of-the-shelf appraisal software packages that a construct an evaluation for a manager.

Technology can be applied in several ways in performance management. In the first place , routine jobs can be subject to computerized performance monitoring (CPM) system that helps generate performance data. Second , softwares are available that helps generate appraisal forms. Third, performance management system can be integrated with an overall enterprise resource planning system (ERP) software system. This helps HR professional to identify high performers, spot skill and competency gaps and to analyze pay relative to performance. With this information being available, HR manager can plan for training, coaching and education. Forth, firm intranets and internet may also help performance management process. Fifth, stand-alone software packages are a great help in performance management system. The greatest benefits of appraisal software are the elimination of paperwork and simplification of the logistics for evaluators, workers and administrators.

e-Learning: e-Learning is the use of technology to enable people to learn anytime and anywhere. e-

Learning can include training, the delivery of just-in-time information and guidance from experts. 13

e-Learning is learning that takes place in an electronically simulated environment. e-Learning, web-based training, internet-based training and computer-based training are the next-generation instruction methods being developed today. With e-Learning, users can immerse themselves in a three-dimensional environment to further enhance their learning experience. Moreover, e-Learning can be done anywhere and anytime as long as the user has the proper hardware. Today, e-Learning is fast becoming a reality through companies like Trainersoft and others.

e-Learning can be done using an internet connection, a network, an intranet, or a storage disk. It uses a variety of media like audio, text, virtual environments, video, and animation. e-Learning, in some ways, is even better than classroom learning methods as it is a one-on-one learning method, it is self-paced and it has an experiential-learning format.

As with any other forms of learning, e-Learning depends on its delivery method and content to ensure its success. For this reason, e-Learning modules have to be interesting, interactive and informative in order to be effective. Because it is computer/software based however, e-Learning has the capability of immersing its students completely within an environment most conducive to learning. This sets it apart from classroom- style learning..

Advantages of e-Learning

Lower Costs and Larger Capacity

With e-Learning, students don't have to physically attend classes, seminars or training programs. e-Learning is web-based and disk-based so participants don't have to spend a lot of time away from their work. They can choose how much time or what specific time to devote to learning the subject matter offered.

A web-based e-Learning program is a lot less expensive to maintain. e-Learning program operators need only maintain the networking infrastructure that will deliver their e-Learning content to their students and participants. This is a small investment compared to what is required to pay for instructors and training personnel in classroom-style learning. Moreover, participants need not spend money on travel and other expenses just to attend seminars and training courses.

e-Learning also allows for more participants than traditional learning methods since the number of participants is not constrained by venue limitations.

Convenient Learning

Students can fit their learning activities easily with their daily routine. They need not leave home to participate in an e-Learning program and learning does not require complex logistics. All a participant needs is a computer, internet connectivity, access to the web-based server, and if necessary, the special e-Learning software provided by the e-Learning program operators.

Easily Updated and Upgraded

e-Learning modules can be easily revised. Activities can be easily added and incorporated. The e-Learning software can also be automatically updated by connecting to the server. This is definitely a lot faster than retraining professors and reprinting books and manuals.¹⁴

Class work can be scheduled around personal and professional work

Reduces travel cost and time to and from school

Learners may have the option to select learning materials that meets their level of knowledge and interest

Learners can study wherever they have access to a computer and Internet

Self-paced learning modules allow learners to work at their own pace

Flexibility to join discussions in the bulletin board threaded discussion areas at any hour, or visit with classmates and instructors remotely in chat rooms

Different learning styles are addressed and facilitation of learning occurs through varied activities

Development of computer and Internet skills that are transferable to other facets of learner's lives

Successfully completing online or computer-based courses builds self-knowledge and self-confidence and encourages students to take responsibility for their learning

Disadvantages of e-Learning

Unmotivated learners or those with poor study habits may fall behind

Lack of familiar structure and routine may take getting used to

Students may feel isolated or miss social interaction

Instructor may not always be available on demand

Slow or unreliable Internet connections can be frustrating

Managing learning software can involve a learning curve

Some courses such as traditional hands-on courses can be difficult to simulate

Knowing e-learning advantages and disadvantages helps with learning software selection as well as online distance learning programs structure and selection. It is important to know the merits and demerits of e-learning to make a decision.

Challenges before HRM

The HR Managers of today may find it difficult because of the rapidly changing business environment and therefore they should update their knowledge and skills by looking at the organization's need and objectives.

Managing the Vision: Vision of the organization provides the direction to business strategy and helps managers to evaluate management practices and make decisions. So vision management becomes the integral part of the process of Man management in times to come .

Internal Environment: Creating an environment which is responsive to external changes, providing satisfaction to the employees and sustaining through culture and systems is a challenging task.

Changing Industrial Relations: Both the workers and managers have to be managed by the same HRM Philosophy and this is going to be a difficult task for the managers of tomorrow.

Building Organizational Capability: Even in the adverse circumstances the employees have to be made to live in psychological state of readiness to continually change.

Job Design and Organization Structure: Instead of depending on foreign concepts we need to focus on understanding the job, technology and the people involved in carrying out the tasks.

Managing the Large Work Force: Management of large workforce poses the biggest problem as the workers are conscious of their rights.

Employee Satisfaction: Managers should be aware of techniques to motivate their employees so that their higher level needs can be satisfied.

Modern Technology: There will be unemployment due to modern technology and this could be corrected by assessing manpower needs and finding alternate employment.

Computerized Information System: This is revolutionary in managerial decision making and is having impact on coordination in the organization.

Managing Human Resource Relations: As the workforce comprises of both educated and uneducated, managing the relations will be of great challenge. One of the challenges HR managers face is issues of up gradation of the skill set through training and development in the face of high attrition. Indian companies are recognizing their responsibilities to enhance the employee's opportunity to develop skills and abilities for full performance within the position and for career advancement.

HRM Practices In India

India's Changing HRM Horizon

The outlook to Human Resource Management in India has witnessed sea-change in last two decades. Economic liberalization in 1991 created a hyper-competitive environment. As international firms entered the Indian market bringing with them innovative and fierce competitiveness, Indian companies were forced to adopt and implement innovative changes in their HR practices. Increasing demand for skilled performers forced the companies to shift focus on attracting and retaining high-performing employees in a competitive marketplace.

Emphasis on Employees: Human Resource policies, forming the framework for the culture in the business management, create awareness towards the need to achieve the business goals in the best possible and

ethical manner. Indian companies have realized that in today's competitive business milieu, the quality of people you employ can make all the difference. In the last few years, the Human Resource has become a key player in strategic planning – it has come a long way from traditional HR operations like managing the recruitment process, handling staff appraisals.

HRM Challenges: One of the challenges HR managers face is issues of up gradation of the skill set through training and development in the face of high attrition. Indian companies are recognizing their responsibilities to enhance the employee's opportunity to develop skills and abilities for full performance within the position and for career advancement.

Progressive HR Policies: Today, most Indian companies are committed to providing equal employment opportunities for both men and women. The employers are increasingly realizing the value of trained human resource, especially women in India. Some organizations are changing their HR policies to stick with their valuable employees. MNCs like Pepsico are providing flexibility so that female employees at various life stages could benefit from these policies like working from a different city, sabbatical from corporate life, and extended maternity leave.

Entrepreneurship by Employees: India Inc. is encouraging 'intrapreneurs' or employees who have ideas that could potentially become a venture. Companies like Pepsico, NIIT, and Adobe are actively promoting practice of entrepreneurship by employees within the organization. Human Resource Management has taken a leading role in encouraging corporate social responsibility activities at all levels. Companies like Wipro inculcate corporate social responsibility values amongst its workforce right at the beginning during the induction process. Corporate presentations and keeping employees updated through regular newsletters are the instruments used by HR to keep employees energized about the organization's socially responsible initiatives.

Over the last decade, India's vast manpower has played an instrumental role in its economic success story. Indeed, the success of Indian companies is not based on superior access to raw materials or technology or patents, but fundamentally upon human skills. The synergy between the strategic planning and innovative HRM practices will be important as Indian Industries embarks itself on the global journey.

Self Assessment Questions -

1. What do you understand by human resource management? Why is it needed?
2. Explain the role of HR manager in present times?
3. Discuss the recent trends or emerging issues in HRM?
4. Discuss the changing role of HRM. In which particular business areas HR can play its role?
5. What are the challenges faced by HR managers in present time?

Growth & Development of Human Resource Accounting

Research into Human Resource accounting began in the 1960's by Rensis Likert. It supported long term planning on diverse qualitative human resource variables yielding superior benefits in long run. Human resource Accounting is the outcome of numerous research studies conducted in the field of accounting and finance. Human resource as an asset if positioned & nurtured in the right direction may realize its full

potenti
al.

Lately, the Behavioral scientists criticized the conventional accounting practice of valuing human resource along with physical resources and stressed on the concept of assigning monetary value to human resource of the organization. They advocated that any expenses incurred on the development of human resources should be treated as capital expenditure as in the long run it gives benefits which can be measured in monetary terms.

Eric Falmholtz divided the development of Human Resource Accounting into five stages, which can be summed up as follows:-

First Stage (1960 – 66) – This symbolizes the beginning of Human Resource Accounting where the focus was to derive the concepts of Human Resource Accounting from other studies like economics etc.

Second Stage – (1966 – 71) – The objective here was to assess some models that would cover both costs models & monetary & non – monetary value of Human Resource .

Third Stag - (1971 – 76) – Here noticeable significance in the field of Human Resource Accounting grew leading to number of researches in the field. The focal point was the application of Human Resource Accounting in business organizations.

Fourth Stage - (1976 – 80) – This period saw the collapse of the concept of Human Resource Accounting as the organizations were not prepared to invest time , energy and most importantly the funds needed to research further deep into the concepts of Human Resource Accounting.

Fifth Stage - (1980 Onwards) – The explosion of service economies in developed countries brought about a renewal of interest in Human Resource Accounting. And further in mid 90's the application of Human Resource Accounting to business management gained greater impetus.

Concept of Human Resource Accounting

Meaning & Definition

The concept of human resource accounting can be better understood by following important definitions given by eminent authors in the accounting field.

M.N. Baker defines, “H.R.A. is the term applied by the accountancy profession to quantify the cost and value of employees to their employing organization”.

K.Foley Defined “Human Resource Accounting is the measurement of the cost and value of people for organization.”

Human Resource Management

Prof. Davidson Defined “Human Resource Accounting is the term used to describe a variety of proposals that seek to report and emphasize the importance of human resource knowledgeable , trained and loyal employees in a company earning process and total assets”.

The American Accounting Society Committees on Human Resource Accounting defined it as follows:-

“Human Resource Accounting is the process of identifying and measuring data about human resources and communicating this information to interested parties.”

Flamholtz defines “Human Resource Accounting as the measurement and reporting of the cost and value of people in organizational resources.”

In short, the definition of Human Resource Accounting brings out following characteristic features:

Need and Importance of Human Resource Accounting

The need for Human Resource Accounting felt largely as a result of the emerging concern for human relations management in industry. The very importance of Human Resource Accounting can be summed up through following major points –

- (a) Human Resource Accounting helps management in acquiring placing and in making effective utilization of human resources.
- (b) To retain the qualified employees
- (c) It aids in deciding the transfers , promotion , training etc of human resources.
- (d) It serves as a tool to measure and compare the expenditure incurred for imparting the training to employees and in turn the benefits derived by the firm.
- (e) Human Resource Accounting helps to improve the profile of the enterprise and its image.

Objectives of Human Resource Accounting

Putting in a capsule the main objectives of Human Resource Accounting are to:

Figure 15.2

Human Resource Valuation

Human Resource Accounting can be explained in three ways :-

1. MONETARY MODELS – The Models which are created using monetary variable are called monetary models.

(A) COST BASED MODELS

(i) Historical Cost Model :- This Model was developed by Willim C. Pyle , R. Lee Brummet and Eric.

G. Flamholtz. This is also called original cost method or outlay cost method. In this method actualcost incurred on recruiting , selecting , hiring , training and developing the human resource of the organization are capitalized and amortized over the expected useful life of human resources. If the human assets are liquidated pre-maturely the whole of the amount not written off is charged to the income of the year in which year the assets is liquidated. If the useful life is recognized to be longer than originally expected revision are affected in the amortization schedule. The un-expired value is shown in balance sheet as investment in human assets.

Merits:

- (i) it is a simple method.
- (ii) This method can be used for evaluating return on investment in human resources.
- (iii) This method is objective rather than being subjective.

Limitations :

- (i) Accurate measurement not possible.
- (ii) It is difficult to estimate the number of years an Employee is going to be with the firm. Hence there is a problem of estimate the number of years over which the capital expenditure is to be amortized.

(ii) Replacement Cost Model: The replacement cost method of valuation of human resource has been developed by Eric G. Flamholtz. Under this method value to an organization of an individual's services is reflected by the amount that the organization would have to pay to replace these services.

Merits : -

- (i) It considers the current value of the human resource.
- (ii) Replacement cost are present oriented.
- (iii) Replacement cost is better than historic cost.

Limitations :

- (i) There may be no identical replacement of the existing human resources.

(ii) The valuation of human resources based on replacement cost is affected by subjective consideration.

(iii) **Opportunity Cost Model:** This method was suggested by Hekimian and Jones. This method is based on an economist's concept of opportunity cost. Under the opportunity cost method, the value of an employee in his alternative use is determined. This value is taken as the basis for estimating the value of human resources employed by the organization.

Merits :

(i) Opportunity cost approach gives more optimum allocation of personnel.

(ii) It provides a quantitative base for evaluating human assets.

Limitation :

(i) This method is expensive.

(ii) The measure of reliability of opportunity cost is less.

(iv) **Standard Cost Method:** David Watson suggested this approach. Under this method, employees of an organization are categorized into different groups as per their hierarchical positions. The standard cost is fixed for each category and then their value is calculated. The standard cost of recruiting, placing, training, and developing per grade of employee is developed and established and made up to date every year. The standard method provides easy implementation.

Replacement Cost Chart

* Recruitment

* Selection

* Hiring

* Placement

* Promotion

* Training

* Development

* Separation pay

* loss of efficiency

due to vacant post

during search

* Transfer

(B). VALUE BASED MODELS

(i) Lev and Schwartz Present Value of Future Earning Model. s

(ii) Flamholtz Stochastic Rewards Valuation Model.

(i) Present Value of Future Earnings Model: This model is suggested by Branch Lev and Aba. Schwartz. This model is also known as compensation model. What is the present value of an employee? In order to find out the present value we take the discount rate. This discount rate is normally that rate which is cost of capital. Each and every employee is classified according to his age and efficiency. Then we find out what is average income of an employee in different groups. Then we calculate the income of every group up to the date of retirement. Then we apply the cost of capital rate. Then we arrive at value of human assets of the group.

Lev and Schwartz has given the following formulas

$V_x \square T$

$$\frac{\sum_{t \square x} I(t)}{(1 \square r)^{(t \square x)}}$$

Where

V_x = The human capital value of a person X year old. $I(+)$ = The person's annual earnings up to the retirement r = A discount rate specific to the person

T = Retirement age

Merits :-

- (i) This method depends upon future earnings capacity of an employee.
- (ii) This method is depending upon the present value of future earnings capacity so this method appears to be most logical.
- (iii) Discount rate is based on cost of capital, which appears to be fair.

Demerits :-

- (i) The method does not take in to consideration that the employees leave the organization due to number of reason other than death & retirement.
- (ii) This method ignores change in the profession of an employee due to age , health etc.

(ii) Flamttltz’s Stoochastic Rewars Valuation Model: The model is based on the presumption that a person’s value to an organization depends upon the position he holds in the organization. This model gives five steps for valuing an individual in an organization.

- (i) Find out the expected service life of an individual in any organization.
- (ii) Identify how much time he will remain on particular status.
- (iii) Estimate the value derived by the organization when a person holds a particular position.
- (iv) Estimate the probability of occupying each possible mutually exclusive status at specified future time.
- (v) Discount (at a predetermined rate) the expected service rewards to their present value. The Model has used the following formulae.

n

$$\sum (RV) \sum$$

$$t \sum 1 [\frac{R_i P (R_i)}{\sum_{i=1}^m}]$$

$$(1 - r)^t$$

$\sum (RV)$ Expected Realized value

R_i = Amount of service received

(R) at every possible state or status

$P(R_i)$ = Status Possible expected service to be received by the organization

T = time period.

M = Retirement Stage

$(1+r)$ = Rate of Depreciation for money

Merits :-

- (i) This method takes into account the probability of a person's career movement and of his leaving the organization prior to his retirement or death.
- (ii) The model combines both monetary and non-monetary variables.

Demerits :

- (i) It is expensive.
- (ii) It is very difficult to estimate that for how much period an employee will continue in an organization.

Dr. S.K. Chakraborty's Model of Human Resource Valuation: -

According to Dr. Chakraborty human assets should be included in Balance sheet on assets side under the heading "Investments" He is of the opinion that if we include it in the heading fixed Assets it will create problems like depreciation, capital gains or losses , etc. The value of human resources on a group basis can be found out by multiplying the average salary of the group with the average tenure of employment of

the employee in that group. He has suggested that recruitment , hiring , selection , development and training costs of each employee should be recorded separately , it can be treated as deferred revenue expenditure to be written off over the expected average stay of the employee in the organization and the deferred position should be shown in balance sheet of the organization. If there is a premature exit on account of death , retirement etc then the balance on the deferred revenue account for the year attributable to that person should be written off against the income of the year of exit itself.

2. NON-MONETARY MODEL

(A) Likert's Casual, Intervening and End-Result Variable Model :-

This model is based on behavioural variable. This model was developed by Rensis Likert and David G. Bowers of U.S.A. The model is comprised of three variables – Casual , intervening and end results.

- (i) **Casual Variable** – The casual variables are independent variables which can be directly changed by the organization and its management and which in turn determine the course of developments within an organization.
- (ii) The intervening variables reflect the internal state, health and performance capabilities of the organization e.g. the loyalties, attitudes, motivation, performance goals and perceptions of all members and their collective capacity for effective action , interaction , communications and decision

– making.

- (iii) The end result variables are the dependent variable, which reflect the result achieved by the organization such as its productivity costs, scrap loss, growth, share of market & earnings.

Merits :-

- (i) Model is based on non-monetary variables.
- (ii) The model is highly useful in decision making.

Demerits :-

- (i) The degree of objectivity is less
- (ii) The degree of reliability is low.
- (iii) The method is expensive.

3. STATISTICAL BASED METHODS

Under statistical based method of Human resources no accounting is involved. The statistical information regarding human resource is collected and they are presented in annual reports. They may be of following types:-

- (i) Monthly Statistics on.
 - (a) Recruitment Costs
 - (b) Selection Costs
 - (c) Training Costs
 - (d) Special Development programme costs
 - (e) Worker's education programmes
 - (f) Auxiliary costs such as canteen, medical and other fringe benefits
- (ii) Total Human Resource Investment analyzed workmen into
 - (a) Personnel Officers, staff and workmen
 - (b) Department wise
 - (c) Expenses Category wise
- (iii) Periodical change in Human Resources Investment.
- (iv) Statement of contribution factor separately for officers, staff and workmen.

- (v) Statement on human resource cost co-efficient (human resource investment human resource current cost) separately for officers, staff & Workmen.
- (vi) Times rate of return analysis.
- (vii) Statement of human resource performance index showing separately for officers , staff & workmen.
- (viii) Statement of per capital Human Resource performance index showing separately for officers, staff & workmen and also total.
- (ix) Age wise Service Status
- (x) Monetary value of service statutory
- (xi) Statistics on employee turnover.
- (xiii) Any other statistics relevant to the organization.

Human Resource Reporting in India

In India, reporting practices of Human Resource Accounting is extremely low. A few companies do report in their annual reports. The reporting of Human Resource Accounting is in some sentences. Some Companies furnish information about number of employees working in the organization, how many working hours have lost, what is the situation of industrial relation etc.

Both Public sector and private sector companies have used economic value approach instead of cost approach. Most of the companies have used Lev and Schwartz model. They have Lev and Schwartz model in modified way, which is similar to Flamholtz model. It has been discovered that most likely variety of the companies is replacement cost model, Human resources reporting is not because there is no legal compulsion by Indian Companies Act 1956. There is also problem in measuring Human Resources.

Human Resource Accounting has been reported by above – mentioned companies as a supplementary information in their annual reports , such reporting by companies are audited. The companies have classified their employees, age wise, they have further classified them in managers, executives, supervisors, Artisans, clerical staff etc.

Some Companies in India shows human Resource development cost i.e. training and development cost in detail while some corporation are showing them in short, some shows them in “Director’s Report or chairman speech.”

Productivity / performance statistics of human resource have been presented by some companies in detail. Average employee cost is shown by few companies only.

Appreciations and Awards received by the companies have been shown by the companies under the heading “High light” or Director’s Report or elsewhere in the annual reports of the Companies Highlight’s.

For purpose of calculating the present value of future earning of employees , all the companies have adopted a discount rate , which is not common. Majority of the companies adopted 12%.

Some of the companies have not mentioned the purpose for which they are reporting HRA information in their annual reports. Whereas some companies have clearly mentioned their objective of reporting human resource data. It seems that some companies report HRA for image building purposes. Some companies have also given additional information as regarding number of employees , average salary , average age of employees , average production per employee etc.

Problems in HRA Reporting

1. Human Resource Accounting is shown as supplementary information in the annualreports , which has no significance.
2. All the companies who are reporting Human Resource Accounting have used Lev and Schwartz model but this model is suffering from some drawbacks. One it has assured state promotion policy and consistent average salary to all the employees in a particular group. These two assumptions are far from reality , difference in skill , experience qualifications and increasing importance of employees union often lead to change in these policies.
3. Though human capital plays an important role in any organization , there is a wide spread , disagreement regarding the reorganization and valuation of human resource as assets on generally the assets is one which fulfills the following three criteria. They are (i) the entity should have legally enforceable claim to it. (ii) It should be owned by the entity (iii) the entity should posses it with the expectation of deriving services from it in future HR are not fulfilling any criteria. As such thereis a problem in recognizing human resources as assets.
4. Proper matching of costs with revenue is not possible unless the costs on the recruitment training and development of personnel are capitalized over their effective service lives. It is so because the benefits from such expenses are usually derived over a period beyond the year of payment. However in a number of cases, the earnings potential of employees may not depend upon the expenditure incurred by the firms for the purpose. But it depends upon behaviour aspects like skill

, motivation group loyalty capacity for effective interaction and decision making etc , to influence the end results of an enterprises effectively.

5. The very idea of showing human resource as an asset on the balance sheet of a firm tends to be arbitrary for this purpose as per the methods available, human resource are to be valued either on the basis of cost incurred by a firm on recruitment trainings etc or replacement cost. In both the methods cost is taken as the value of human assets. But this hardly represent the real value of personnel in particular and the firm in general. The other method like discounted wage, and salaries method, economic value method, and opportunity cost method, involves the element of subjectivity in valuing the human resources.
6. Yet another difficulty regarding HR is Quantification and pricing of employees in respect of jobs which do not yield any physical output. Determination of probabilities of the expected services of the employees is also a difficult task. These practical difficulties are subject to the influence of age qualification, the previous experience point of first entry, employment period and turn over as well as the organizational pulls and pressures on different categories of employees.
7. In all the methods, the salaries earned by the employees are taken as the basis for valuing human resources. Thus the career movement of employees either within the organization or elsewhere in the other organization is kept outside the purview of valuation. Since the employees make constant trials to occupy higher position during their effective service life, any valuation process without considering this way tend to be less meaningful.
8. The provision of existing tax laws, do not recognize the amortized portion of capitalized human resource value as deductible expenses for computing income. Even if attempts are made to amend the existing provision of tax laws there is a greater amount of scope to misuse the facility as the employers may adopt fictitious method to undertake the profitability of their business and may show unrealistic value of the firm.

In India, human resource accounting has not been introduced so far as a system. The companies Act 1956, doesnot require, furnishing of any significant information about human resource in financial statement of the Companies. The Institute of Chartered Accountant of India has also developed 18 Accounting Standards. The accounting standards are applicable to public and private sector companies & large borrowers of funds from banks and financial institutions in the corporate sector. It is the duty of the members Institute of Chartered Accountants of India to ensure that the accounting standards are implemented in the presentation of financial statements covered by their audit report. All these accounting standards are quite important from point of view of measurement and disclosure of accounting information.

Summary

In today's globalized world it has become imperative to give necessary consideration to the Human Resource of the organizations. Without human resource no other resource can function effectively, therefore Human Resource has been recognized as a crucial part of total organization worth. Human Resource Accounting facilitates the management of people as organizational Resources. Human Resource Accounting in application of accounting concepts & methods to management of Human Resources it deals with investments in people and with economic results of those investments. Human Resource Accounting field underwent a number of stages beginning from 1960 to till date to assume the status of a fully fledged subject. It greatly helps the management of the business organizations in acquiring, placing and inmaking effective utilization of human resources. Human Resource Accounting has its number of models under the purview of monetary, non - monetary and statistical methods. But the plight of Human Resource Accounting in India is extremely poor and both public and private sector companies do not pay much head to Human Resource Reporting. Therefore, the government needs to take steps in the right directions for promotion of Human Resource Accounting Practices in India.

Question Bank

1. What do you mean by "HRA ". Explain & Detail.
 2. Classify the various stages in development of Human Resource Accounting.
 3. Discuss the importance of HRA in today's globalized world.
 4. Write short note on Human Resource Reporting in India.
 5. What are the different valuation models of HRA ? State their merits and demerits.
-

PREVIOUS QUESTION PAPERS

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Second Semester MBA Degree Examination – June 2019

Human Resource Management & Audit

Time: 2 Hours

Max. Marks: 50

SECTION-

(8x1=8)

Note: Answer any EIGHT questions. Each question carries ONE mark.

1. Human Resource management helps improve
 - a) Production
 - b) Productivity
 - c) Profits
 - d) Power

2. The actual achievements compared with the objectives of the job is –
 - a) Job performance
 - b) Job Evaluation
 - c) Job description
 - d) None of the above

3. Majority of the disputes in industry are related to the problem of
 - a) Wages
 - b) Salaries
 - c) Benefits
 - d) All of the above

4. The following type of recruitment process is said to be a costly affair
 - a) Internal recruitment
 - b) External recruitment
 - c) Cost is same for both types

5. The basic managerial skill(s) is (are)
 - a) To supervise
 - b) To stimulate
 - c) To motivate
 - d) All of the above

6. The process which is continuous and stops only when the organization ceases to exist is
 - a) Training
 - b) Job Evaluation
 - c) Hiring
 - d) All of the above

Human Resource Management

7. _____ can be defined as a written record of the duties, responsibilities and conditions of job.
 - a) Job description
 - b) Job Specification
 - c) Job Profile
 - d) None of the above
8. The following is concerned with developing a pool of candidates in line with the human resources
 - a) Development
 - b) Training
 - c) Recruitment
 - d) All of the above
9. In collective bargaining, the negotiation process starts with _____.
 - a) Understanding and interpreting on existing contract.
 - b) Submission of demand of the trade union to the management.
 - c) Circulation of the terms of the contract and agreement reached to all the employees.
 - d) Intervention of the government or its representative to help resolve the dispute.
10. Indian Infotech Ltd. has officers in Mumbai and New York. Its compensation structure is such that software developers working in these two locations have different wage packages. This wage differentiation may be termed as an example of _____ differences.
 - a) Location differences
 - b) Cultural differences
 - c) Time zone differences
 - d) None of these

SECTION-B

(4x7=28)

Note: Answer any FOUR questions. Each question carries SEVEN marks.

11. Describe the nature and scope of human resource management.
12. Discuss the process of performance appraisal?
13. Elaborate on the concept and preparation of job descriptions.
14. Compare and contrast the advantages and disadvantages of the internal and external sources of work force recruitment.
15. Explain the various internal and external factors influencing compensation.
16. Describe the grievance handling procedure in detail.

SECTION-C (Compulsory)

(1x14=14)

17. Samsui Company is an engineering company with employee strength of 1,000. The company has a system of incentive linked monthly productivity bonus for the shop floor employees, which serves the purpose of rewarding good work. The HR director, Mr.

Inderjit has been facing a dilemma, how to evaluate the performance of the middle management and how to link it with productivity. After deliberate discussions with individual managers, he develops a plan. The plan is designed to enhance team work and provide incentives for improvement and excellence among middle level managers. Briefly the pay will be split into two components. The first consists of 80% of original salary, which will be a fixed component and will be determined as before. The second component of 20% will be flexible and will depend upon the ability of each team as a whole to show minimum of 5% improvement in their respective areas. The scheme when discussed with managers, received a number of negative remarks. One manager said that why should their performance depend upon the performance of other members of the team. The new pay scheme makes them team players first and specialists in their areas next. Another objection was that why the good persons in the team should suffer if the other members were not measuring upto the expectations. Moreover, there are a number of external factors which affect the individual and collective performance. For example, if a product suddenly goes out of demand affecting marketability, why should the concerned marketing team be penalized for something beyond its control.

Now Mr. Inderjit is in a perplexed situation. The company has been the trend setter in executive compensation in Indian industry as they have been paying the best. Will the new plan ensure that it remains that way? If the plan succeeds Samsui sets another trend in executive compensation. But how should he see this plan through?

Questions :

1. Do you think it is proper to evaluate manager on the basis of productivity?
2. In your opinion, individual performance or team performance is the most suitable criteria for incentive plans?
